

Recognition

case-studies

indicators

methodologies

SYMPOSIUM

SPATIAL JUSTICE IN PRACTICE

tools

Distributive

comparisons

frameworks

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS
30 NOV | 1&5 DEC
2023

pedagogies

Procedural

UP2030

SYMPOSIUM

**SPATIAL
JUSTICE
IN
PRACTICE**

**BOOK OF ABSTRACTS
NOVEMBER-DECEMBER
2023**

COLOPHON

Spatial Justice in Practice Symposium

Faculty of Architecture & the Built Environment (BK)
Delft University of Technology, The Netherlands
Julianalaan 134, 2628 BL, Delft. Berlagezaal, West Wing.

Organising committee

Roberto Rocco (TUD)
Caroline Newton (TUD)
Juliana Gonçalves (TUD)
Marcin Dabrowski (TUD)
Hugo Lopez (TUD)
Andrés Maglione (University of Naples Federico II)
Russell Smith (Winston-Salem State University)
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Booklet designed by Hugo Lopez, Roberto Rocco and Andrés Maglione

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The book of abstracts compiles a total of 127 abstracts presented during a three-day event held in November and December 2023 at the Faculty of Architecture and the Built Environment of the Delft University of Technology.

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VENUE | 30/NOV

Faculty of Architecture and the Built Environment
TU Delft, Julianalaan 134, 2628 BL, Delft, The Netherlands.

Note: All times indicated in this booklet are CET (Central European Standard Time (GMT+1))

Delft

Station

Bridge

Small bridge

Faculty of Architecture

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ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

We extend our heartfelt gratitude to all the participants, speakers, students and volunteers who contributed to the Symposium 'Spatial Justice in Practice: Benchmarking Spatial Justice in Policymaking, Planning, and Design' with 127 accepted abstracts from all over the world, addressing a wide variety of topics connected to spatial justice.

We would like to express our sincere appreciation for the TU Delft Design for Values Institute (DDfV) for supporting the organisation of this symposium and for their commitment to advancing the understanding and application of values in design and engineering, and for having justice as their core theme in 2023-2024. <https://www.delftdesignforvalues.nl>

Special thanks to the Horizon Europe project, UP2030, for their support. UP2030's incredible team of talented professionals and their dedication to promoting socio-technical transitions and addressing climate neutrality targets through urban planning and design, with spatial justice at its core, has been instrumental in shaping this symposium. <https://up2030-he.eu>

We also acknowledge the contributions of all the researchers, scholars, and practitioners who have tirelessly worked towards developing frameworks, indicators, and benchmarks for the practical implementation of spatial justice. Your collective efforts are driving positive change and inspiring more equitable and just futures.

Lastly, we express our gratitude to the broader academic and professional community for their ongoing commitment to the exploration and advancement of spatial justice, which remains a critical dimension in addressing contemporary societal challenges.

Thank you for your unwavering dedication and support.

The Organising Committee

This symposium is an integral part of the **UP2030 Urban Planning and Design Ready for 2030**, funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. UP2030 has received funding from the Horizon Innovation Actions under the grant agreement n° 101096405.

THE DIMENSIONS OF SPATIAL JUSTICE*

RECOGNITIONAL Justice

Recognition of needs,
interests, histories and
aspirations.

Spatial Justice

DISTRIBUTIVE Justice

The fair distribution
of the burdens and
benefits of our human
association.

PROCEDURAL Justice

The fairness in
decision-making,
participation and co-
design.

*Although a specific definition of Spatial Justice lacks consensus, at TU Delft, we conceptualise it as comprising three interconnected and mutually reinforcing dimensions: distributive, recognitional, and procedural.

INTRODUCTION TO THE SYMPOSIUM

The Symposium 'Spatial Justice in Practice: Benchmarking Spatial Justice in Policymaking, Planning and Design' (30 NOV at TU Delft, 1 and 5 DEC 2023 Online) aims to foster discussions and exchange that allow us to take a step further in the formulation of frameworks, indicators and benchmarks for the practical application of the concept.

While a definite definition of Spatial Justice is elusive, at the TU Delft, we conceptualise it as having three interconnected and mutually reinforcing dimensions: distributive (the fair and equitable distribution of the burdens and benefits of our human association); procedural (the justice found in planning and design procedures, the justice in decision-making processes, the inclusion of vulnerable groups in planning processes) and recognition (the social recognition and validation of disadvantaged groups' specific needs, identities, cultural heritage, histories and experiences). Spatial Justice is a core dimension of transitions to sustainability, encompassing issues such as climate justice, mobility justice, participation, democracy, access to public goods and more.

Benchmarking spatial justice involves developing methods and indicators to assess and compare the levels of justice across different regions or communities. It provides a valuable framework for identifying spatial inequalities, evaluating policy interventions, and guiding decision-making processes towards a more equitable and just future.

This symposium is organised by the TU Delft Centre for the Just City in the framework of UP2030 <https://up2030-he.eu>. This Horizon Europe project aims to support cities in driving the socio-technical transitions required to meet their climate neutrality targets by leveraging urban planning and design. It has spatial justice as one of its main frameworks for policy and project design, implementation, and assessment.

The organising committee is composed by:

Roberto Rocco (TU Delft)
Juliana Gonçalves (TU Delft)
Caroline Newton (TU Delft)
Marcin Dabrowski (TU Delft)
Hugo Lopez (TU Delft)
Andrés Maglione (University of Naples Federico II)
Russell Smith (Winston-Salem State)
Shahryar Sarabi (University of Utrecht)

DAY 1: Thursday | 30/NOV | PROGRAMME

PHYSICAL AT THE FACULTY OF ARCHITECTURE & BUILT ENVIRONMENT
JULIANALAAN 134, 2628BL, DELFT (15 MINUTE WALK FROM DELFT TRAIN STATION) +
ONLINE ON ZOOM

These are the main highlights of the programme at TU Delft. BZ 1 and 2 stand for BERLAGEZAAL 1 & 2. (Rooms Berlage, where most of the conference takes place).

9:00 Registration - Berlagezaal BZ1			
9:30 Opening BZ1			
9:45 Keynote BZ1			
10:30 Cities Panel BZ1			
11:10 Track 1 BZ1	11:10 Track 2 BZ2	11:10 Track 3 ROOM U	11:10 Track 4 ROOM K
12:10 LUNCH BZ2			
13:10 DdfV WORKSHOP BZ1			
13:40 Track 5 ROOM K	13:40 Track 6 ROOM U	13:40 Track 7 BZ2	13:40 Track 8 BZ1
14:50 Track 9 BZ1	14:50 Track 10 BZ2	14:50 Track 11 ROOM U	14:50 Track 12 ROOM K
15:50 Coffee Break			
16:20 Track 13 ROOM K	16:20 Track 14 ROOM U	16:20 Track 15 BZ2	16:20 Track 16 BZ1
17:20 PLENARY			
18:00 DRINKS			

DAY 2: Friday | 01/DEC | PROGRAMME

16:00-18:45 (CET/ AMSTERDAM)

ONLINE ON ZOOM: [LINK](#)

The online sessions are organised on Zoom, using break-out rooms as parallel tracks. Please join the break-out room indicated in the programme for your abstract.

16:00 OPENING			
16:05-16:25 KEYNOTE			
16:25 Track 17 CITIES	16:25 Track 18 CITIES	16:25 Track 19 PRACTICE BASED	16:25 Track 20 PRACTICE BASED
17:25 Break			
17:35 Track 21 CITIES	17:35 Track 22 PhD	17:35 Track 23 PhD	17:35 Track 24 PhD
18:35 Plenary & conclusion			

DAY 3: Tuesday | 05/DEC | PROGRAMME

16:00-18:45 (CET/ AMSTERDAM)

ONLINE ON ZOOM: [LINK](#)

16:00 OPENING			
16:05-16:25 KEYNOTE			
16:25 Track 25 ACADEMIC	16:25 Track 26 ACADEMIC	16:25 Track 27 ACADEMIC	16:25 Track 28 ACADEMIC
17:25 Break			
17:35 Track 29 ACADEMIC	17:35 Track 30 ACADEMIC	17:35 Track 31 ACADEMIC	17:35 Track 32 ACADEMIC
18:35 Plenary & conclusion			

PROGRAMME OVERVIEW

DAY 1 | 30 NOVEMBER

LOCATION: BERLAGEZALEN 1&2, Room U, Room K

- 9:00 Registration + Coffee Berlagezalen 1 & 2**
Registration at the entrance of the Berlagezalen located at the Urbanism wing of the Faculty of Architecture. Address: Julianalaan 134, 2628 BL Delft.
- 9:30 Opening Berlagezaal 1 (BZ1) [LINK](#)**
Welcome and housekeeping (Organising committee).
Jackie Ashkin, spoken word artist & social anthropologist.
- 9:45 Keynote BZ1 [LINK](#)**
Alexandre Apsan Frediani, International Institute for Environment & Development.
- 10:30 Cities Panel BZ1 [LINK](#)**
- 11:10 Parallel tracks: Tracks 1 to 4**
Track 1: Berlagezaal 1 [LINK](#)
Track 2: Berlagezaal 2 [LINK](#)
Track 3: Room U [LINK](#)
Track 4: Room K [LINK](#)
- 12:10 LUNCH Berlagezaal 2 (BZ2)**
- 13:10 Delft design for Values Workshop BZ1**
- 13:40 Parallel tracks: Tracks 5 to 8**
Track 5: Room K [LINK](#)
Track 6: Room U [LINK](#)
Track 7: Berlagezaal 2 [LINK](#)
Track 8: Berlagezaal 1 [LINK](#)
- 14:50 Parallel tracks: Tracks 9 to 12**
Track 9 Berlagezaal 1 [LINK](#)
Track 10 Berlagezaal 2 [LINK](#)
Track 11 Room U [LINK](#)
Track 12 Room K [LINK](#)
- 15:50 Coffe Break**
- 16:20 Parallel tracks: Tracks 13 to 16**
Track 13 Room K [LINK](#)
Track 14 Room U [LINK](#)
Track 15 Berlagezaal 2 [LINK](#)
Track 16 Berlagezaal 1 [LINK](#)
- 17:20 Plenary conversation: Agendas for Research and Action [LINK](#)**
Open conversation on the takeaways from the day
- 18:00 Cocktail**

DAY 2 | 1 DECEMBER

LOCATION: ONLINE ([LINK](#))

- 16:00 **Opening**
 Juliana Gonçalves
- 16:05 **Keynote**
 TBC
- 16:25 **Parallel panels: Tracks 17 to 20**
 Track 17 Breakout room 1
 Track 18 Breakout room 2
 Track 19 Breakout room 3
 Track 20 Breakout room 4
- 17:25 **Break**
- 17:35 **Parallel panels: Tracks 21 to 24**
 Track 21 Breakout room 1
 Track 22 Breakout room 2
 Track 23 Breakout room 3
 Track 24 Breakout room 4
- 18:35 **Plenary conversation: Agendas for Research and Action**
 Open conversation on the takeaways from the day
- 18:45 **End**

DAY 3 | 5 DECEMBER

LOCATION: ONLINE ([LINK](#))

- 16:00 **Opening**
 Caroline Newton
- 16:05 **Keynote**
 Behnam Taebi, Full Professor of Energy & Climate Ethics
- 16:25 **Parallel panels: Tracks 25 to 28**
 Track 25 Breakout room 1
 Track 26 Breakout room 2
 Track 27 Breakout room 3
 Track 28 Breakout room 4
- 17:25 **Break**
- 17:30 **Parallel panels: Tracks 29 to 32**
 Track 29 Breakout room 1
 Track 30 Breakout room 2
 Track 31 Breakout room 3
 Track 32 Breakout room 4
- 18:35 **Plenary conversation: Agendas for Research and Action**
 Open conversation on the takeaways from the day
- 18:45 **End**

PRESENTATION GUIDELINES | PHYSICAL

Participants are required to give a concise and engaging 7-minute pitch about their research idea with the aim to facilitate meaningful discussions during the panel. All participants are required to read all abstracts being presented at their session beforehand.

Guideline for the pitch structure:

Opening (1 slide):

Start with a brief personal introduction, including your name and affiliation. Provide context for your research idea by mentioning its relevance to the conference theme or the field of study.

Research Question (1 slide):

Clearly state your primary research question. Make it succinct and to the point. If applicable, introduce any sub-research questions that support your main inquiry.

Methodology (1 slide):

Briefly outline the research methodology or approach you plan to employ to answer your question. Highlight any innovative or unique aspects of your methodology that set it apart from existing approaches.

Results (if available, 1 or 2 slides):

Present any preliminary or anticipated results if they are already available. If not, briefly discuss your expectations regarding the potential outcomes of your research.

Discussion and Significance (2 slides):

Engage with the participants by inviting questions and discussion points. Highlight the significance of your research idea within the broader academic or practical context and in connection with the conference call. Address potential implications and applications of your research.

Conclusion and Future Steps (1 or 2 slides):

List the key takeaways of your pitch. Conclude by briefly mentioning the next steps in your research process.

Presentation Style:

While the context is key, please don't lose yourself in too much contextualisation.

Use as little text as possible on slides. Prefer keywords or bullet points.

Use visuals.

Ensure that your pitch is engaging and free from jargon, making it accessible to a broad audience.

Maintain eye contact and pay attention to non-verbal communication.

Discussion Period:

After each pitch, allow time for questions and discussions (approximately 10 minutes per presentation).

Encourage participants to provide constructive feedback and insights.

Moderators may facilitate the discussion by posing initial questions or comments.

Closing Remarks:

These guidelines should help presenters deliver concise and informative pitches, fostering productive discussions and academic exchange during the conference session.

PRESENTATION GUIDELINES | ONLINE

Participants are required to give a concise and engaging 7-minute pitch about their research idea with the aim to facilitate meaningful discussions during the panel. All participants are required to read all abstracts being presented at their session beforehand.

Introduction (1 slide):

Begin by introducing yourself briefly.

Clearly state the title of your research project.

Highlight the significance of your research topic within the context of spatial justice, governance, or democracy in spatial planning, and the theme of the conference (benchmarking spatial justice).

Research Questions (1 slide):

Present your research questions succinctly.

Explain why these questions are relevant and how they connect to the conference theme.

Mention any theories or concepts you draw upon (e.g., Rawlsian justice or Harvey's spatial analysis).

Methods (1-2 slides):

Describe your research methodology briefly.

Mention key data sources, data collection techniques, and analytical tools.

Explain how your chosen methods are appropriate for addressing your research questions.

Key Findings or Hypotheses (1 minute):

Present any preliminary findings or hypotheses.

Emphasise how these findings relate to your research questions.

If applicable, discuss their implications for addressing issues connected to the symposium.

Theoretical Framework (1 minute):

Briefly explain the theoretical framework underpinning your research.

Connect your framework to the broader discourse in spatial justice, governance, or democracy.

Implications and Significance (1 minute):

Discuss the potential societal or policy implications of your research.

Explain how your work contributes to the public sphere and the challenges it addresses.

Key take aways (1 minute):

Summarize your main take aways.

Highlight the unique contribution of your research.

Conclude with a call to action or future research directions.

Q&A (10 minutes):

Open the floor to questions from the audience.

Be prepared to provide concise answers.

Encourage further discussion and feedback.

Ensure that you adhere to the time limit for each section to maintain clarity and engagement throughout your presentation. This structure should help you effectively pitch your research idea and generate interest among your audience.

PRESENTATION INDEX | PHYSICAL 30 NOV

34 Track 1 Recognition Berlagezaal 1, 11:10-12:10

1. Intersectional Methodologies for Analysing Spatial Justice in Cali's Popular Neighbourhoods.
Author: ISABELLA JARAMILLO
2. Categorising experiences of misrecognition in energy contexts: a recognition justice framework.
Authors: NYNKE VAN UFFELEN & LARA M. SANTOS AYLLÓN
3. 4emotions Methodology.
Authors: HONORATA GRZESIKOWSKA, EWELINA JASKULSKA

38 Track 2 Recognition Berlagezaal 2, 11:10-12:10

4. Territorial stigma and Chelas: past and future coping strategies towards destigmatization.
Author: HADIL JS AYOUB
5. Methodological Approaches for Assessing Spatial Justice.
Authors: MAI JOSEPH & ROBERT KORNER
6. Pushing the Boundaries of Spatial Justice in Urban Renewal.
Authors: NANKE VERLOO, MALENA RINAUDO VELANDIA, JOHNNY TASCÓN VALENCIA

42 Track 3 Recognition Room U, 11:10-12:10

7. Mapping Inequality: Navigating Law in Time & Space.
Author: DAPHINA MISIEDJAN
8. Reading Spatial Justice Through Google Maps Reviews.
Authors: MELIKE AKKAYA, ÖZLEM ÖZÇEVİK
9. An explorative design-based methodology to assess, project and operationalise spatial justice in conditions of ethnic conflict: The case of Eelam Tamils in the North-East of Sri Lanka.
Author: JOHNATHAN SUBENDRAN
10. Visibilising the Invisible: The Hidden Everyday Practices of Urban Scavengers in a Just Circular Transition. [WITHDRAWN]
Author: TAMARA EGGER

48 Track 4 Recognition ROOM K, 11:10-12:10

11. Designing Public Space for All: A Review on the Key Challenges of Older People's Inclusiveness.
Authors: ANDRÉ SAMORA-ARVELA, SARA ELOY, SIBILA MARQUES, MARIANA MONTALVÃO E SILVA
12. Making visible other ethnic representations: the moderating effect of harmony in Rotterdam.
Author: CAMILO BENITEZ-AVILA
13. Bridging the Gap: Pedagogy for Addressing Socio-Spatial Public Transit Exclusions in India.
Author: LAKSHMI SRINIVASAN

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Track 5 Procedural ROOM K, 13:40-14:40

14. **Towards Spatial Justice in Arab Countries: A Comparative Analysis of the Local Governance, Participation, and Public Space in Tunisia, Lebanon, Jordan, Sudan, Iraq and Egypt.**

Authors: HASSAN ELMOUELHI, H. AZIZ, S. YASSINE TURKI, O. BEN MEDIEN, N. ZEIDAN, FARAH ALATRASH, H. BANI AMER, L. M. RASWOL, M. SOLIMAN, I. Z. BAHRELDIN

15. **How to Select Communities for Urban Resilience Building Initiatives.**

Author: VALERIE BROWN

16. **JUST GROW? Co-designing justice-centric indicators to understand trends of intensification in urban agricultural systems.**

Authors: ADAM CALO, ANN-KRISTIN STEINES, PATRICK BAUR, KIYOKO KANKI, MICHAEL MARTIN, KATHRIN SPECHT, HEIDI VINGE

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Track 6 Procedural ROOM U, 13:40-14:40

17. **Co-designing towards Spatial Justice: In Policy and Practice.**

Authors: JANE WONG, YIP SIU, LYDIA TOOHEY

18. **Seeking a Just Transition for Social Inclusion.**

Authors: AMMALIA PODLASZEWSKA, KONSTANTINA CHRYSOSTOMOU, BRAM DEWOLFS, LUISA TUTTOLOMONDO, ANNABEL MEMPEL, ANNA STAMOULI

19. **Measuring spatial justice: Including children as creative knowledge producers.**

Authors: K. MAEVE POWLICK, GEERTJE SLINGERLAND

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Track 7 Procedural BERLAGEZAAL 2, 13:40-14:40

20. **Unravelling the Role of Social Organisations in Integrated Urban Regeneration: The Case of Brussels.**

Author: ATHINA MOROGLU

21. **Analysis of the dynamics of public space appropriation during a participatory planning process. Case of Borj Louzir, Tunisia.**

Authors: HASSAN ELMOUELHI, SAMI YASSINE TURKI, HELLEN AZIZ, OLFA BEN MEDIEN.

22. **Moving Towards Healthy Ageing: Understanding and Promoting Cycling Behavior Among Older Adults in Munich.**

Authors: MARÍA TERESA BAQUERO LARRIVA, DAVID DURÁN-RODAS, BENJAMIN BÜTTNER

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Track 8 Distributive BERLAGEZAAL 1, 13:40-14:40

23. **Quantifying Accessibility in Public Transit Systems using Learned Vector Embeddings.**

Author: ANDREW AZIZ

24. **A Methodological Research in the Context of Spatial Justice and the 15-Minute City: A Micro Case Study in Beyoglu.**

Authors: ZEHRA ÖZÇELİK, CENK HAMAMCIOĞLU

25. **Critical Data Science: From inequalities to shared knowledge.**

Author: TRIVIK VERMA

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Track 9 Distributive. BERLAGEZAAL 1, 14:50-15:50

26. The Spatial Justice of Employment Opportunities: developing indicators for spatial justice.

Author: RUTH NELSON

27. Assessing spatial justice in urban mobility through risks and misfortunes.

Author: DORCAS NTHOKI NYAMAI

28. Jakarta Green Justice: Evaluating the Provision of Jakarta Green Open Space.

Authors: GILANG PIDIANKU, AMANDA M. SAPUTRI, DANIEL J. HARIANTO, GABRIEL AKARNADI, JULIA S. DAHLAN, KEVIN SUTJIJADI, MIFTAH ADISUNU, NUGROHO ALUI

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Track 10 Distributive. BERLAGEZAAL 2, 14:50-15:50

29. Navigating Justice in Spatial Planning: Insights from a Systematic Literature Review.

Author: CLAUDIA ROT

30. Towards a systematic measurement of mobility injustice: A pilot study in the city of Munich.

Author: SINDI HAXHIJA

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Track 11 Multidimension ROOM U, 14:50-15:50

31. Spatial justice, between quantitative criteria and relationship with institutions.

Author: ANOUK CHAINAIS

32. A Public Participation Integrated Design Framework for Public Parks in Malaysia: A Quantitative Approach.

Author: UNGKU NORANI SONET

33. Spatial Justice in Low-Income Settlements in the Global South - Using Grounded Data from Ahmedabad and Lima to Explore Thermal Comfort and Wellbeing.

Authors: M.F. NAWAZI, J. GONÇALVES, T. VERMA, T. HOPPE, N.DOORN

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Track 12 Multidimension ROOM K, 14:50-15:50

34. Urban social reproduction: a new perspective on the requirements of just cities.

Author: SANDER VAN LANEN

35. Interrogating Spatial Justice: a comparative analysis of slum-redevelopment models in India.

Authors: ELISABETTA GOBBO, ANITRA BALIGA

36. Assessing the "right to the city" through experiential information: towards a holistic approach to spatial justice indicators.

Author: ANITA DE FRANCO

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Track 13 Multidimension ROOM K, 16:20-17:20

37. Socio-spatial inequalities in energy efficiency in the private rental sector in cities in England and Wales.

Author: CAITLIN ROBINSON

38. Using Mexico's National Housing Survey to Assess Social Housing Policy from a Spatial Justice Perspective.

Author: JAMES J. BILES

39. Towards Equitable Urban Green Open Spaces in Jakarta, Indonesia: A Spatial Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis Approach.

Authors: LUTHFI MUHAMAD IQBAL, GABRIEL ARAÚJO NJAIM

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Track 14 Multidimension ROOM U, 16:20-17:20

40. Practicing Citizenship in a Post-Truth World.

Author: GREGORY BRACKEN

41. The Regional deal of Zaan IJ to strengthen the broad welfare of four marginalised districts.

Author: DIVYA GUNNAM

42. Resisting creatively, designing collectively. From shelters to infrastructures for civic imagination.

Author: HELEEN VERHEYDEN

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Track 15 Multidimension BERLAGEZAAL 2, 16:20-17:20

43. Social impact assessment of urban regeneration operations for a methodological and operational approach aimed at planning and implementing interventions.

Author: GIULIA D'ANTONIO

44. What is the relative effectiveness of different pedagogies for teaching conceptual and methodological approaches to spatial justice benchmarking?

Authors: SARAH BISSETT-SCOTT, NEZHAPI-DELLÉ ODELEYE

45. Gentrification around Metro Stations in Bengaluru: A Report and Toolkit

Authors: DEEPSHIKHA CHAUDHURI, LAKSHMI S.

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Track 16 Multidimension BERLAGEZAAL 1, 16:20-17:20

46. Climate adaptation imaginaries in translation: international collaboration in Chennai.

Authors: RAQUEL HADRICHSILVA, DOMINIC STEAD, MARGREET ZWARTEVEEN, TANEHA KUZNIECOW BACCHIN.

47. Towards a Sustainable and Equitable Future: Queer Mobilities, Climate Change, and Spatial Justice.

Author: LUIGI BARRAZA CÁRDENAS

48. The space of justice. Disentangling the notion of "spatial justice" and re-discussing the "spatial turn".

Author: STEFANO MORONI

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49. Methodological Approaches for Measuring and Assessing Perception of Urban Safety Among Women, case study of Kazakhstan.
Author: AIDANA TLEUKEN
50. Role of Spatial Frameworks in Spurring Climate Justice and Responsible Investment.
Authors: LUIZ BARATA, EMILY KING, VIJAY KESAVAN
51. Just Participation or Just Participation? Assessment of Community Participation in Heritage Planning Process in Tanjungpinang, Indonesia.
Author: UMMU INDRA PERTIWI
52. Spatial Justice on Indonesia Housing Policy and Program.
Authors: RAMALIS SOBANDI & REZA PRIMA
53. Just affordances: a framework for spatial justice.
Author: HIMANSHU BURTE
- 112 **Track 18 Multidimensional ONLINE|16:25-17:25|Breakout room 2**
54. Practicing Social Justice Impact in Spatial Design Work: Venting Practices in Neo-Apartheid Cities.
Authors: JHONO BENNETT, OLWETHU JACK, JACQUELINE CUYLER
55. The Equitable Development Data Explorer.
Author: JAMES PIACENTINI
56. The Basti Project of Delhi.
Authors: SHIEKH INTEKHAB ALAM, AMRITA KAUR SLATCH
57. Gender Perspectives in Vienna's Parks: Understanding Inclusivity and Spatial Justice
Author: MÉLANIE MICHEL
58. Women-friendly bicycle system in Turin: assessing requirements, strategies and potential influence on air quality.
Authors: ANDREA ROSSO, GIULIA MELIS
- 118 **Track 19 Multidimensional ONLINE|16:25-17:25|Breakout room 3**
59. Leveraging Community Data for Spatial Justice.
Authors: RACHAEL LISHMAN, CATHY RUSSELL, ELLIOTT SHAW, AMIR HUSSAIN, ALEJANDRO QUINTO
60. Towards a Fair Housing Space Standard: Rethinking Housing and Public Realm in the Densification of Zurich.
Author: MIRIAM STIERLE
61. Understanding the 'Just City': Benchmarking Spatial Justice in the Transportation.
Author: YASHSWANI SHARMA
62. Schools for the transformation of Public Spaces that promote a good start in life and are references for healthy bonds: "Escuelas Limeños al Bicentenario I y II" Program.
Authors: ANDREA LOYOLA RAMIREZ, PATRICIA QUEVEDO CASTAÑEDA,

OMAR JUAREZ PONCE

63. Using Place-Based Reviews to Inspire Spatial Justice.

Author: ALISSAR RIACHI

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Track 20 Multidimensional ONLINE|16:25-17:25|Breakout room 4

64. Women's Perception of Safety in Public Space: The STEP-UP Project.

Authors: LILY SCARPONI, LAMIA ABDELFAH, ANDREA GORRINI, CATALINA VALENZUELA CORTÉS, GERARDO CARPENTIERI, CARMEN GUIDA, FLORENCIA ANDREOLA, AZZURRA MUZZONIGRO, LAURA DA RE, ELEONORA GARGIULO, CARLOS CAÑAS, JIM WALKER, RAWAD CHOUBASSI

65. The spatial justice as an analytical and territorial tool: readings from Portugal.

Authors: JORGE GONÇALVES & SÍLVIA JORGE

66. Developing a Restorative Justice Master Planning Framework.

Authors: ARON LESSER & MELISSA LEE

67. The paradigm of citizen participation: Slum parliament, a convergence model.

Authors: MEENAKSHI MEERA & GANGA DILEEP C.

68. Picturing spatial justice through multimodal collaborative ethnographies.

Author: KITTI BARACSI

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69. Equality opportunities-based social and spatial distributive justice of on-line-offline public services.

Authors: YUAN ZHUANG, HAN, QI, DUJUAN, YANG

70. Accessibility-Based Land Value Change Leading to Unjust Distribution of Rights Through Planning.

Authors: Ü.ÖZLEM.ÜNVER-GÖÇER, FATMA ÜNSAL

71. A Futures-driven Approach to Design for Spatial Equity in Cities.

Author: TATIANA EFREMENKO

72. Spatial Justice in Urban Landscapes: The Relationship between Accessibility Improvement and Residents' QOL in Singapore.

Author: QIYAN CHEN, YE ZHANG

73. A Place-based Conceptual Framework for Studying Green Gentrification: The Case of Toronto.

Author: ELIKA ZAMANI

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74. How Digital Planning Stimulate Spatial Justice.

Author: KHALAFALLA OMER

75. The visual dilemma of spatial (in) justices: Presenting The Need for Urban Visualisation Annotations.

Author: MENNATULLAH HENDAWY

76. Porosity as a figure of spatial justice: strengths and critical issues from the case of pedestrianisation of via Andrea Costa in Mestre and Altobello 'Neighbourhood Contract' urban transformation.

Author: LUCA NICOLETTO

77. The Sad Story of Sistan & Balouchestan: Evaluation of the province's position in development and inequality indicators.

Authors: HOJJAT MIRZAEI, HODA POURPIRALI.

78. The Post-Participation Phase: Strategies for Enhancing Data-Driven and Inclusive Urban Design and Planning.

Authors: CEM ATAMAN, BIGE TUNCER, SIMON PERRAULT

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79. Understanding Urban Environments from a Maternal Perspective: Exploring Maternal Experiences and Spatial Justice.

Author: LAMA AKMEEL

80. Theories of spatial justice: the case for an engagement with racial capitalism.

Author: CLAIRE CHRISTOPHER

81. Enhancing commuting experience in Almaty's suburbs: strategies for improving public transport accessibility.

Author: KENZHEKHAN KABDESOV

82. Towards a More "Spatially Just" transition in Urban Transport System: The Capability Approach as a Framework for Action.

Author: PETER KARIUKI

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83. Assessment of socio-economic embeddedness of Urban green space in Delhi: A microlevel study using geospatial techniques.

Authors: RAVINDRA SINGH, MILAP PUNIA

84. Evaluating Practices Producing Collective Services in Maputo through the Spatial Justice Lens.

Author: MILOUSA ANTÓNIO

85. A Planner's Quest for Identifying Spatial (In)Justice in Local Communities: A Case Study of Urban Census Tracts in North Carolina, USA.

Author: RUSSELL M. SMITH

86. Spatial Justice: Unravelling Distributive Spatial Disparities, A Multidimensional Methodological Frameworks Approach to Distributive Justice with a Focus on Kumirmari in the Sundarbans.

Author: UDIP PRAN DAS

87. Thinking at Intra-city Scale to Promote Spatial Justice: Reflections from Cape Town, South Africa.

Author: ARINDAM JANA

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88.Climate x Spatial Justice: Measuring the Impacts of the 2019-2028 São Paulo Cycling Plan on Climate Change Mitigation and Spatial Inequalities.

Authors: FERNANDO TÚLIO SALVA ROCHA FRANCO, LUCAS GÉREZ FORATTO

89.Environmental Justice in Italy: A Geostatistical Analysis of Environmental Hazards and Socioeconomic Factors.

Authors: GIORGIA SCOGNAMIGLIO, ROSSELLA BERNARDINI PAPALIA

90. Understanding Disparities of Public Green Spaces Accessibility in Urban Fringe Areas: A Comparative Analysis Based on Gravity-based and Ga2SFCA Methods.

Author: MENGXUAN LIU

91.Processes and Patterns of Structural Violence and Spatial (In)Justice in Housing Production within a Complex Geopolitical Border Context.

Authors: SARA MORALES CÁRDENAS, ALMA ANGÉLICA RODRÍGUEZ MORENO

92.Spatial Injustice: Analysis and Registration of its Manifestations in Barrio Sinaí.

Authors: VERÓNICA CAMPOS CÉSPEDES, ANDREA CASTRO JIMÉNEZ, ANGÉLICA SOLÍS ARCE, JOSUÉ ZELEDÓN RODRÍGUEZ

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93.Spatial Justice and Education Equity: Analysing the Factors Shaping Basic Education Access in São Paulo.

Author: CAMILLA DO CARMO PEROTTO

94.Introducing Equity in the Planning of Bicycle Lanes.

Author: AURIANE TECOURT

95.Spatial justice for food security in São Paulo.

Authors: LETÍCIA MACHADO, CAROLINA CARVALHO

96.Towards a Mobility Just City: The Taiwan Pedestrian Rights Movement.

Author: WU YUN-CHING

97.Assessing EU Policy Framework for Spatial Distributive and Procedural Justice.

Author: CATERINA QUAGLIO

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98.Developing a Social Justice Assessment Tool for Public Green Spaces of Istanbul.

Authors: ECE YORULMAZ, ELIF KISAR

99.Smart Cities or Smart Neighborhoods? The case studies of three South American Smart Cities.

Author: AGUSTINA PÉREZ MIRIANCOT

100.Redefining Urban Safety: Exploring Gender Intersectionality and Temporality in Young Women's Experiences of Urban Spaces.

Author: ANNA BEDNARCZYK

101.Socio-spatial resilience in the Indian city: the case of Newtown, Rajarha.

Author: ARKADIPTA BANERJEE

102.Spatial justice indicators centred on the body-space perspective.

Author: LIA ANDREIA CRISTÓVÃO FERREIRA

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103. Marka Camp (Jordan): An Evolving Definition of Refugee Camp and Hosting City. Employing Mental Mapping Dissecting the Conceived, Lived, and Perceived Spaces.

Author: DINA DAHOOD DABASH

104. Landscapes of Inequality: Exploring the Determinants of the Urban Landscape that Perpetuates Inequality in Southern Madrid .

Author: ALBA R. ILLANES

105. Addressing Climate Equity and Environmental Justice in Urban Planning & Addressing Climate Equity Concerns in Urban Planning through Citizen Science.

Authors: AKRUTI MURHEKARTS, SARAYU MADHIYAZHAGAN. AAPOORV AGRAWAL

106. A vocabulary of spatial justice in practice- migrants' engagement with space in Kolkata and Perth.

Author: ANURADHA CHAKRABARTI

107. Transforming Urban Mobility for equitable and sustainable streets for all.

Authors: GIULIA MELIS, ANDREA ROSSO

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108. Future Scenarios; rethinking spatial injustice and EU territorial inequalities.

Authors: MARIE MAHON , MATT FINCH , MICHAEL WOODS

109. An Understanding of Inequality Through A Comparative Study at City Scale: 'white' area (Vincent) versus 'black' area (Peffer-ville).

Author: KELSEY BLIGNAUT

110. Spatial Justice and Environmental Inequities: A Multidimensional Exploration of Structured Racism in Cleveland and Detroit's Urban Landscape.

Author: TARANEH MESHKANI

111. Evaluating Lisbon's Recent Public Space Transformations: A Spatial Justice Perspective.

Author: DUYGU CIHANGER RIBEIRO

112. Street Food Vendors under Siege: Reassessing Spatial Justice for Street Vendors in Soi Convent, Bangkok, Thailand.

Author: BOONYAKORN DAMRONGRAT

Track 30 Academic ONLINE|17:35-18:35|Breakout room 2

113. Seeking Spatial Justice in Southern Croatia: Grassroots Initiatives against Privatisation of Public Land.

Author: SONJA DRAGOVIĆ

114. Resistive urban spatial practices and cultures as signs of spatial justice and resilience in India: Impact of globalisation in the restructuring of Bengali Society & urban space in Kolkata from

the perspective of public nuisance.

Author: ARKADIPTA BANERJEE

115. Fostering Spatial Justice through Climate Resilient Design and Planning: Key findings of UCCRN Third Report on Climate and Cities (ARC3.3) and lessons from the Urban Design Climate Workshops.

Authors: CRISTINA VISCONTI, ANDRÉS DAVID MAGLIONE

116. The Just City in Kenya: From Conceptualisation to Implementation.

Author: ALFRED OMENYA

117. Spatial Justice in Low-Income Settlements in the Global South - Using Grounded Data from Ahmedabad and Lima to Explore Thermal Comfort and Wellbeing.

Authors: RITA LAMBERT, ARGYRIS ORAIOPOULOS, JANINA L FUCHS

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118. Exploring Gendered Spatial Justice: An Analysis of Women's Safety and Urban Space in London.

Authors: TRISHLA CHADHA, YUXUAN LIU

119. A House All My Own: An intersectional reflection on the failures of post-apartheid law and policy to provide tenure security for black women in urban South Africa.

Authors: ADENIKE FAPOHUNDA, DEBORAH RABUDA

120. Design Reparations. Harlem, New York: A Case Study.

Author: SHAWN L. RICKENBACKER

121. Envisaging future cities within intersectional strategy in the Arab Region.

Author: NOHA ESSAM

122. Benchmarking Inclusion in Public Space.

Authors: RASHID A. MUSHKANI, SARAH TANNIR, TOUMADHER AMMAR & SHIN KOSEKI

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123. Socio-spatial equity: An application of Space Syntax in analysing the spatial justice among women pedestrians in Monastir, Tunisia.

Author: ASMA REJEB BOUZGARROU

124. Mobility Justice Pedagogy for Whom? Reading urban roads beyond car usage.

Author: ALOKEPARNA SENGUPTA

125. Public Space and Deafness: A Change of Perspective.

Author: MARINA FANARI

126. Exploring Trispaciality and Spatial Injustice in the Achievement of Economic and Social Rights: An Analysis of Spatial Barriers to Access Public Programs in Chile.

Author: GABRIELA GUEVARA-CUE

127. The growth of Oxxo retail in São Paulo, Brazil: a food gentrification analysis.

Authors: ANA MARIA BERTOLINI, LUIZA FERNANDES TAMAS, PEDRO HENRIQUE CAMPHELLO TORRES, GABRIELA DI GIULIO

SYMPOSIUM

DAY 1

BERLAGEZALEN 1&2

ROOM U & ROOM K

09:45-10:30

Berlagezaal 1

Keynote

Alexandre Frediani

Principal researcher, Human Settlements at the
International Institute for Environment and
Development

Alexandre Apsan Frediani specialises on issues around human development in cities of the global South. His work explores participatory approaches to planning and design of interventions in informal settlements in cities in Latin America and sub-Saharan Africa. Alexandre is an expert affiliate of Architecture Sans Frontières UK, a fellow of the Human Development and Capability Association, and part of the boards of Habitat International Coalition and the Sierra Leone Urban Research Centre.

In October 2020, Alexandre was elected as a fellow of the Human Development and Capability Association, joining the likes of Amartya Sen, Martha Nussbaum and Frances Stewart.

10:30-11:00

Berlagezaal 1

Cities panel

UP2030

UP2030 URBAN PLANNING AND DESIGN READY FOR 2030

This symposium happens in the framework of UP2030.

UP2030 is a Horizon Europe project that aims to support cities in driving the socio-technical transitions required to meet their climate neutrality targets by leveraging urban planning and design. Within the project city stakeholders and local authorities will be supported and guided to put neutrality on the map of their communities in day-to-day actions and strategic decisions.

An innovative methodology (5UP-approach) will be developed and applied through the co-development and implementation of science-based - yet practical - tools, and methods.

Inclusive participation is key throughout the project's full cycle of activities so that real

needs of communities are reflected in the city-specific visions, and co-designed interventions maximise delivery of co-benefits. As such, UP2030 will have a measured positive impact on spatial justice in the pilots, and give the opportunity to citizens to participate in the transition by becoming agents of change themselves through their sustainable behavioural shifts.

TU Delft is a Work Package leader in charge of creating a Spatial Justice framework and benchmarking of urban carbon neutrality strategies. Juliana Gonçalves, Roberto Rocco, Marcin Dabrowski, Hugo Lopez and Andrés Maglione are actively involved in WP3 and contribute to various aspects of the project.

The symposium Spatial Justice Practice contributes to Work Package 3 in the project.

To learn more, please visit <https://up2030-he.eu>

Budapest

BUDAPEST METHODOLOGY FOR HEALTHY STREETS UPSCALING

HISTORY

Budapest's leadership decided in 2021 to introduce the Healthy Streets approach developed by Lucy Saunders in London, United Kingdom. Under the programme of EU structural and cohesion funds in the 2021-2027 programming period, Budapest dedicated EUR 69 million for a call for application. Districts will be able to apply with individual projects which designs is based on the principles of Healthy Streets. The Municipality of Budapest in collaboration with Lucy Saunders adapted the Healthy Streets Design Check to the local features, with special focus on significant climate issues such as changes in precipitation patterns and transportation design standards.

SPATIAL AND SOCIAL CHARACTERISTICS

The main goals of the Healthy Streets program:

- to create healthier and safer environment on the streets mitigating the harm effects as well as the air pollution and the noise of traffic
- blue and green infrastructure are highly welcomed in the program as well
- to motivate the users for biking and walking and for other activities preventing health issues

Via these goals spatial justice can be granted, as the distribution of space will be more equitable and the opportunities in the use of places will be easily recognisable. Increasing the blue and green infrastructure on the streets of the city centre results an equal access comparing with the uptown. The involvement is also a key requirement, as each project must consider the users participation; identify the target groups, define the way of how they will be involved and the level of their involvement.

Also, the methodology of Healthy Streets gives an equal scoring system, which ensures the objectivity between each project.

THE CALL FOR HEALTHY STREETS PROGRAM BUDAPEST

Individual locations will be scattered around the city. However, all projects must meet selection criteria defined in the call for application. All submitted applications should be in line with the Healthy Streets approach assessed by the municipality experts. The project proposals will be ranked based on the difference between current and designed street plans' scores. The evaluation will follow the Healthy Streets Design Checklist, which is available for the applicants in Hungarian since September 2022.

During the summer of 2022, an extensive testing phase was carried out with the involvement of the professional urban design company of the city and NGOs. All feedbacks were evaluated, and the Design Checklist was adjusted accordingly. Within the EU funds framework, additional points can be earned for other project elements or approaches outside the Healthy Streets® methodology: developing of community spaces on street openings, developing of other public assets as public transport stops and public toilets, cost-benefit ratio of the project (unit cost per user, unit cost per area), project contributes to core objectives of the integrated development plan (supports brown field development, green-blue infrastructure target area), project based on community design or public poll, involvement of NGOs and local communities, supporting energy efficiency and application of renewables. There will be an impartial Jury set up to evaluate the submitted projects of the districts, which is set up from members of the Municipality of Budapest, Budapest Transport Centre, the Government's Jury of Cycling Infrastructure and Green Infrastructure to assure equal opportunity for all participants.

Currently the call for application is under preparation in cooperation with the Managing Authority.

Rotterdam

A POLICY ANALYSIS OF RESILIENT BOTU 2028: PRINCIPLES & TRANSFERABILITY

Resilient BoTu 2028 is an integrated programme with the goal to raise the social index of Bospolder and Tussendijken to the urban average within 10 years, making BoTu Rotterdam's first resilient district. The way towards the establishment of this programme was paved by many different policy pathways and needs, combined with the district-specific issues, and city-wide transitions. At the core, the philosophy and structure of this programme seek to facilitate long-term sustainable development of the district. To enable this sustainable change, the focus is laid on social and community resilience at the heart of this programme, as well as leveraging urban transitions, such as the energy transition and climate adaptation, to strengthen social resilience.

- Website BoTu
- Article 'Making Rotterdam's First Resilient Neighborhood through Social Cohesion'
- Energy transition in Bospolder-Tussendijken

HOW, WHAT, WHERE

- How: an open process, public-private partnerships, strengthening networks
- What: interventions on different themes
- Where: strengthening promising places in the district

In essence, the programme is characterized by its 'open process', in which local residents and parties are invited to take an active part. In this open process, new forms of collaboration between residents, businesses and the city are stimulated. The philosophy of this programme is value-based and aims to empower the community, by recognizing that 'real change comes from within'; building further on the existing strengths of the community, that is, local initiatives and networks. The strength and capacities of the locals are taken as a starting point, which can be seen in BoTu's "Open call", or

participation in the redevelopment of Driehoeksplein. Community-building is one of the ways in which there is actively worked on social and community resilience, based on the principles of Asset-based Community Development (ABCD).

- Article 'France gets inspired by the approach of Resilient BoTu'
- Field Academy monitor - project page
- Field Academy - online interactive monitor (in Dutch), monitor page (in Dutch)

CURRENT FOCUS

The local context, pre-existing challenges and combined policy pathways, political leadership and attention were determinant of the emergence and the content of the programme of Resilient BoTu 2028. The question whether such an approach - if it would be possible to narrow it down into 'one approach' - can be replicated in other districts, has entered the phase of reformulation. In this phase, the focus has been laid on the comprehension of underlying principles, and the discussion is now concerned with whether it would be possible to 'make' the underlying principles of, first of all, the programme as a whole, second of all, the principles behind the interventions taken at different scales, transferrable and accessible across the municipal organisation.

The latter is exactly one of the questions that Rotterdam seeks to address through its participation in UP2030. The ambition is not to integrate these principles into existing structures, frameworks, and standards, but to anticipate on the common language and thinking of the internal bureaucracy. This question is being addressed through a co-creation process, a process in which the underlying principles and corresponding lessons and practices will undergo a phase of implicit matchmaking with other districts and programmes. The second question to be addressed is concerned with the coming five years of the Resilient BoTu programme itself, in which the focus is laid on the evaluation of the first phase of the programme, and the identification of the priorities and thematic areas for the years to come.

RECOGNITION

11:10-12:10

Berlagezaal 1

Intersectional Methodologies for Analysing Spatial Justice in Cali's Popular Neighbourhoods

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Urbanisation in Latin America and the Caribbean (LAC) has led to approximately 80% of the population residing in cities (ECLAC, 2012). In the peripheries of these urban centers, poverty-stricken communities, often comprising migrants seeking economic opportunities or forced to relocate due to displacement, are prevalent. Despite residing in self-built neighborhoods, these communities do not automatically experience an improved quality of life.

Focusing on Cali's urban peripheries, a significant portion of the population faces poverty and resides in informal settlements. While these settlements offer shelter, they do not inherently ensure a dignified quality of life, underscoring spatial injustice. The Colombian government and local authorities have initiated upgrading programs to improve living conditions through infrastructure, housing solutions, and property titles. However, disparities in resource allocation and limited opportunities persist due to diverse social identities within these neighborhoods.

Addressing these inequalities necessitates a comprehensive and intersectional approach, considering the diverse population and local knowledge of these communities. Since 2020, Cali has been implementing a Comprehensive Habitat Upgrading with an Intersectional Approach (CHU-I) pilot, seeking to improve the quality of life and reduce territorial inequalities in specific neighborhoods. This paper centers on Cali, Colombia, advocating for the application of Intersectional Methodologies to understand the territory comprehensively and promote the inclusion of diversity, needs, and perspectives in the Comprehensive Habitat Upgrading. Inter-

sectional methodologies serve as pivotal tools, enabling a nuanced understanding of intersecting identities and experiences within these communities.

By employing an intersectional lens, this research aims to illuminate the multifaceted dynamics influencing spatial injustice and propose tailored solutions for Cali's diverse population. The study outlines recommendations for effectively integrating Intersectional Methodologies within the Comprehensive Habitat Upgrading framework in Cali, with the ultimate goal of fostering more equitable and just urban spaces in this vibrant Colombian city.

Urbanisation, Spatial Injustice, Intersectional Approach, Informal Settlements, Habitat Upgrading

Categorising experiences of misrecognition in energy contexts: a recognition justice framework

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Within applied justice scholarships, such as spatial justice, energy justice, and mobility justice, distinct categories or “tenets” of justice are distinguished, such as procedural, distributive, and recognition justice (David Schlosberg, 2007). Especially the concept of recognition justice seems to have an analytical and moral appeal, as many energy conflicts cannot be explained in purely distributive and procedural terms (Pesch et al., 2017). However, many questions still surround the concept of recognition justice. Many definitions and interpretations circulate, and a clear framework to detect and understand experiences of misrecognition is missing. By going back to the philosophical roots of the concept, Van Uffelen distinguishes between three modes of recognition: love, law, and status order (van Uffelen, 2022). Recognition through love refers to intimate relations between a few people; through laws, we recognise others as having equal dignity; and through the status order, we attribute value to (individual and group) differences and achievements. Recognition through these modes contributes to self-confidence, self-respect and self-esteem, all of which contribute to autonomy – understood as a fundamentally relational concept – and therefore to justice (Anderson & Honneth, 2009). We consider the taxonomy of love, law, and status order a valuable analytical tool to analyse and understand grievances of misrecognition.

However, they remain wide-ranging classifications, thus the current typology is not granular enough to be applied in concrete cases (Desmet & Fokkinga, 2020). Moreover, the categories of love, law, and status order remain abstract or distant from the empirical world

at first sight. The link with applied contexts, such as energy technologies, policies and systems in cities, appears far-fetched. Therefore, a translation from these abstract categories to the concrete situations at hand seems useful. These two problems add to many difficulties in understanding experiences of misrecognition in energy contexts. For detecting misrecognition, qualitative research is vital, as misrecognition often has harmful effects on individuals, in other words, it hurts. Yet, analysing qualitative interviews through a recognition justice lens can be extremely difficult without appropriate conceptual tools. Therefore, this paper facilitates a better understanding of experiences of misrecognition by making recognition justice more granular. We pose the following research question: how can experiences of misrecognition in the energy context be categorised? This paper aims to formulate subcategories within the categories of law, love, and status order that describe in a more fine-grained manner the diverse ways actors can be (mis)recognised in energy contexts. We do so in two phases.

First, we study interpretations of recognition justice in critical theory and various taxonomies of human needs to create a first iteration of subcategories. Second, these findings are tested by thoroughly analysing a small sample of interviews in which participants express various experiences of misrecognition. The resulting framework for categorising recognition justice can support researchers and decision-makers in identifying, placing and analysing experiences of misrecognition in energy contexts.

Recognition Justice, Spatial Justice, Energy Justice,
Categories of Justice, Modes of Recognition

4emotions Methodology

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Historically, and now, architecture and urban planning are prioritising a 'one-man-fits-all' approach to behaviours and needs, resulting in non-gender-neutral cities. Women, girls, and sexual and gender minorities of all ages and abilities have been under-served and under-represented in the urban planning and design fields, resulting in urban environments that fail to meet their needs. On the other hand, cities have more women-headed households, and more women are participating in the formal economy than ever. Women are recognised as "a city's greatest asset and contribute heavily to sustainable urban development" (UN-HABITAT, 2012). While efforts are being made to promote inclusivity in academia, practice, and policymaking, existing inclusive design strategies often focus on specific topics, such as physical disability, without considering gender or age within that group. Addressing these challenges requires a novel approach to incorporate gender perspective analysis into city governance, thus mitigating gender inequalities in urban contexts. Drawing upon the key concepts of "gender-equal space" and the ability to "envision the equitable future," a new methodology, called Equal-Spatial Sequence, was outlined. The method aims to elucidate what constitutes a gender-inclusive space. Finds its roots in the pioneering work of K. Wejchert, a prominent Polish urban planner, who introduced the concept of the 'Curve of Impressions' in 1974, focusing on analysing the urban order of space. The curve is a visual representation of the impressions experienced by individuals within a given urban environment. However, it only considers factors connected with the physical built environment: urban form and built elements, i.e., facades.

The current approach builds upon Wejchert's framework, employing it as a comparative tool to illustrate disparities and divergences. The Equal-Spatial Sequence methodology places equal importance on emotions as to technical solutions when designing cities. While emotions are difficult to define precisely, the awareness of their existence and the ability to express them defines our behaviour in both the built environment and society. Therefore, expanding knowledge in this field and considering emotions when changing our cities is extremely important. Using the same comparative scale as Wejchert, the emotions chart was plotted, which includes (a) a sense of security and (b) exclusion, alongside (c) comfort of use and (d) aesthetics.

By juxtaposing the new methodology with the Curve of Impressions, we can identify differences between the two approaches - the former made by men, and the latter a female perspective. This advancement leverages the foundation laid by Wejchert's seminal work to enhance our understanding and analysis of spatial experiences. The report describes the pilot study of the methodology conducted on the main high street of Warsaw (Jerozolimskie Avenue), which was exhibited in the Museum of Contemporary Art in Warsaw in November 2022. It concludes that the new methodology (1) offers diverse insight for the design of the built environment, (2) empowers excluded groups of inhabitants to raise their voice, (3) raise awareness about spatial perceptions, (3) helps guide urban planning and design decisions by considering the subjective experiences of individuals in relation to the physical space they inhabit.

Gender-Inclusive Space, Equal-Spatial Sequence Methodology,
Urban Planning, Emotional Impact, Spatial Experience

RECOGNITION

11:10-12:10

Berlagezaal 2

Territorial stigma and Chelas: past and future coping strategies towards destigmatisation

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The stigma surrounding the Chelas area in Lisbon has existed at least since the formal establishment of the social housing neighborhood and has persisted over the past few decades despite the changing realities and conditions of the area. The 'stickiness' of this stigma can be understood through the framework of territorial stigmatization, which refers to the blemish attached to a place which subsequently impacts the material conditions of the place and the people within it. Since Luic Wacquant's formulation of the concept of territorial stigmatization, many researchers have used this framework to understand the stigma of place in different urban neighbourhoods. One of the contested parts of the early framework was in Wacquant's discussion of responses to stigma, mainly his focus on submission as being the main response. Later, this was adjusted to add resistance as well. Submission can happen through dissimulation, mutual distancing and elaborating of micro differences, lateral denigration, retreat into the private (family) sphere, or simply by exiting. Resistance, on the other hand, can happen through studied indifference, defence of neighbourhood, and stigma inversion (Wacquant et al. 2014). However, despite the inclusion of resistance against stigma, multiple studies found that there are limits to what local resistance can achieve towards erasing or dispelling stigma (Schemschat 2021; Power et al. 2020; Broudehoux et al. 2017). Oftentimes, the destigmatisation in question ends in gentrification and the displacement or erasure of those whom the blemish of place impacted the most. As part of a multimethod research on Chelas, including in-depth semi-structured interviews, archival research, and discourse analysis, this paper examines how Chelas, both in the past and the present, has dealt and negotiated with

the realities of stigma fastened upon it, be it through submission or resistance by local residents or other impacted actors, and investigates the potential for successful destigmatisation of Chelas not despite but because of it being one of the largest social housing projects in Portugal. Early insights indicate that the physical separation of Chelas from its surroundings through highways, green space, and railways is in fact, protecting its neighbourhoods from encroaching development gentrification (or at least slowing it down). Meanwhile, within Chelas, initiatives and projects are working - sometimes with the city municipality - to dispel the stigma that stuck to the area for years, improve the conditions of the neighbourhood, and push back against displacement while also having cultivated a strong identity tied to the place, the culture, and the name of Chelas.

Territorial Stigmatisation, Chelas Area, Resistance to Stigma, Gentrification, Social Housing

Methodological approaches for assessing spatial justice

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How to foster imagination, leading to a higher participation rate? Confronted to the context of Bucarest, Romania, where a lot of places are undefined, we developed a methodology based on the possibilities of these in-between spaces in a city. They are neglected by the public but offer unique opportunities for these that do not find a place in a community (intentionally excluded or not fitting needs into the rigid planning scheme).

The problem needed to be addressed: in a society, planning is usually not able to respond to all groups and needs in one. Places that are free of definitions can provide opportunities to understand needs and foster imagination - which is a crucial basis for participation.

We applied the methodology on a deconstruction site in the centre of Bucharest - a field filled with grey rubble - which was the result of a clear formal act of destruction of the city. The field has remained in this temporary phase for over a year.

How to understand the potentials and the users of this "in-between space"?

Starting with observational, social and historical research, two important elements were identified. The use by the youth, attract by destruction, and neighbours' indifference to the site.

To be able to talk about the space we worked with two different methodologies -> indirect and direct ex-change with stakeholders.

Indirect: "artistic" experiments that entailed two different effects

-> Provocation for the neighbours by the appearance of a "construction site" -

-> Imagination of the children through the analogy to a playground construction site / space of trying out.

Like the space itself, the intervention was not well defined and therefore triggered a reaction and reflection from local stakeholders about the space that surrounds them.

And on the other hand, the direct exchange: With photo exhibitions and spatial exhibitions on site - small-scale model of the site with small-scale rubble - we enabled playful creative experiments. This gave rise to a wide variety of ideas about a possible definition of space, which in turn constitutes the richness of the undefined: <https://wonderland.cx/event/bucarest-in-between-space-and-regulation/>

Current conclusion of the ongoing research:

Upon our return from the exchange year, we as students were able to better understand our own reality. Saw a critical role in strengthening the imagination of stakeholders in the planning process and at the same time identifying more of these in between spaces to understand how far they can be a tool for city planners to understand and reach out to groups that are usually left out.

Imagination, Participation, In-between Spaces, Urban Planning, Community Engagement

Pushing the boundaries of spatial justice in urban renewal

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In the 21st century, many countries in Latin America have implemented urban renewal (UR) in order to densify central areas and attract new investments. These policies have silently promoted the acquisition of land by private agents, which have resulted in gentrification processes in the central and peri-central areas of major cities in the Latin America region. In the center of Bogotá Colombia, several UR projects led to the displacement of residents and gentrification of neighborhoods, leaving a collective memory of unjust urban renewal. In the context of these memories, the Fenicia Triangle Project (ongoing since 2014), located at the urban center of Bogotá, sought to change this memory by launching an 'model of just UR'. The project introduced a complex land management strategy to generate a land readjustment process that disrupts with the traditional UR model by engaging landowners, residents and business-owners in the development of the plans and promoting their permanence once the project is executed. The project has been recognized nationally and internationally because of its innovations to address the traditional challenges of urban renewal. First, by offering residents the possibility to stay in the newly developed housing by exchanging the built square meters of their old property one by one, instead of paying a price for land value that would not offer enough resources to stay in the area. Second, by defining long-term social compensations for the residents; for example, by guaranteeing an income during the period of construction for those who contribute their property to the project; by covering legal fees associated with the complex tenure dynamics of land. Third by addressing the expected increase in municipal tax and other costs of living defined in Colombia by what is called 'strata'. The project freezes the costs

of the original strata for residents remaining in the area for ten years, which ensures that remaining after the UR stays affordable for them. These innovations thus address the needs of citizens and incorporate many of what the UR literature would recommend to address spatial justice. In the paper we will assess what 'just UR' means by analyzing these what we call 'hard dimensions' of the project in relation to existing literature. Our own practice, engagement and research in the project, however, brought us to questioning whether these hard dimensions suffice when we seek to understand justice from a more experiential and everyday perspective? In our case study we observed what we will introduce as the 'soft dimensions' of justice, for example the meaning of home, the everyday practice of community, or the experience of time. These cannot be captured in 'hard' measures such as economic prosperity, land value or square meters. We thus seek to push the boundary of what is considered 'spatial justice' and argue that there is a need to recognize the 'soft' dimensions of justice to explore and identify what makes it meaningful for residents to stay. Drawing on existing literature and ethnographic experiences in the case of Fenicia, we propose a framework for understanding spatial justice as a triad of three "soft" dimensions—spatial, relational, and experiential. By considering these dimensions as a triad, we aim to explore other aspects and delve into the complexities of spatial justice. This approach allows us to explore not only the physical aspects of justice but also to emphasize the importance of the lived experiences and the everyday lives of residents, categories that we argue contribute to understanding what needs to be taken into account to make spatial justice meaningful for those who claim it.

Urban Renewal, Gentrification, Land Management
Spatial Justice, Soft Dimensions of Justice

RECOGNITION

11:10-12:10

ROOM U

3

Mapping Inequality: Navigating Law in Time and Space

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The law shapes the world in tangible and intangible ways. It can demarcate spaces for certain functions or incentivise and sanction specific usage or interactions (de Witte, 2022). Similarly, maps play a central role in claiming, naming and bounding spaces in order to control them. This project explores the relationship between law and space and how this relationship facilitates inequalities experienced by communities in public spaces (such as air pollution, access to green spaces and surveillance). This project searches for ways in which 'the legal side of' processes of inequality can be made visible to assist communities in advocating for change.

This project asks the following questions:

- What are the spatial impacts of laws and regulations (especially concerning public spaces) for marginalised communities?
- The legal part of this project will be carried out by employing desk-based research, to study conventional legal sources (legislation, general principles, etc.). Followed by socio-legal methods to explore how communities relate to these laws through (group) interviews and observations.
- What would maps look like if they would reflect experiences with inequality and oppression of marginalised communities in The Hague and Rotterdam?

To answer this question, methods of counter-mapping will be used, which call to decolonise 'the privileged worldviews projected in and through maps and transforming the authori-

ty' to write the earth (Alderman et al., 2021). Counter-mapping could be done through using institutional map-making in 'bottom-up ways'. However, for this project, a wide range of experimental forms and creative practices and collaborations will be deployed to align with the practical needs and political objectives of local communities.

Law and Space, Inequalities, Marginalised Communities,
Counter-Mapping, Community Advocacy

Reading Spatial Justice through Google Maps Reviews: A Case Study of Esenyurt Square

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One of the pieces of information provided through Google Maps is the ability for Google users to write reviews about a place. Without the requirement of visiting or residing in the area, everyone has the right to write reviews about any place listed on Google Maps. This dataset provides city planners with the opportunity to read and analyze spatial usage experiences. Within this context, it has been observed that injustice exists in the spatial experiences of user groups who have experienced Esenyurt Square, a public square in Istanbul. With its multicultural population fueled by external migration, the Esenyurt district occasionally becomes a stage for conflicts among these different groups. As the most central square in the district, Esenyurt Square is also a place where these conflicts take place, and as such, the atmosphere of conflict can be discerned in the comments related to the square. In brief, local residents who have resided in the district for a long time have voiced complaints about the use of the square and the dominance of newcomers, leading them to seek alternative locations. Here, spatial injustice arises due to the inability to establish coexistence policies, resulting in inequality in the use and access to space among different groups. Spatial injustice occurs when there is unfairness or inequality in the access to or usage of a space by a specific community, group, or individual. The group that arrives through migration unconsciously restricts the equal access and usage of the space by the other group. Therefore, the newcomer group is not the factor creating injustice, and both groups experience a sense of injustice. What is lacking in this context is the absence of coexis-

tence policies. This study aims to explain how this analysis is conducted and to detail the dimensions of spatial injustice through the reviews of different groups about the square. Thus, the goal is to propose a method for evaluating spatial justice.

Spatial Usage Experiences, Spatial Injustice, Esenyurt Square, Coexistence Policies, Google Maps

An explorative design-based methodology to assess, project and operationalize spatial justice in conditions of ethnic conflict: The case of Eelam Tamils in the North-East of Sri Lanka

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The dominance of Western Spatial Justice theory has often overlooked the vulnerabilities of minority ethnic groups amidst conditions of oppressive power and ethnic conflict. This necessitates an alternative approach and reimagined context-specific perspectives to better address the realities faced by marginalized populations and their pursuit of justice and self-determination. This research aims to investigate how an explorative design-based methodology could enable alternative spatial-political imaginaries and uncover new insights for design, planning, and policy toward context-sensitive spatial justice for Eelam Tamils in Sri Lanka's north-east.

In doing so, this research reconceptualized spatial justice as a theoretical construct, that more accurately reflects a context characterized by ethnic conflict and systemic oppression. The alternative conceptual framework serves as indicators for assessing and projecting the territorial, procedural, and socio-economic implications of spatial justice within the North-East of Sri Lanka. Through the use of transcalar spatial mapping, sociospatial, and statistical analysis, challenges and opportunities were identified that were core in the development of hypothetical spatial political scenarios. This played a central role in the backcasting of different spatial-political futures, simulating different institutional, territorial and socio-economic configurations at the regional, urban, and architectural scales.

By reconceptualizing spatial justice through the lens of oppressed Eelam, particularly in their pursuit of self-determination within a

context of conflict, alternative futures become conceivable. Unlocking these spatial-political imaginaries aids in identifying novel ideas and insights for design, planning, and policy in operationalizing spatial justice such as new land use strategies, the transformation of public space, and coalitions between critical stakeholders. These scenarios enabled an alternative reality to play out where untapped potential and unique opportunities emerged.

The lessons learned and insights gained from applying such a design-based methodology, in this case, could prove valuable in similar contexts. An explorative approach, using design, has the potential to generate alternative pathways and ideas toward self-determination and spatial justice that take into account institutional, political, and territorial dynamics within conditions of ethnic conflict. Regarding future research, this methodology would require additional testing and exploration to understand how design could play a role in conceptualizing and operationalizing spatial justice in conditions of conflict.

Spatial Justice, Ethnic Conflict, Design-Based Methodology
Self-Determination, Minority Ethnic Groups

Visibilising the Invisible: The Hidden Everyday Practices of Urban Scavengers in a Just Circular Transition

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Waste is often perceived as “unwanted resources” in the urban landscape, ideally relegated to underground garbage bins and out of public sight and mind. Usually overlooked but always there, urban scavengers silently navigate city streets in their search for valuable resources that others discarded. An estimated 1% of the global population derives their livelihood from scavenging. As waste itself, urban scavengers remain unseen – often operating at nighttime to avoid social stigma. In some cities, they function alongside official municipal waste management systems, while in others, they serve as the sole means of waste collection.

Our study posits that urban scavengers are not mere waste collectors but key contributors to urban circularity, bringing along unique knowledge and strong social networks – which ‘formal’ circular approaches often struggle to build. However, despite these contributions, their work remains largely unrecognised, due to the social devaluation of waste and the work associated with it. In many cases, urban scavengers struggle with conditions of informality, precarious working conditions, and a lack of access to space. The current discourse of circular transition on the urban level prioritises top-down approaches and technological innovation – but misses out on recognising the potential contribution of existing practices, such as scavenging.

Our research aims to close this gap with three objectives: first, to bring visibility to the often-invisible practices of urban scavengers; second, to scrutinise the spatial and social aspects of their operations; and third, to explore ways to formally recognise their contributions through equitable remuneration, safe

er working conditions, and legitimate spatial access. We argue that “formal” approaches to circularity, such as municipal recycling systems, can learn much from scavenger’s self-organised social networks, forms of collaboration, and creative use of urban space.

To explore this, we employ ethnographic methods in three distinctive urban contexts: the cartoneros/as in Buenos Aires, the korales in Addis Ababa, and the chatarreros/as and traperos/as in Barcelona. Through methods like shadowing, observations, and walk-along interviews, we map socio-spatial aspects such as their daily routes, storage facilities, points of redistribution, and social networks. Second, the study will extract lessons learned from scavenging practices. Third, it will examine the interplay between formal and informal systems operating within the same urban environment.

Our study seeks not only to “visibilise” but also to valorize the vital but often overlooked roles of urban scavengers. In doing so, this study contributes to a more inclusive and equitable discourse on circular transition in urban planning. It challenges binary categorizations of formality and informality, advocating instead for a nuanced understanding that acknowledges the rich diversity of urban economies. The expected outcome is not just a rethinking of waste management strategies but a push toward a just circular transition that harmoniously integrates both environmental sustainability and social justice within diverse urban economies.

Urban Scavengers, Waste, Circular Transition, Social Justice, Diverse Community Economies, Urban Ethnography

RECOGNITION

11:10-12:10

ROOM K

4

Designing Public Space for All: A Review on the Key Challenges of Older People's Inclusiveness

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Globally, it is paramount that the design of public space deals with the older people's specific needs, given the increasing population ageing and the social exclusion that this age group may endure due to built environment misfits. As such, the age-friendliness of cities is guided by three key core principles: equity, accessibility of the physical environment, and inclusiveness of the social environment (WHO, 2015). Equity refers to the spatial justice between sub-groups and the total population. The accessibility of the physical environment concerns the fact if the public space design considers the older people context, namely: i) the neighbourhood walkability and physical activity of older persons, ii) safety and comfort of public space, iii) accessibility of public spaces and buildings; iv) access to public transports; and v) affordability of housing. Inherently, considering the dignity of older persons as public space users should raise the inclusiveness of the social environment and the cities' spatial justice, creating opportunities for social interaction with all age groups and lowering exclusion, isolation, and social dissimilarity. Accordingly, for the public space to be more inclusive, it is mandatory to empower the participation of older people in the local decision-making of its design. Besides that, the public built environment is still not fully accessible and inclusive for older people, especially when the design of green streets, which integrate active mobility modes such as bicycles and scooters as well as vegetation, does not consider the context of the older persons as pedestrians and as users of a shared public space.

Under the scope of a large research project (name omitted for anonymous review), our main goal is to research the effects of the urban green streets design on mobility, social integration, and ageism against older people.

As such, we will present a literature review and a methodological framework to debate which challenges still exist regarding the inclusion of older people in the public space design process, namely in the design of streets.

Firstly, the sustainable development and climate change agendas advocate a necessary transition to carbon-neutral mobility that does not safeguard the older person as a pedestrian when sharing the public space with bicycles and other soft mobility modes, constituting a paramount spatial justice challenge.

Secondly, we expect to identify the dimensions of inclusiveness of older people in the street's quality design, focusing on their public space sharing with bicycles and scooters.

Thirdly and above all, it is imperative to involve older people in the design of more inclusive streets. Therefore, we propose a methodological framework to build a tool to assess the street quality for older people and identify which streets are more suitable for older people, e.g. with joint cycle and sidewalk lanes or with separate lanes. In this context, our proposed methodological framework focuses on the one hand, on observation and the application of questionnaires to older persons and, on the other, on interviews with stakeholders.

Thus, only a cross-sectorial collaboration can carry out this transition to a more just public space.

Age-Friendly Cities, Spatial Justice, Urban Green Streets
Mobility, Inclusiveness

Making visible other ethnic representations: the moderating effect of harmony in Rotterdam

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Urban renewal programs build their legitimacy upon the premise that negative perceptions of social cohesion trigger people to move from their neighbourhoods. In super-diverse cities, low social cohesion is often linked to ethnic diversity. Cultural differences prevent having the same views about what is and is not allowed in the neighbourhood, increasing the willingness to move from the neighbourhood (Figure 1a). Such assumption lies at the basis of many breaches to recognitional justice in urban policies in Rotterdam, problematising ethnicity and migrant populations (Scholten et al., 2019), enabling ethnic-based urban revanchism (Van Eijk, 2010), and structuring territories of exceptionality by ethnic profiling (Uitermark et al., 2017). I argue that one can de-problematize ethnicity by researching perceptions of harmonic inter-ethnic interactions moderating the expected negative effect of neighborhood diversity on sharing views and, altogether, the willingness to move (Figure 1b). I test two models, using a database of perceptions of neighbourhood cohesion surveying 14662 people in Rotterdam (2019) and a Herfindahl-Hirschman-based Diversity Index of their neighbourhoods (buurt). Results are based on SEM-PLS modelling on the 63% of people interviewed who expressed an opinion on this concern (n=9264).

Results support Model 1. There is a significant negative effect of “Neighborhood ethnic diversity” on “Shared views on rules” ($\beta = -0.1800$; 95% CI=[-0.2015; -0.1604]), and a positive significant effect on “Will to move from the neighborhood” ($\beta = 0.1469$; 95% CI=[0.1274; 0.1665]). On another hand, “Shared views on rules” has a significant negative effect on Will to move from the neighborhood ($\beta = -0.2654$; 95% CI=[-0.2874; -0.2439]). The model can explain the 3% and 10%

of the variance in “Shared views on rules” and “Will to move from the neighborhood.”

Model 2 assessment indicates that Ethnic harmony perception counteracts the effects in the original model. For individuals with an average perception of ethnic harmony, the effect of “Neighbourhood ethnic diversity” on “Will to move from the neighborhood” scores $\beta = 0.1516$ (95% CI=[0.1338; 0.1693]). However, for those whose perception of ethnic harmony ranks one standard deviation above the average, the effect of Neighbourhood ethnic diversity” on “Will to move from the neighborhood” reduces to $\beta = 0.1271$. This is due the moderating effect of $\beta = -0.0245$ (95% CI=[-0.0469; -0.0013]) (Figure 2). Similarly, the effect of “Neighbourhood ethnic diversity” on “Shared views on rules” increases by $\beta = 0.0301$ (95% CI=[0.0071; 0.0518]), and the effect of “Shared views on rules” on “Will to move from the neighborhood” increases by $\beta = 0.0454$ (95% CI=[0.0262; 0.0642]) for those with above-average perceptions. These results indicate that even when one can find evidence problematizing ethnic diversity to some degree, introducing the ‘perception of harmony’ shifts the policy question to conditions that might increase its moderating effect. By doing so, I showcase how scrutinizing official surveys can open up possibilities for alternative representations of ethnicity. This is not a trivial issue. Surveys for benchmarking Rotterdam have played a role in disparaging people through stereotypical cultural representations. In any case, the low variance explained by the model suggests the need for a better understanding of the factors that trigger people to move and shape their perceptions of shared normative views beyond the degree of ethnic diversity, including why many do not express an opinion.

Urban Renewal, Social Cohesion, Ethnic Diversity,
Perceptions, Neighbourhood Dynamics

Bridging the Gap: Pedagogy for Addressing Socio-Spatial Public Transit Exclusions in India

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In Spatial Justice praxis, decoding socio-spatial exclusions and understanding of spatial inequalities are foundational (Soja, 2009). Therefore, in all educational processes that intend to incorporate social justice education or to benchmark it, methodologies to decode these socio-spatial exclusions and understand how to map, comprehend, and attempt to measure them, need to be introduced. This paper presents a pedagogical framework designed to enhance the robustness of analysing and addressing socio-spatial exclusion in the Global South (specifically Bengaluru, India). Focused on the themes of urban mobility and public transit infrastructure, this pedagogy was implemented in a thesis design studio at Srishti Institute of Art, Design & Technology comprising of twenty-eight students. Several factors underscore the necessity for this pedagogical approach. There is a need for greater quantity of resources that address context-specific exclusions and spatial justice studies in India and the Global South to facilitate comprehensive examinations of spatial inequalities (Srinivasan, 2022). For instance, literature prescribing methods for measuring gentrification in the Indian context or prescribed methods for mapping socio-spatial exclusions within informal economies such as street vending unique to the Global South. The need for this pedagogy is especially substantiated by a need for actionable tools based on spatial justice literature for both practitioners and students. This paper also makes a case for incorporating nuanced theories pertaining to exclusions such as intersectionality and cognitive mapping from other fields to bolster spatial justice methodology. The design studio was titled "Bridging the Gap: Decoding Transit, Exclusion". The pedagogy was designed in-line with critical pedagogy (Freire et al., 1993) as one of the pedagogical frameworks, consciously integrating the principles of dialogical education, critical

consciousness, problem-posing education, liberation, and praxis. The paper presents this pedagogy as a five-step process:

- 1) EVALUATION: Critical assessment of existing approaches for studying spatial exclusion in transit infrastructure.
- 2) INTEGRATION: Incorporating interdisciplinary methods and concepts to enhance research methods.
- 3) INTERACTION & ENGAGEMENT: Engaging in co-design and public participatory studies to gain deep contextual insights into mobility injustices.
- 4) INSIGHT GENERATION: Creating exclusion maps and generating insights on mapping, measuring, and categorizing spatial exclusions.
- 5) IDEATION: Bridging the gap between spatial design literature and practice with respect to urban mobility and public transit infrastructure.

In addition to this, a strategic partnership was struck with the Bengaluru Metro Rail Corporation Limited (BMRCL) to allow students to study the metro stations in Bengaluru and address issues on-ground.

Over 50% of the students created outcomes in the form of toolkits and frameworks that display potential to become new benchmarks and methodologies for analysing and/or addressing inequalities in mobility justice in the Indian context. Others produced designed outcomes such as artistic interventions and activist or government campaigns that called for socio-spatial justice and equality in public transit. These outputs addressed a wide range of issues including walkability, gentrification, public participation, wayfinding, gendered mobilities, ecological impacts etc. The paper examines and evaluates the effectiveness of the pedagogy through case studies of student work, illustrating its potential to foster the creation of new spatial justice benchmarks in practice. The paper concludes by contemplating the implications of adopting this pedagogy to establish benchmarks for spatial justice.

Spatial Justice, Socio-Spatial Exclusion, Pedagogical Framework, Urban Mobility, Public Transit Infrastructure

The Delft Design for Values Institute

Marielle Feenstra

Why design for values?

The 21st century is characterised by rapid change and fast-paced technological development. Countries are struggling to face economic, social, political and environmental challenges. People are migrating to megacities, natural resources are becoming increasingly scarce, and changes in the global climate are becoming intensely palpable. Breakthroughs in science and technology offer hope for the betterment of the planet and the human condition, but bring in turn, ethical questions, including debates on the social implications of scientific and technological advances, and the distributive justice of access to beneficial forms of technology.

If we want to ensure that new technologies in the 21st century benefit rather than endanger humankind and the planet, we need to design them for values. We need to integrate moral and social values from the very start in the design process of new systems, products and services. Doing so will help to design technologies that are both morally acceptable, i.e., that respect relevant moral values such as sustainability, beneficence and justice, and socially accepted, i.e., that address the values and needs of relevant stakeholders.

What is design for values?

Design for values is a design approach aimed at integrating values in all stages of the design process. It foregrounds sensitivity to values instead of seeing them as a mere constraint at the end of a design process. Design for values addresses values through a design approach, aimed at finding new creative solutions for societal and moral challenges.

Research, development and innovations are designed to advance technology, to stimulate business and to serve society. Responsible research and innovation framework is emerging in design principles to ensure that the impact on society is not only responsible but also serving other ethical and moral values, like justice. The involvement of end-users and stakeholders in the design process is one example of integrating justice in design.

Design for values requires the integration of different kinds of expertise and skills. It requires knowledge of and expertise in design, philosophical knowledge of values and relevant moral theories, and domain knowledge of specific technologies. TU Delft is uniquely positioned to bring such knowledge and skills together in one institute. It is well known for its excellence in engineering and design, but it also has unique expertise in philosophy and ethics of technology. In the last few decades, researchers from TU Delft have internationally played a prominent role in (further) developing the design for values approach.

<https://www.delftdesignforvalues.nl>

Marielle Feenstra is the coordinator of the Delft Design for Values Institute and a postdoctoral researcher on gender and inclusive research and innovation. Her PhD research resulted in a gender just energy policy framework juxtaposing gender approaches and energy justice tenets.

PROCEDURAL

13:40-14:40

ROOM K

5

Towards Spatial Justice in Arab Countries: A Comparative Analysis of the Local Governance, Participation, and Public Space in Tunisia, Lebanon, Jordan, Sudan, Iraq and Egypt

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Decentralisation in urban governance has proven to be one important factor for enhancing the quality of urban life. Moreover, democracy within Cities development can be achieved through participation, supported by relations within networks, relying on comparative urbanism and cities learning from each other. However, local authorities in many Arab-MENA countries suffer from a lack of finances and resources, as well as from having less control over decision-making, which often occurs at the national level through a centralised structure. That shapes a challenge to achieve spatial justice in these countries, especially through participatory process in creating public spaces. This paper is a part of the research project 'PR-GPS, Power Relations in Local Urban Governance: participation in Arab public space' funded by the DAAD Ta'ziz network program (2023- 2025), in initiated by the Habitat Unit, TU Berlin, with cooperation with academic and non-academic actors, including universities, local governments and civil society from 6 Arab countries; Tunisia, Lebanon, Jordan, Iraq, Sudan and Egypt. This network aims to enhance democracy and spatial justice in the partner Arab countries. This paper aims to compare the urban governance in the different partner countries, through understanding the structure of power relations, different terms and definitions, participation and public space according to every country's laws, perceptions and local context. This paper mainly depends on literature, and legal references from each country. Towards understanding the local governance system in each country, this paper will investigate the power relations, politics including the different stakeholders involved, the

different levels (such as local, district, national), and their relationships. Moreover, it will show a description of the current competencies of the lowest levels and if there is a process for decentralisation and transfer of competencies and the decision making process. We will analyse the participation factors and levels according to the laws, the practices and the local context of every partner country, trying to answer these following questions in every partner country: How is participation defined? Is it mentioned in the regulations ? What are the reasons for the emergence of participation? What are the different topics where participation can be ensured in formal and informal manners? - What are the different levels of participation? What are the approaches ? What are the impacts and limits ? This paper focuses on the public spaces in different types and functions (e.g. public parks or gardens, kids' areas, street markets), is one of the most important areas for urban governance, and has a great role in shaping the urban forms and functions of a city. Further, it plays an important role, socially, economically, environmentally as well as politically, which is eventually a reason for conflict creation amongst actors. So this paper attempts to answer the following questions based on the laws, the perceptions and the local context of every partner country: -What are the different definitions of Public space(s)?- What are the different types of public space? -What are the processes of creating/improving a public space? - What are the main conclusions of studies on the perception, ownership and uses of public space? What are the ingredients for an enlarged use of public space?

Decentralisation, Urban Governance, Participation, Spatial Justice, Public Spaces, MENA Region

How to Select Communities for Urban Resilience Building Initiatives

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The Resilience for Communities program (R4C), executed by the Resilient Cities Network, is underway in Boston, Houston, Greater Manchester, and Melaka. In close collaboration with local government, R4C aims to enhance vulnerable communities' resilience to climate-related hazards such as heat and floods. Through the program, local governments will gain a deeper understanding of actions and solutions that can help their communities become more resilient. In each of these four cities, together with the local authorities we identified two communities with which to co-design resilience-building initiatives. Our approach to selecting the two communities is centred around three factors: exposure to selected climate hazards, vulnerability, and the enabling environment. We found that each city has a unique context and requires a different approach to measuring these three factors. Therefore, we deployed a mixed-method approach to inform our decisions. This was a combination of consensus building, quantitative data analysis, qualitative data gathering, and competitive bids. For assessing exposure, the primary reliance was on quantitative metrics, utilising climate hazard maps alongside flood and heat data. Special emphasis was placed on cross-referencing these data points with historical weather patterns and projected climate scenarios to ensure a robust and forward-looking assessment. Each region used a different approach to measure vulnerability. In the US vulnerability was measured using existing census data, in Melaka the lack of data was bridged by using key informant interviews and site visits. In Greater Manchester an existing tool, the Neighborhood Flood Vulnerability Index, was used to measure community vulnerability to flooding.

One of the most critical components of the

selection process, and the project's overall success is the enabling environment. These are central to understanding how a community interacts with and responds to resilience-building initiatives. Elements such as existing climate strategies, community participation levels, the community's role in the broader city ecosystem, and even the presence of active volunteer organisations offer invaluable insights into the project's feasibility and potential impact. Furthermore, residents' attitudes toward governmental interventions and historical perspectives on community initiatives can significantly influence the program's reception and efficacy. To tailor our approach to each city's unique context, we adopted diverse methodologies for gathering this information. In U.S. cities, we leveraged consensus-driven workshops with local authorities. In Greater Manchester, a competitive Expression of Interest (EOI) application and interview process were utilised. Meanwhile, in Melaka, direct site visits and interviews with key community stakeholders offered the necessary insights. By integrating these enabling factors into our selection process, we aim to build not just resilient but also empowered and engaged communities.

Key Findings:

1. **Diverse Methodologies:** The use of both quantitative and qualitative data enriched the selection process and provided a nuanced understanding of community-specific challenges and opportunities.
2. **Contextual Adaptation:** The approach was highly adaptable, allowing for context-specific customisation in each city, which led to more targeted and effective resilience-building initiatives.

Community Resilience, Climate-Related Hazards, Vulnerability Assessment, Enabling Environment

JUST GROW? Co-designing justice-centric indicators to understand trends of intensification in urban agricultural systems

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Urban and peri-urban areas are increasingly being imagined as sites for sustainable intensification of agricultural production to meet the growing global demand for food in the future. Planners, municipal actors, citizen groups, and businesses see integrating food production into urban spaces as promising to shorten supply chains and reconnect producers and consumers while meeting goals of improving socio-environmental sustainability and resilience.

Sustainable urban agricultural intensification (UAI) is likely to involve increased use of technologies that envision decoupling food production from environmental conditions (such as seasonal climate and available land). Technological systems range from capital-intensive approaches such as vertical farms to more knowledge-intensive approaches such as urban agroecology. As demands of social and ecological resilience are providing legitimacy for urban agricultural intensification, the justice dimension of urban food governance remains largely unaddressed.

The JUST GROW project (2023-2026) aims to fill this research gap by studying six urban regions in a transnational, transdisciplinary research approach: the Rhine-Ruhr metropolitan region (Germany), the Greater Providence metropolitan region (RI, USA), the Rotterdam-Amsterdam-Den Haag metropolitan region (Netherlands), the Keihanshin (Kyoto-Osaka-Kobe) metropolitan region (Japan), the Trondheim-Trondelag region (Norway) and the Greater Stockholm region (Sweden).

The project proposes a comparative assessment of equity and justice impacts of different development pathways for sustainable urban food systems will shed light on multiple potential futures of UAI.

To holistically integrate equity considerations into policy and governance structures for new food systems, the project will expose the hidden justice dimensions in existing, planned, or imagined intensification of urban food systems. We propose five dimensions that of UAI are central to characterizing the equity of UAI: land access, labor equity, food security, environmental impacts, and cultural sustainability. Centering justice in the governance of urban food will provide indicators that city regions can use to assess the impact of specific UAI approaches on different equity dimensions in new food consumption and production systems. Within the project recommendations for transformative, justice-oriented policy innovations and principles will be developed that will strengthen city region governance networks to steer UAI towards a just food system.

Sustainable Urban Agricultural Intensification (UAI), Food Governance, Equity and Justice, Urban Food Systems, Policy Innovation

PROCEDURAL

13:40-14:40

ROOM U

6

Co-designing towards Spatial Justice: In Policy and Practice

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We are happy to put forward a presentation on an on-going interdisciplinary and international project (funded by the Royal Institute of British Architects, University College London and the British Council) on the potentials of co-designing for spatial justice, health and wellbeing.

We see this as an opportunity to share our findings and ideas in regard to forging new modes of co-making in future cities, and to challenge the currently dominant approaches in city development that focus on aspects of capital, infrastructure and technology as the basis for better and healthier living. We are keen to find ways to contribute to countering the growing alienation of people, othering, increasing precarity, vulnerability and contestation. In the same line, we believe that people are agents of their lives. As such, a precondition for a dignified living is the ability to influence the transformation of their surrounding environments.

Managing our coexistence in shared urban spaces as co-created urban commons should convey multiple narratives and foster inclusion and engagement for healthy and equitable living. The collaborative process of place-making can contribute to designing the marginalised groups in the public spaces, decrease environmental inequalities and reduce health inequities. The concept of 'participation' has been part of urban discourses for decades. However, although 'participatory tools' have become common practice, until today, the standards fall short of achieving the implied and aspired goals, and cases where they contribute to empowerment or transformative development of excluded and marginalised groups have been the exception rather than the rule (Hickey & Mo-

han 2004, Healey 1992). This is due to the fact that hitherto most methods imply symbolic participation (Dryzek 2000), which was already described as 'manipulation' and 'therapy' back in the 1960's (e.g. Arnstein 1969), and this seems to have not fundamentally changed. Citizens' involvement has little if any influence on urban processes, and many supposedly 'participatory' approaches can be described as mere tokenism.

Over the course of three years, we have developed international case studies on different methods of co-design, as part of the report 'Towards Spatial Justice: A guide for achieving meaningful participation in co-design processes' (2022), co-authored by Jane Wong, Tom Greenall and Lydia Toohey, which provides a whole host of tools and resources for designers and built-environment practitioners to refer to and adapt in their own work. Building off this report, we developed a collaboration with the Greater London Council and the Bremen Senate to create city-to-city learning on different ways of commissioning and delivering participatory or co-design projects, identifying the key challenges at both the strategic level and local delivery.

Our work brought together together policy-makers, academics, and practitioners, including architects, urban designers, public health experts, engagement facilitators and public realm experts to develop strategic guidance for co-design at local governance level. We would like to share peer-reviewed findings, results from the application of the aforementioned guidance and tools on live projects, and strategic recommendations to influence future policymaking.

Co-design, Spatial Justice, Health & Wellbeing
Participatory Tools, Urban Commons

Seeking a Just Transition for Social Inclusion

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The research was based on European Project “Placemaking for Inclusion”, conducted in 6 European countries (Germany, Belgium, Spain, Italy, Greece and Norway). Our team is consisting of practioners, educators, urban researchers, youth workers and municipality consultant. In the framework of recognitional justice, we have observed that social exclusion remains one of the biggest challenges in our society, starting at the neighbourhood quarters in the cities where often young people live surrounded by the invisible borders defined by culture, religion or traditions, additionally influenced by transition that are irreversibly changing the dynamics. The search of inclusive paradigm has become a powerful agenda and mobilising force for new social movements, extending the concept of justice beyond the social and the economic to new forms of struggle and activism. Within the context of a rapidly shifting society, with upheavals in the labour market, the social and political sphere, and the very physical environment, it is clear that challenging social exclusion requires inclusive tools. These tools must be collaboratively developed by broad sets of stakeholders and must provide moments, resources, and structures for the empowerment of the individual by society for active participation in social, political, and economic life and society. “Placemaking” as the recognitional instrument in spatial and social justice is also emphasised as a process of co-design, aiming not so much at the construction but at the deconstruction of the real, in order to enable a ‘reactivation’ of the place and the community that lives there. We see “Placemaking” as the result of social construction with emphasis on how places fundamentally constituted by social relations and reflexive practice (Massey, 2005; Murdoch, 2006; Sheller and Urry, 2006). The used methodology aimed at

this research, on the one hand, to engage critical informants on this topic and exchange experience during the “knowledge dialogue” and, on the other hand, to build a progressive mapping system as a base to evaluate the level of development of placemaking initiatives and their relation to grassroots initiatives in 6 European countries. The progressive maps (preliminary conversations, the focus groups, the survey, and from each of the partners’ experiences) were created for each of the partner countries. In addition to this progressive mapping and focus groups, local surveys have been done in each country to incorporate a direct youth and youth workers’ perspective on placemaking and validate the results. The conclusions have two readings: on the one hand, the local scale of the six countries, and on the other hand, their comparison. The conclusions focus on comparative findings from the mappings, the survey, the focus group’s social investigation, and the engagement competencies. In all six countries, placemaking for inclusion is recognized as an opportunity to empower youth and youth workers in decision-making. This transnational research highlighted the importance of the key findings on the competence for citizen engagement. Based on 6 case studies undertaken by qualitative research, observation and continuous documentation, the research draws on recent work on the placemaking and youth engagement and the assemblages of urban policy. It highlights the role of the cultural politics and urban practices, and its implications for value transferability across continents in creating networks and connections between and within places. The main hypothesis argued for is the frontier of innovative and experimental practices to the establishment of an apparatus for framing the cities that are taking shape in a more horizontal planning approach.

Placemaking, Social Inclusion, Recognitional Justice
Youth Engagement, Grassroot Initiatives

Measuring spatial justice: Including children as creative knowledge producers

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Inclusive approaches to measuring spatial justice often share goals of amplifying quiet voices, including those previously marginalised from planning processes and planning in such a way that is responsive to needs and desires of residents. However, children and youth are often left out of these processes, even though they live in every city. As young people are a source of creative energy and innovative ideas that adults may miss, it is a lost opportunity to not include them. Children and youth also have a unique perspective on their communities and on justice, as their daily activities, needs, and wants are different from adults. What does it mean to include children and youth in a city? How do we acknowledge their right to use of space? How do we ensure that opportunities within a city are fairly distributed between young people and adults and also among young people with different lived experiences? This session will take the form of an interactive workshop to build together a toolkit for involving children in measuring and benchmarking spatial justice, expanding on tools that already exist. Using digital tools to facilitate collaboration, we will think through the goals of including children and youth in measurement, ways to collect data with youth of different ages (from young children to young adults), how to involve young people in scientifically grounded analysis of data, and how to incorporate this data into planning processes run by adults. We will also discuss ways to involve children and youth in collaborative processes such as through youth advisory boards, and discuss challenges that may arise in implementing youth involvement. The session will build on work by Geertje Slingerland co-designing outdoor spaces with children and designing playable cities along with

work by K Maeve Powlick in co-creative research with undocumented youth in the Netherlands and collaborative program evaluation with children participating in afterschool programs. This session is proposed as part of the track on “methodological approaches for measuring and assessing spatial justice.”

Spatial Justice, Inclusive Approaches, Children and Youth
Measurement and Benchmarking, Youth Involvement

PROCEDURAL

13:40-14:40

BERLAGEZAAL 2

Unravelling the Role of Social Organisations in Integrated Urban Regeneration: The Case of Brussels

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The interconnected nature of the urban problems concentrated in disadvantaged areas has led many cities over the last three decades to develop and implement urban policies of Integrated Urban Regeneration (IUR) based on holistic, area-based and decentralised approaches. Going beyond sectoral approaches and combining diverse expertise with financial and human resources, such policies aspire to develop integrated solutions to combat economic, social and environmental challenges (Musterd and Ostendorf 2008). Central features of IUR strategies are the partnerships of diverse stakeholders and the participation of citizens in the design and implementation of local projects. Nevertheless, since the conception of IUR in the 1990s scholars have vigorously raised the issue of neglecting the needs and interests of vulnerable groups due to their underrepresentation or total exclusion from participatory processes (Gaventa 2003; Klöti, Drilling, and Fabian 2017) and others have called for attention on the question of who actually benefits and who should benefit from IUR (Robinson and Shaw 1991). In this context, authors have acknowledged the potential of community-based organisations to address these challenges through the exploration of innovative models of service provision, addressing local needs and enhancing democratic processes (Healey, 2015). Some call the planning research community to allocate greater attention to the development and impact of community organisations (Bailey, 2012; Healey, 2015; Monardo, 2013).

The research is part of an interdisciplinary PhD project which aims to explore the role of

third sector community organisations in processes of citizen participation of disadvantaged areas within the framework of Integrated Urban Regeneration policies. The questions that seek to answers are related to the profile of these actors, their approach towards participation and the relevant challenges they face. The research uses qualitative methods and multiple case studies for the collection and analysis of data: document analysis and semi-structured interviews with neighbourhood organisations participating in the policy of the Sustainable Neighbourhood Contracts (hereafter CQD from French Contrats de Quartiers Durables), an exemplary case of IUR strategy implemented by Brussels Capital-Region since 1994. The creation of the CQD is directly linked to the social uprisings of 1991 in neighbourhoods with immigrant populations, highlighting the need for holistic social improvements and integration measures. The findings of this study indicate differences among the organisations related to the approach towards citizen participation ranging from institutional to grassroots social movements. The former adheres to the formal participation and consultation criteria stipulated by the Urban Planning Department of the region. At the same time, the latter encompasses all informal activities conducted by these organisations beyond the established frameworks. Qualitative data underscores the intrinsic connection of these patterns to aspects of heritage, governance, and the organisations' dynamics with the state. Future research will delve deeper into the primary challenge recognised by the organisations: environmental gentrification.

Integrated Urban Regeneration (IUR), Citizen Participation, Disadvantaged Areas, Community-Based Organisations, Sustainable Neighbourhood Contracts

Analysis of the dynamics of public space appropriation during a participatory planning process. Case of Borj Louzir, Tunisia

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In Tunisia, as in other countries in the southern Mediterranean region, the study of public space must incorporate the specificity of traditional modes of urban production, which shape public space differently from Western urban composition methods (David 2002). It must also consider the fact that the social production of territory often occurs with a gap from formal urban planning (Cattedra 2005). In addition to this observation, since the Tunisian revolution of 2010-2011, and considering the 12 years since then, there have been transformations observed in the appropriation and practices of public spaces on the one hand (Sebastiani et al. 2016), and in urban development and governance policies on the other.

Based on this observation, we will focus our study on a public space created in the popular area of Borj Louzir in Soukra, north of Greater Tunis, as part of a formal project initiated by public authorities and designed within a modern urban operational framework. Our objective is to track, through a case study analysis, the changes in the practices of local residents in a public garden following a redevelopment initiative and the adoption of an approach that included citizen participation in the design and implementation of the project. This methodology of action research was initiated between 2022 and 2023 when we launched a redevelopment operation for this public garden, seeking to involve different stakeholders, including institutional representatives, primary school students, and neighbours in different steps of the design process of the public space. Subsequently, we observed user practices during the implementation phase and evaluated the state of the public space one year after its cre-

ation. This case will be compared to a recent case study that has been initiated recently in order to better understand the power relations in both cases and the dynamics of stakeholders within the public space.

Two major observations emerge from our analysis. The first concerns the diversity of approaches to engaging with public spaces, ranging from prolonged use to complete opposition to the existence or redevelopment of the site, with determinants evolving based on the specificity of exposure and the physical relationship to public space. The second observation pertains to the evolution noted in space appropriation through practices and protection, which varies from one group to another and follows a trend of decline over time, motivated by the damage inflicted on public space.

Action Research, Urban Governance, Citizen Participation, Public Space, Tunisia

Moving Towards Healthy Ageing: Understanding and Promoting Cycling Behavior Among Older Adults in Munich

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Introduction: In the context of an ageing world population, cities need to take action to adapt to the needs of older people and facilitate their independence, health and well-being. Active mobility brings economic, social, environmental and health benefits. Cycling tends to decline with age, despite its potential to minimise dependency, social isolation, mobility problems and sedentary lifestyles. There is a lack of comprehensive understanding of the factors associated with cycling among older people, which limits efforts to develop cycling initiatives for this population. Therefore, this study aims to assess the variables that influence cycling behaviour of adults and older adults.

Methods: Taking Munich as a case study, this study has been developed through a quantitative approach, including spatial analysis for neighbourhood's built environment characteristics (5D's) and a national mobility survey for personal or individual level information regarding sociodemographic variables, transport modes availability and use of transport modes.

Results: Statistical differences were found between older and younger adults in the use and frequency of cycling. The neighbourhood's built environment had a greater influence on the cycling behaviour of older adults than for younger adults. The results revealed that older people living in peripheral neighbourhoods were more likely to use the bicycle as a means of transport. Currently, these neighbourhoods have a higher percentage of green areas, lower intersection density and lower motorized traffic, all of which are factors associated with safety and barriers for cycling for older adults. In both age groups, higher income and education

levels exhibited higher odds of cycling. Additionally, occasional car and public transport users were more likely to cycle, which may be related to combined trips.

Conclusions: These findings could help urban planners and practitioners to design cities that promote cycling among all populations, especially older adults, to achieve healthy ageing as a lifelong process.

Active Mobility, Cycling Behavior, Older Adults, Built Environment, Healthy Aging

DISTRIBUTIVE
13:40-14:40
BERLAGEZAAL 1

Quantifying Accessibility in Public Transit Systems using Learned Vector Embeddings

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Public transit serves as a key resource in the pursuit of developing sustainable and equitable cities. However, given that many cities have yet to establish fully accessible subway/metro stations across the entirety of their transit network, spatial injustice exists for people with mobility disabilities who require an accessible means of travel.

Given this context, this paper seeks to quantify and map public transit accessibility for those with mobility disabilities, generating a mobility access index such that it is possible to perform intra- and inter-city study and comparison of transit accessibility.

Using Milan, Italy as a case study, this paper proposes using a process of unsupervised feature learning to generate vector embeddings - a technique from natural language processing (Mikolov et al. 2013; LeCun, Bengio, and Hinton 2015) - to study, quantify, and generate a public transit accessibility index. This approach has been adapted for mapping other transit and spatial data (gtfs2vec, urban2vec, highway2vec) (Wang, Li, and Rajagopal 2020; Gramacki, Woźniak, and Szymański 2021; Leśniara and Szymański 2023), however to the best of the author's knowledge it has yet to be adapted for studying transit accessibility for those with mobility disabilities.

To prepare data for this study, the city of Milan is subdivided into 251 equally sized hexagon subregions (~900m diameter) using Uber's H3 Hexagonal Hierarchical Spatial Index (fig. 1). The centroid of each hexagon is taken as the trip start and end points. For each hexagonal subregion, a trip using public transit is conducted using Google Directions API from that hexagon to every other hexagon (fig. 2)

with the following data being collected using Google's Directions API, Maps API, and Elevation API:

- A true/false value for whether that trip can be made successfully by someone using a mobility aid.
- Number of individual segments of the trip that are not fully accessible.
- Number of required interchanges to reach the destination.
- Total distance travelled by walking or using a mobility aid as well as the absolute value of the total elevation gain and descent.

All trip data for each hexagon is consolidated and a 64-dimension vector is generated using a neural network performing unsupervised feature learning. This vector describes the public transit accessibility data for each hexagon. The distance between any set of vectors is measured using Euclidean distance, providing a similarity score (from 0 - 1) with vectors closer to each other having a higher score compared to those further away. Using this approach, vectors for each hexagon subregion can be compared to other hexagons within the same city and also in other cities. As such, it is possible to quantitatively identify subregions in the city that do not adequately support people with mobility disabilities.

This paper proposes the creation of vector embeddings to quantify and describe the level of public transit accessibility for people with mobility disabilities. This offers a novel approach to study and define spatial injustice in an effort to make cities a more equitable place for all.

Public Transit Accessibility, Mobility Disabilities, Spatial Injustice, Urban Mobility, Vector Embeddings

A Methodological Research in the Context of Spatial Justice and The 15-minute City: A micro case study in Beyoğlu

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The rapid urbanization process has brought forth numerous challenges such as pollution, transportation problems, urban transformation, sustainability, and pandemics. Throughout history, crises encountered in urban areas have prompted different groups including policymakers, urban planners, and citizens to shape urban spaces (Martinez & Short, 2021). As a major instrument of land-use, public service and facility areas, which impact urban form, are scarce and critical resources in cities. The unequal distribution of public uses has led to a polarized urban space, where citizens cannot equally benefit from urban services (Ghouchani et al., 2023; Hataminezhad et al., 2012). The balanced organization of space through the proper distribution of urban services contributes to the sustainability of the city (Dadashpoor & Rostami, 2011). Land use planning that considers proximity to essential services in residential areas contributes to social and spatial interactions and improved accessibility (Nyamai & Schramm, 2023). In order to transform urban space into a place that offers equal opportunities to all residents and to measure the level of justice in a city, access to services and the spatial and functional distribution of services must be addressed together.

To ensure a just urban space, it is essential to establish land use that provides equal basic services to all residents and to create a well-developed network of transportation. Based on the concept of spatial justice, strengthening the neighborhood unit in the city is primarily required. In this regard, the 15-minute city concept offers a comprehensive framework (Allam et al., 2022; Caselli et al., n.d.; Cha-

baud et al., 2022; Ingram et al., 2006; Moreno et al., 2021; Tzanni et al., 2022).

The study aims to determine the common ground between spatial justice and the criteria for the 15-minute city and to evaluate the study area in Istanbul (Beyoğlu) based on these criteria. In this context, the hypothesis of the study suggests that an urban area with principles of the 15-minute city can be used as a method to achieve spatial justice. Within the scope of the study, initially, a literature review will be conducted, and spatial justice and the criteria for the 15-minute city will be established on a common basis. Subsequently, in a selected study area in Istanbul (Beyoğlu), fundamental data related to population, transportation, and services in the city will be presented based on these criteria. Using spatial analysis methods, the distribution of public transportation, bicycle lanes, and pedestrian pathways in the city will be examined and the distribution and accessibility of urban public services will be revealed. Finally, through surveys, the access to and accessibility of services by city residents will be evaluated. In this way, the convergence of spatial justice and the criteria of the 15-minute city and how the sample study area aligns with these criteria will be examined in more detail. The results obtained will provide valuable insights for urban planners and policymakers. They can use the data to develop strategies for creating more sustainable, accessible, and just cities.

15-Minute City, Spatial Justice, Accessibility, Public Services

Critical Data Science: From inequalities to shared knowledge

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With developments in computational infrastructures, data science and AI have advanced, and in part replaced, several processes of engineering. Our students with data science knowledge now work in all sectors of society. Education material is dominated by western perspectives and largely developed by able-bodied cis-gendered men, centring singular thinking in how we collect, clean, map, model, interpret and evaluate data, and share or cite evidence. Those who are represented get to shape futures for themselves (educated, urban, young adults), while the rest of the identities and issues are shifted to the margins of society. When colonial forms of education at scale are combined with nationally funded Artificial Intelligence programs of research, it legitimises data extraction and unequal forms of participation in decision, labour, and society, further perpetuating damages to vulnerable communities. To make space for alternate social realities, lived experiences, datasets, methodologies, map-building practices, and frameworks, we will develop a decolonising process for data science education. Our approach will combine non-western geographical knowledge, transdisciplinarity, community participation, and intersectional and reflexive thinking to deliver an open, interactive, and co-created textbook for data science education at engineering universities.

Data Science Education, Decolonising, Intersectionality
Transdisciplinarity, Community Participation

DISTRIBUTIVE

14:50-15:50

BERLAGEZAAL 1

9

The Spatial Justice of Employment Opportunities: developing indicators for spatial justice

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Spatial justice has been explored conceptually and descriptively in the domains of geography and urban theory, by authors such as David Harvey (1973), Edward Soja (2010) and Susan Fainstein (2010). However, specific urban indicators to quantify aspects of spatial justice based on particular ethical theories for comparative purposes are lacking. In this paper we develop three indicators for spatial justice derived from ethical principles of Egalitarianism, Utilitarianism and Rawls' Egalitarianism. We utilise these indicators to evaluate neighbourhood reach opportunities to places of employment through cumulative accessibility metrics. These metrics are based on the application of the Dijkstra algorithm to integrated urban network models of transportation, land-use, and street configuration, created from open access data. We find that smaller commuting times reveal local centres, highlighting the role of local mixed land-use. Whereas increased access to global centres and mass transportation plays more of a role for longer commuting times. The results highlight how spatial justice to places of employment is both scale and value reliant, depending on the applied commuting time and ethical principle. The methodological innovation presented here is based on principles of reproducibility and allows for the opportunity to bring moral clarity to strategic planning decisions across urban contexts that could serve as a useful baseline to develop policy.

Spatial Justice, Urban Theory, Network Science, Cities,
Employment Accessibility

Assessing spatial justice in urban mobility through risks and misfortunes.

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When relating mobility to justice, research often points to equitable distribution of resources – material, spatial, environmental and financial. The geographical differences between various localities, however, create and sustain spatial inequalities. Assessing justice, therefore, goes beyond merely considering fair distribution of resources. It becomes crucial to focus on risks and misfortunes that individuals are exposed to and how these are distributed across the society. With regards to this research, the focus on the risks and misfortunes of daily urban travel that some groups of commuters are exposed to more than others, reveals the underlying injustices related to urban mobility.

Justice in relation to urban mobility places emphasis on prioritization of the mode of mobility mostly used by the least fortunate. Applying this to the context of African cities, walking is a mode of mobility commonly adopted by the poor and low-income groups due to the unaffordability of public transit. Pedestrian safety is, however, a pressing concern as they are exposed to a heightened risk of road crashes. Pedestrians also mainly constitute informal workers and casual labourers commuting to their places of employment. The tragic misfortune of these road crashes is the loss of breadwinners or key contributors to their families, often leading to deeper poverty and inequalities for the affected households.

This research takes the approach of evaluating equity through risks and misfortunes related to urban mobility, specifically active travel. In this understanding, the extent to which certain groups bear more risks in their daily

mobility over others guides the assessment of injustices in urban mobility. This constitutes the starting point to develop approaches that would directly address risks and misfortunes and in so doing, advance a mobility system that leaves no one behind. The study applies a three-dimensional framework that includes the spatial, individual and modal dimensions as exemplified by Nyamai and Schramm (2022) in their study on accessibility and spatial justice. In this research, the spatial dimension investigates the origin of the risks and where they mostly occur within space. The individual and modal dimensions are interlinked since active travel represents a form of personal mobility that relies solely on the individual's ability, without involving machines such as vehicles.

To contextualize these dimensions, the research carries out a progressive analysis of each dimension in Nairobi. It begins with a spatial assessment of roads to map the areas where accidents occur. This enables a visualization of the spatial distribution of mobility risks for non-motorised users. For the individual and modal dimensions, the research analyses the travel behaviour of pedestrians along the corridors that register high risks of accidents. This allows for an in-depth assessment of infrastructure design and the areas where spatial inequalities manifest.

The interaction of these dimensions frames the approach and understanding of how risks and misfortunes related to active travel emerge and are sustained. It also guides the assessment of how these risks unfold and how they can be mitigated in order to advance a more spatially just mobility landscape.

Urban Mobility, Spatial Inequality, Pedestrian Safety,
Active Travel, Mobility Risks

Jakarta Green Justice: Evaluating the Provision of Jakarta Green Open Space

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DKI Jakarta Provincial Government has been targeting to increase & expands its Public Green Open Space Provision to 30% of its total area as regulated on DKI Provincial Regulation Year 2012 no. 1 (Peraturan Daerah DKI Jakarta Nomor 1 tahun 2012). The municipal government of DKI Jakarta has reported that the city currently has 5% of Green Open Space on 2022, which even still includes passive Green Spaces not intended to be used for social-cultural-economical activities such as green space in highway corridors.

Numerous studies have shown that the provision of Green Open Space is crucial for the well-being of society. Its presence has been recorded to have positive impacts on urban area as a whole and individuals, among others; improving physical health (Bo-Yi Yang et al., 2021), strengthening social relationships (Viniece Jennings et al., 2019), reducing neighborhoods crime rate (Zander S. Venter et al., 2022), and – as one of the primary pillar of a sustainable urban place – Green Open Space positively correlated with human well-being (Muhammad Jabbar et al., 2021). As a part of Public Space, which defined as a shared resource (Adam Perkins, 2021), spatial justice of public opportunity to use or benefit from accessing Public Green Open Space is an inherent quality that has to be maintained to ensure that the positive impacts are equally shared among the populace.

This paper aims to investigate the existing Public Green Open Spaces through spatial analysis by assessing various attributes such as

actual accessible space, location, dispersion, usage/program, access network on various level, population/density & connectivity to surrounding program within the whole Region and selected District(s). The utilization of spatial analysis will facilitate the determination of the Green Justice Rate which consist of the metrics on the actual active green open space accessibility. In order to do so, this paper intend to identify the existing GIS data regarding [1] Green Open Spaces in Jakarta especially the ones intended to be accessible for public activities (e.g. Public Parks), and [2] Pedestrian connectivity which is represented by road networks equipped with ‘proper’ pedestrian infrastructure and public transit integration.

Learning from the Green Justice Rate, this paper may uncover whether or not a city is just enough based on the provision of public green open spaces and to identify strategies that can guarantee justice of public access, which will ultimately enhance the quality of life and well-being of the people living in urban areas, thus promoting a justice and sustainable community.

Public Green Open Space, Green Space Provision, Spatial Analysis, Spatial Justice, Green Space Accessibility

DISTRIBUTIVE
14:50-15:50
BERLAGEZAAL 2

10

Navigating Justice in Spatial Planning: Insights from a Systematic Literature Review

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The complexities of contemporary spatial planning are exacerbated by rapid urbanization, extreme climate events, and the increasing demands on limited resources, notably land. These multifaceted challenges often engender contested spaces and conflicts over land use, particularly in densely populated regions and their peripheries. In the pursuit of 'just,' 'fair,' and 'efficient' spatial allocations, such conflicts are inevitable. This study delves into the nexus of justice and spatial planning, drawing upon the compelling case of the Netherlands' agricultural transition and the nitrogen crisis.

As societal challenges, including climate change and urbanization, continue to shape land use conflicts, justice considerations play a pivotal role in future spatial planning endeavors. Hence, the intersection of justice concepts and spatial planning research and practice becomes increasingly pertinent.

This study aims to identify and analyze the indicators used to operationalize justice concepts in spatial planning literature and their associations with procedural and distributive justice. The research reveals the diversity of justice interpretations within planning literature and the wide array of operationalization indicators used, highlighting the need for clarity in their application. To achieve this goal, a systematic literature review was conducted to identify relevant studies, assess their methodologies, and extract data on justice indicators and their associated domains. The collected data are then analyzed to draw insights into the operationalization of justice concepts in spatial planning.

Justice concepts in spatial planning provide moral guidelines for decision-making, posing the fundamental question of "what is the right

thing to do?" in the allocation of resources, opportunities, and environmental impacts. However, the normative nature of justice renders its interpretation multifaceted, reflecting diverse schools of thought within planning theory. This explicit consideration of justice ensures that planning processes align with the moral standards of stakeholders and the public interest, a criterion of paramount importance in legitimizing planning actions.

Within planning literature, a plethora of justice interpretations exist, ranging from prioritizing meritorious ideas over majorities to addressing existing inequalities and advancing social justice. Each perspective offers a unique lens through which to view planning's role in achieving justice.

Moreover, justice in planning encompasses a spectrum of ideological concepts, domains, and thematic fields, leading to a diversity of operationalisation indicators. The mixing of these indicators with various conceptualisations can result in misinterpretations, potentially carrying over from theory into practice. While numerous frameworks and indicators exist to operationalise justice, a lack of clarity persists regarding which justice concepts are used in planning theory, hindering their effective application in practice.

By addressing this gap in knowledge, this study seeks to enhance the understanding of justice in spatial planning, fostering more informed and equitable decision-making processes. The research offers valuable insights into the operationalisation of justice concepts, including spatial justice, providing a foundation for improving the alignment of spatial planning with ethical considerations and the public interest.

Spatial Planning, Justice Concepts, Operationalisation
Spatial Justice, Land Use Conflicts

Towards a systematic measurement of mobility injustice: A pilot study in the city of Munich

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The surge in interest in transportation justice topics has contributed to the diversification of theoretical concepts from transport equity and transport justice to mobility justice. However, most of the methodologies developed to analyse mobility injustices at different spatial scales are closely related and limited to distributive principles of justice theories. This paper argues the need for an in-depth engagement with ethical and moral issues when developing methodological approaches to investigating mobility justice. A survey instrument framework that tries to integrate both distributive justice principles with recognition justice has been proposed as a way to shift towards more society-centric research on transport (and mobility) justice. It mixes both utilitarian and non-utilitarian questions in order to (1) account more precisely for the individual characteristics of mobility barriers, (2) identify mobility opportunities that people may aspire to, but that currently cannot achieve, and (3) reasons behind what contributes to perceptions of mobility injustices. The instrument is tested in a large-scale survey (n=1000 valid responses) in two neighbourhoods in Munich. A descriptive analysis will be performed in order to explore reasons for injustice in mobility by comparing different social groups and individual perspectives. The paper ends with suggestions for further improvement to the developed questionnaire and its relevance for transport planning and policy.

Mobility Justice, Ethical Issues, Survey Instrument
Distributive Justice, Recognition Justice

MULTIDIMENSION

14:50-15:50

ROOM U

1

1

Spatial justice, between quantitative criteria and relationship with institutions

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Since the early 2000s, a debate has emerged in France in the academic, political and media spheres that contrasts poor suburbs and areas far from the centre of metropolises, also known as 'peripheral France', which might qualify as 'left-behind places' (Pike, 2023). As part of this debate, some claim that the latter are victims of a lack of public investment because of a focus on the attractiveness and the competitiveness of large metropolitan centres. Others claim poor suburbs of metropolitan areas are the real victims of inequalities. On both sides, the points given often mention public services and equipment spatial distribution.

This debate intensified with the Gilets jaunes (yellow jackets) movement. The working class and the middle class, previously at odds, gathered around the aspiration for a more dignified life and the mobilisation against 'those at the top' (Coutant, in Confavreux, 2019). This brought the peri-urban areas back into the question of inequalities and injustices. It helped to shift the public policy agenda in favor of periurban rings, small towns and rural areas (Lefebvre, 2019). Yet, very recently, in 2023, the poor suburbs called for justice, in a movement that was reminiscent of the 2005 revolts.

In any case, space or territory, has a strong role in feelings of injustice. Indeed, it is partly spatial dimension that distinguishes mobilisation in the poor suburbs from the Gilets jaunes. That is why my PhD work aims to measure the spatial dimension within the feelings of injustice. The goal is to discuss a quantitative

comparison with qualitative research based on residents' perceptions.

To conduct this study, I chose two low-income neighbourhoods, one is a poor suburb of Lyon (the Mas du Taureau, in Vaulx-en-Velin) and the other is the centre of a small town located in the remote periurbs of Lyon (the centre of La Tour-du-Pin, 65 km away).

My survey is divided into two parts. At first, during a quantitative analysis, I treated various data. I made socio-economical portraits of the two neighbourhoods. I also compared the distribution of services according to two criteria, the distribution on the territory and the number of services per inhabitant. I have also considered public policies and investment programs that have been or still are ongoing on both sides. Each neighbourhood suffers inequalities, that are reflected in different ways in terms of space.

Currently, I am studying how these inequalities translate into feelings of injustice. It is the main aim of my PhD, the second year of which is starting now. After extensive reading (including Spire, 2019, 2021), my hypothesis is that the relationships and contacts with the institutions might be more important than the distribution of public services and equipment in nurturing feelings of injustice. To question this, I am beginning a qualitative study based on interviews with inhabitants. I plan to collect their life experiences without orienting to one or another institution, in order to find out if there are certain recurrences in different speeches that affect their lives and their perceptions of justice.

Spatial Injustice, Peri-urban Areas, Inequalities,
Public Services, Feelings of Injustice

A Public Participation Integrated Design Framework for Public Parks in Malaysia: A Quantitative Approach

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The motivation behind this research comes from the three-governance policies in Malaysia, which include democratic governance (DG), sustainable development goals (SDG) and local agenda 21 (LA21), all of which soundly encourage the implementation of public participation in moving towards sustainable development. Besides, public participation also contributes to the social sustainability factor in the development and illustrates the importance of a bottom-up development policy instead of a top-down approach. Therefore, public participation's long-term significant contribution in public parks design demonstrates the necessity and urgency to establish an integrated design framework in the landscape department of the local authority in Malaysia. Public parks are known to provide several important contributions to the quality of life in urban areas, including the maintaining of the general public's mental well-being and it is found to be correlated with the presence of social interaction and engagement with one and another. The main problem statement of the research consists of the need for major transition in Malaysia's democracy as the present design frameworks for public spaces are no longer considered appropriate, social sustainability is neglected in its definition and level of public participation in Malaysia is reported to be low in its implementation and satisfaction level. This research addresses the issues of public participation and public parks development policy in Malaysia. Therefore, this research aims to develop a Public Participation Integrated Design Framework for Public Parks in Malaysia (PPIDF). The objectives of the research are to examine the effect of variables in public participation exercise (PPE), including the development stage, method of approach, type of public and public

parks design criteria on public awareness towards the attribute of public participation in designing public parks in Malaysia, to measure the weightage of variables and indicators in public participation exercise (PPE) on the development stages of public parks in Malaysia, and to develop and validate the proposed public participation integrated design framework for public parks in Malaysia (PPIDF) through expert's opinions. The research hypotheses were constructed and tested to investigate the relationship between variables within the conceptual framework. This research adopted a quantitative analytical method throughout a survey questionnaire, which was distributed among the public at two public parks in Johor Bahru. Consequently, four variables and twenty-two indicators were established through the partial least squares-structural equation modelling (PLS-SEM) assessment. Furthermore, the proposed framework was developed and validated through the analytical hierarchy process (AHP) assessment method. The findings indicated that the established variables and indicators are essential and significant in organising public participation in designing public parks in Malaysia. As a result, the PPIDF significantly contributes to enhancing the DG, SDG and LA21, and towards socially sustainable development (SSD) factors in the public parks design. The outcome of this research contributes to the existing public parks design theory through the implementation of public participation, with particular emphasis on obtaining direct input from the public users towards a 'people-centred' development approach. This research also contributes to the improvement of the current development framework by the landscape department, including the development of an empirical design based on the needs of Malaysian public parks.

Public Participation, Public Parks, Integrated Design Framework, Social Sustainability, Malaysia

Why a socio-spatial approach is required to tackle the energy poverty crisis in The Netherlands: Evidence from Amsterdam Zuidoost

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Driven by climate change and energy crises, an increasing number of households in the European Union are becoming vulnerable to energy poverty. Yet, existing renovation programs often fall short in effectively targeting and addressing the needs of vulnerable groups, particularly in underprivileged neighborhoods where low effectiveness rates and resident resistance to renovation measures persist. This exacerbates the risk of social and spatial inequity, calling for an urgent integration of justice considerations in European renovation policies.

To address this challenge, this study proposes a novel case-study mixed methods (CS-MM) approach to include justice in renovation policies, considering the socio-spatial vulnerability to energy poverty. This method comprises three core phases: a system analysis, socio-spatial analysis, and the formulation of policy strategies. The case of Amsterdam Zuidoost is examined to achieve four main objectives: [1] identify systematic challenges in tackling energy poverty in underprivileged neighborhoods, [2] develop a vulnerability framework encompassing social, economic, energy, institutional and building-related factors, [3] identify and localize energy vulnerable groups, and [4] tailor policy strategies in a multi-stakeholder environment based on the characteristics and needs of the identified vulnerable groups.

Within the context of Amsterdam Zuidoost, we identify the pressing need for a socio-spatial approach to combat energy poverty in the Netherlands. Employing a multidimensional vulnerability framework, nine key dimensions that significantly impact vulnerability to energy

poverty are identified. These dimensions include accessibility, financial capacity, energy efficiency, and social networks. Seven distinct vulnerable groups, disproportionately affected by energy poverty, emerge, with a spatial concentration in the Bijlmer-Centrum area. Based on the characteristics and needs of these groups, we propose tailored policy strategies aimed at alleviating burdens on vulnerable groups, such as single-parent households and the elderly who provide or seek care. Collaboration among housing associations, municipal departments, NGOs, and institutions surfaces as pivotal for effectively addressing energy poverty, underlining the significance of a spatially informed and community-driven approach.

From a scientific perspective, this study enriches existing knowledge by providing valuable insights into the identification of vulnerable groups, the integration of justice into renovation policies, and the deployment of the CS-MM approach to address socio-spatial vulnerability to energy poverty. On a societal level, our findings empower local decision-makers to identify vulnerable groups and tailor policies accordingly.

Spatial Justice, Renovation, Socio-Spatial Vulnerability, Energy Poverty

MULTIDIMENSION

14:50-15:50

ROOM K

12

Urban social reproduction: a new perspective on the requirements of just cities

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Conceptualisations of the just city often focus on the distribution of resources and services. Therefore, urban scholars have widely studied the material and immaterial consequences of urban income inequality, including the inaccessibility of adequate housing, healthy food availability, and stress resulting from life in deprived neighbourhoods. However, urban scholars have thus far not studied dynamics like urban exclusion and marginalisation from the perspective of the organisation of such vital needs by inhabitants. To fill this gap, this paper proposes the use of social reproduction theory in conceptualisations of the just city. Social reproduction entails the practices, responsibilities and relationships that make life possible on a daily and inter-generational basis. Starting from social reproductive needs rather than their material satisfaction provides a novel approach to identify what is lacking in unjust cities and what is required to create just cities. Social reproduction is often satisfied through a combination of paid and unpaid, formal and informal activities that can be provided by inhabitants, civil society, the market, or the state. For example, while income from work and (in)formal economic activities affords rent and food purchases, the preparation of food and cleaning the house often remain unpaid. Therefore, this paper proposes to investigate the practices and power relations that emerge where production and reproduction meet. It thus proposes the idea that urban social reproduction, satisfied through unpaid and paid work, can reveal new understandings of urban lives, spaces and dynamics. Studying cities from a social reproduction perspective opens up new avenues to understand and

encourage just cities beyond income distribution and formal economic participation. Such a framework can enable novel ideas to create just cities beyond traditional means of fighting inequality, which are already under pressure from automation, digitalisation, and labour market precarisation.

During this contribution, I will briefly spell out the advantages of a social-reproduction-first conceptualisation of spatial justice. After, I invite reflections and responses from the audience to discuss what such an approach might impact empirical, methodological, and theoretical challenges.

Just City, Social Reproduction Theory, Urban Exclusion
Marginalisation, Social Reproductive Needs

Interrogating Spatial Justice: a comparative analysis of slum- redevelopment models in India

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The question of what spatial justice is has long been discussed in urban studies and sociology. Recently, political philosophers have started contributing to this literature as well, with a specific focus on gentrification and displacement but also with broader applications of the notion of spatial justice (Huber & Wolkenstein, 2018; Putnam, 2021; Zimmer, 2022; Kohn, 2013). Unfortunately, interdisciplinary work between political philosophers and urban scholars is scarce, which impedes the blending of ideas and concepts, especially in policy-evaluation.

In this paper we attempt to bridge the more theoretically laden concerns on spatial justice with an empirical comparative study on slum redevelopment in India. In doing so, we seek to offer normatively grounded methodological tools for comparative policy-analysis in space redevelopment. We contend that “fairing better” should be conceived in terms of how well each model achieves the dictates of the notion of spatial justice.

The structure of the paper is as follows.

First, we will introduce a broadly egalitarian notion of spatial justice, highlighting some core aspects of it that will then be relevant in the policy analysis. Briefly, we contend that spatial justice should be conceived of as a relational concept that is sensitive to (a) a notion of collective authorship over space, (b) a spatially-embedded notion of inequalities in resources, opportunities and relations (e.g., marginalization and segregation), (c) a critique of the economic mechanisms behind space development and how they impinge on both (a) and (b).

Second, we will present the study of slum-re-

development strategies in India, drawing on two on-going slum redevelopment projects: Kathpathli Colony in New Delhi, and Dhobi Ghat Slum in Mumbai, highlighting the core differences between them. In particular we will contend that these two cases are of particular relevance for comparative analysis because they represent two normatively laden paradigms of space redevelopment in the neoliberal era.

Finally we will analyze the two projects based on the egalitarian notion of spatial justice. In doing so, we aim to answer the question : which model of urban spatial redevelopment fares better? To do so, we show that the notion of spatial justice when applied to comparative evaluations of redevelopment projects, helps us identify the normatively relevant dimensions that should be considered in such analysis. In particular, we identify three main criteria to compare the redevelopment models: authorship in space redevelopment, recognition of claim rights to space, and right to better and stable housing. Ultimately, we hope to present a convincing normatively grounded model for comparative evaluation of spatial justice within urban space-redevelopment projects.

Spatial Justice, Gentrification, Slum Redevelopment
Policy Analysis, Comparative Evaluation

Assessing the “right to the city” through experiential information: towards a holistic approach to spatial justice indicators

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The concept of “spatial justice” is much debated and has many definitions in the literature. However, it is not easy to understand which spatial elements relate to, or convey, certain social problems such as that of injustice. In many cases, spatial justice issues are discussed in terms of the necessity to diminish or conciliate certain differences among statuses and lifestyles of urban users. The impression is that increasing attention is focused on rather dichotomic interpretations of local problems (e.g. cars vs people, drivers vs cyclists, grey areas vs green areas, natives vs foreigners, rich vs poor, visitors vs residents, youth vs elders). Unsurprisingly, hasty conclusions tend to lead to abrupt solutions, not necessarily helpful or effective to actualize meaningful agendas. Against this backdrop, this paper proposes a new methodology to assess “spatial justice” through a more holistic approach. The overall idea is that a component of the “right to the city” is also the availability and quality of urban experiences for agents. Through a series of performance indicators, the paper illustrates how “spatial justice” and “injustice” can be indirectly detected by taking into consideration the kinds of information that urban agents receive from their daily interactions with space. The same indicators may be used also to guide public interventions in order to ameliorate experiential inputs (conveyed in form of images, sounds, smells, artifacts, and behaviours), and, consequently to achieve a more robust “spatial justice”. The resulting framework highlights the main challenges and opportunities for implementing spatial justice benchmarks across urban contexts (e.g. intra and inter-urban comparisons), while

informing policymakers on what kinds of urban intervention (e.g. planning and urban design) may be necessary.

Spatial Justice, Urban Experiences, Performance Indicators
Right to the City, Urban Intervention

MULTIDIMENSION

16:20-17:20

ROOM K

13

Socio-spatial inequalities in energy efficiency in the private rental sector in cities in England and Wales

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The private rental sector plays a significant role in housing across a diverse range of contexts globally. As a sector upon which some of the most energy vulnerable communities rely, and where housing quality is often poor, private rental properties are a key site in which to address interrelated challenges of energy poverty, inequality, and climate change. Here, energy efficiency is a mechanism for restorative energy justice via which to address historic and entrenched inequalities in the energy system and society more broadly. In the United Kingdom (UK), 4.4 million households live in the private rental sector as of 2021 (~19% of households) and this number is growing every year. Yet detailed understanding of the socio-spatial distribution of inefficiency across the sector has been lacking, due in part to a lack of high-resolution energy consumption data, with notable exceptions. Given the unique spatial dynamics of energy consumption and demand, data at a high resolution is important to make visible energy-related inequalities and to gain a better understanding of why and how energy is used, as well as the implications of policy decisions and new technologies. Using new property-scale Energy Performance Certificates we analyse data for over 3.9 million private rental properties (~78.8% of the total sector) in England and Wales, the most comprehensive dataset of its kind. Aggregating this data, we develop neighbourhood scale indicators of energy inefficiency in the private rental sector, evidencing the detailed micro-geographies of energy inequality. Unsupervised k-means clustering is applied to generate a small-area classification (~125 households) of

energy efficiency in the private rental sector, integrating variables about the concentration of properties, efficiency characteristics, property type and age. Demographic datasets are used to explore wider socio-spatial inequalities.

Our clusters [mapped here] show how, in the private rental sector, energy inefficiency is highly spatially concentrated and fragmented. A diverse range of energy and housing conditions shaping the everyday lives of tenants. In some cities, large swathes are characterised by dense, inefficient private rental properties. Notably, inequalities in energy efficiency in the private rental sector do not map neatly onto geographies of wider forms of deprivation and inequality.

The challenges for policy and practice are diverse, from areas characterised by young working populations without access to the affordable but carbon intensive gas grid, to neighbourhoods where large numbers of private renters live in old properties that require deep retrofit. In the context of austerity and limited public resources, we highlight neighbourhoods that might be a useful focus for more targeted policies, including selective landlord licensing schemes or as evidence of concentrated spatial energy injustices. However, whilst place-based approaches to retrofit can be useful, we also emphasise the need for a universal approach to tackle deep rooted and systematic energy inefficiency and inequalities across the private rental sector.

Energy efficiency, Private renting, Housing, Inequality, Energy justice, Spatial data science, Energy Performance Certificate

Using Mexico's National Housing Survey to Assess Social Housing Policy from a Spatial Justice Perspective

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For more than three decades, Mexico has made a concerted effort to combat housing deprivation and improve access to essential urban services such as electricity, potable water, and adequate sanitation and drainage. The country's urban development policy agenda during this time has emphasized the construction of large subdivisions (*fraccionamientos*) of small, "social interest" housing units on tiny lots, frequently on the outskirts of urban areas. This strategy has contributed to a significant decrease in the population living in "marginalized" areas, both in relative and absolute terms (Gobierno de México, 2016). However, in pursuit of the efficient and profitable provision of social housing, government policy has prioritized the mass production of standardized single-family dwellings at the expense of creating sustainable communities (Biles, forthcoming). Several researchers have identified the shortcomings of this strategy, including urban sprawl, spatial mismatch between housing and centers of employment, lack of social cohesion, and large numbers of vacant and abandoned properties (Reyes, 2020; Monkonen, 2019; Valenzuela Aguilera, 2017).

To date, scholars and policymakers have fixated on access to adequate shelter and failed to consider the social and spatial justice implications of Mexico's social housing strategy. Conceptualized as the fair and equitable distribution of socially valued resources, basic services, and opportunities (Rocco, 2014; Soja, 2009), spatial justice fosters inclusivity, accessibility, diversity, participation, conviviality, and resilience, which are essential

for urban sustainability (Rocco, 2022). This paper uses a combination of disaggregated data from Mexico's 2020 National Housing Survey and spatial analysis of the built environment to assess the implications of social housing policy with respect to several indicators of spatial justice in an urban context, including access to essential public services such as health care, primary education, fresh and healthy foods, parks and recreational facilities, employment opportunities, and public transportation. Analysis of these criteria is subsequently used to create an index of "spatially just sustainability" at the *fraccionamiento* scale, which serves to evaluate the extent to which social housing policy in Mexico and the resulting built environment fulfill the ideals of spatial justice.

Social Housing Policy, Urban Development, Spatial Justice
Sustainability, Public Services

Towards Equitable Urban Green Open Spaces in Jakarta, Indonesia: A Spatial Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis Approach

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The United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDG 11.7) set forth a global agenda to ensure universal access to safe, inclusive, and accessible green and public spaces by 2030. At the national level, Indonesian guidelines (Law No. 26/2007) emphasize the necessity of allocating a minimum of 30% of urban space to green areas. However, Jakarta's Detailed Spatial Plan 2022-2042 (Governor Regulation 31/2022) envisions only 9% of urban green spaces share. This incongruence highlights significant policy gaps. In response to this challenge, this study addresses the research question: "How to help Jakarta meet its urban green open spaces target by 2042 in the most equitable way?" Equitability here refers to making green spaces more accessible to residents, inclusive to vulnerable groups, and minimising the impact of building and societal displacement. Using WHO guidelines as a benchmark that every citizen should have access to 5-10 Ha parks within 300-meter walking distance, three main analyses were carried out. These included the current accessibility of existing/planned green spaces (null/baseline scenario), equitability of new urban green spaces allocated along riverbanks, following the river renaturalisation plan (scenario 1 & 2), and multi-environmental criteria based on current vegetation, flood risk, heat, and distance to existing parks (scenario 3 & 4). Data was obtained from authoritative sources (such as provincial government, ministries/agencies), or open sources (such as OpenStreetMap, Humanitarian Data Exchange, Global Human Settlement Layer, EU Space Agency/US Geological Survey). The baseline analysis initially conducted was carried out using points along a line to represent park access points and exits every 100 meters.

We then performed a network analysis on parks with a pedestrian coverage of 300 meters. Lastly, we conducted buffer and suitability analyses to develop different scenarios. Our findings reveal that all scenarios were successful in meeting the 30% target for green space proportion and effectively reduced disparities in park distribution. However, Scenario 2, centred on river denaturalization with an all-waterway 80-meter buffer, emerged as the top performer, demonstrating the potential to increase the served population by 6% (from 85% to 91%). Notably, neighbourhoods with a higher proportion of slums, religious minorities, disabled individuals, children, and lower education levels experienced the most significant benefits from Scenario 2, with average distance reductions ranging from 76% to 83%. We then proceed to highlight the relevance of Spatial Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (SMCDA) as an invaluable evaluation tool for assessing multiple dimensions of spatial justice. It goes beyond mere consideration of green space proportion to address access as a crucial dimension of distributive justice, fostering clarity and transparency in planning processes, and facilitating communicative and collaborative urban planning—a step forward in procedural justice. Additionally, it offers a comprehensive examination of recognition justice by conducting comparative socio-economic impact analyses across various scenarios, providing valuable insights into the equitable distribution of urban green open spaces. In conclusion, this research presents a comprehensive framework for achieving equitable urban green open spaces provision in Jakarta and offers actionable insights that can be adapted and applied in similar urban contexts.

Urban Green Open Spaces, Spatial Justice, Spatial Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis, Jakarta

MULTIDIMENSION

16:20-17:20

ROOM U

14

Practicing Citizenship in a Post-Truth World

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Practices of spatial (and social) justice depend on our rights as citizens, and those rights are under threat in an increasingly polarised and authoritarian world. Authoritarianism may be easy to spot in a non-Western, non-democratic context but it exists, too, in the West in the form of Surveillance Capitalism, where wealthy, powerful corporations operating with little regulatory oversight are making decisions that affect our lives, work, and well-being.

This paper will discuss contemporary conceptualisations of spatial justice, beginning with an exploration of the damage being done to procedural justice when our rights are eroded by 'black-box' algorithms which replace human relationships so that certainty can replace trust. The paper will specifically address points 4 and 6: 'evaluation of policy interventions and their impact on spatial justice' and 'challenges and opportunities in implementing spatial justice benchmarks' in order to relate them to distributive justice to show how fair and equitable distribution of the burdens and benefits of human association are being tilted in favour of social media companies through the unprecedented asymmetries in knowledge and power that accrues through their knowledge of us. As Shoshana Zuboff says in *The Age of Surveillance Capitalism: The Fight for a Human Future at the New Frontier of Power* (2019), 'surveillance capitalists know everything about us, whereas their operations are designed to be unknowable to us. They accumulate vast domains of new knowledge from us, but not for us' (italics in original). By examining social media's business model we can see how it sacrifices truth to profit, leading to the 'post-truth' world we now

inhabit, where 'alternative facts' or 'lived experience' make truth in public discourse seem, not just relative, but up for grabs; where strength of conviction seems to count more than any objective assessment of reality.

Using Michel Foucault's theories of power relations to explain the mechanisms of surveillance capitalism, I show how we, as consumers, eagerly insert ourselves into the apparatuses of social media and, as a result, render up our information for others' use and profit. This latest incarnation of Foucault's concept of 'bio-power' revives Karl Marx's nineteenth-century image of capitalism as a vampire feeding on labour, only in the twenty-first century, 'instead of labour, it is feeding on every aspect of every human's experience' (Zuboff 2019).

The paper ends, however, with a note of hope because it argues that we will always be able to have agency as citizens, provided we use that agency and not allow ourselves fritter it away simply because we want to be entertained. We need to practice our citizenship; it is an active thing. The theoretical explorations in this paper will help inform us about the spatial and social practices of justice. By helping us understand what is going on, and the dangers we currently face (as well as highlighting the effects these dangers are already having on our lives) we will be better able to prepare ourselves to deal with them in the future.

Spatial Justice, Surveillance Capitalism
Procedural Justice, Social Media, Agency

The Regional deal of Zaan IJ to strengthen the broad welfare of four marginalised districts

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The Regional deal of Zaan IJ, 2019, aimed to strengthen the broad welfare of four marginalized districts around the Noorder IJplas, in the Amsterdam Metropolitan Region (AMR). These neighborhoods have large migrant populations of non-western backgrounds and are socially and economically vulnerable. The AMR's strong economic growth has not resulted in equitable resource sharing in these districts. Spatially, there is a lack of access to opportunities (both economic and recreational) that add value. The transitions towards sustainability like climate, mobility justice and access will only result in worsened inequalities if not addressed holistically. The project titled "Zaan IJ - Long-term Design Assignment", explores spatial and climate justice Zaan IJ. The brief is to develop pathways for increasing broad welfare to achieve socio-spatial justice. With an approach prioritizing participation and co-creation, workshops were conducted with government organizations, knowledge institutes and local stakeholders. Inhabitants' interviews, town hall meetings, and engagement activities like drawing competitions highlighted resident's needs and short-term goals. These sessions resulted in a long list of 90 long-term and short-term measures. With the help of broad welfare indicators (CBS), impact scores, and neighborhood needs, they were short-listed to 25 measures. The research produced some key observations. Firstly, long-term assignments should be combined with short-term outcomes. There was a conflict in setting up timelines for spatial goals. The top-down processes of creating frameworks to increase well-being are long-term, in the range of 10-30 years. However, the co-creation process showed that the residents lacked trust in the long-term assignments. They

take more ownership and agency, respond positively, and prioritize measurable, visible short-term outcomes. A way to ensure this is by investing in measures that can be linked to current projects. This results in higher engagement with socially vulnerable residents, who due to immediate social concerns, are less likely to see long-term challenges.

Secondly, several indicators were used to short-list measures. One such list was developed by the province of North Holland to benchmark well-being. It included indicators like access to swimming pools as a crucial parameter. However, with the region largely populated with Moroccan and Middle Eastern inhabitants, these lists proved to be insensitive to the cultural differences of the inhabitants, especially the women. It highlights a euro-centric view of governance which should be adapted for benchmarking spatial justice measures better. By giving agency and understanding the needs of the local demographics, context-sensitive indicators should be created.

Third, a physical measure should always be combined with a social measure.

Ex: Physical measure: Green schoolyards, parks and playgrounds with infiltration possibilities. Increase opportunities for sports and create sponge areas for rainwater management. Social Measure: Stimulating bottom-up initiatives + education packages on construction, management, and maintenance, linking to educational programs for young people and teaching programs + linking to nature on prescription and the health sector and the elderly as volunteers.

It became apparent that to build and maintain momentum towards creating long-term strategies for spatial justice, continuous engagement of all inhabitants is crucial.

Spatial Justice, Participation, Co-creation
Well-being Indicators, Cultural Sensitivity

Resisting creatively, designing collectively. From shelters to infrastructures for civic imagination

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When large numbers of displaced people from Syria, Afghanistan, Eritrea and beyond, came to Europe during and after ‘the long summer of migration’ (Kasperek and Speer, 2015), a wave of architectural contributions emerged that focused largely on the technological improvement of temporary structures based on minimum dwelling standards. This article starts from the hypothesis that housing design for the displaced today is stuck in a shelter paradigm with roots in modernism, humanitarianism, and colonialism, that disregards migrants’ home-making, while being materialised in multiple architectural typologies, ranging from tents, containers and collective centres to flats in the city (Scott-Smith and Breeze 2020; Dalal, 2023). The ‘permanent state of temporariness’ (Hilal and Petti, 2019) that displaced people experience in shelters contributes to a material politics of shelters as ‘internal border spaces’ (Fontanari, 2015; Thorshaug, 2019) and the legitimisation of ‘bare life’ (Agamben, 1995). Displaced and illegalised newcomers find themselves stuck in ‘forced shelters’ (Molnar, 2020) while their right to a home depends on their citizenship status.

This article investigates collective and bottom-up design processes for the homing of displaced and illegalised newcomers in the city, through which alternative forms of citizenship and co-habitation can be imagined, that resist the shelter paradigm. The article will more specifically build further on Lemanski’s concept of ‘infrastructural citizenship’ (2020) to rethink citizenship beyond the political concept of the nation-state, and Hoskyns and Petrescu’s feminist spatial practice of ‘taking place’

(2007), to ‘pay attention to mutual differences and “otherness”, not necessarily with the aim of being “included” or “represented” as in the definition of inclusion, but to take part in society directly from a differential position’. These infrastructures for civic imagination encapsulate the significance of everyday mundane acts of home-making and integrate attention to the scales of home and city, for instance through accessing essential urban amenities and services, but also through connecting to safe and hospitable spaces in the city.

The research is based on a multi-year participatory action research in an organisation for artists and art lovers with a background as newcomers in Brussels and will present a critical analysis of the collective process for the purchase and renovations of their building towards their dream of the House for Collective Imagination and the role of the architect therein. The author understands these processes as acts of ‘creative resistance’ (hooks, 1995) against the shelter paradigm. Or as Quizar (2022) puts it when referring to Black grassroots claims to home in Detroit, ‘to refuse creatively. That is, even as they refuse, they do not merely assert an opposite. Rather, they build alternative logics, alternative categories, alternative organisation of space’ (p.17).

Ultimately, the in-depth analysis will serve as the basis to develop tools for architects to transcend the shelter paradigm by putting homing and civic imagination central within co-creative design processes.

Displaced People, Shelter Paradigm, Citizenship
Infrastructural Citizenship, Civic Imagination

MULTIDIMENSION

16:20-17:20

BERLAGEZAAL 2

15

Social impact assessment of urban regeneration operations for a methodological and operational approach aimed at planning and implementing interventions

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Milan is the economic capital of Italy and is characterised by significant development and dynamism, especially in the past two decades. The city hosted Expo 2015 and will host the upcoming Winter Olympics Games in 2026. In the meantime, the Town Administration is promoting a wide program of urban regeneration, mostly led by the private sector, that involved the whole city (from the periphery to the city centre). Also due to this constellation of projects that involves real estate and investors, lately Milan is facing a significant crisis that is impacting the life of its inhabitants: exponential increase in housing prices, privatisation of spaces, and growing influence of private actors in decisions that should be purely public. These developments have resulted in the ongoing exclusion of the poorest populations, the gradual distancing of the so-called “working poors”, and a growing inequality. In this context, the research I am conducting aims to investigate the impact of urban regeneration projects on communities, particularly those vulnerable and marginalised groups already experiencing spatial injustice. The broadness of the topic requires a strong defined framework. To start, it is crucial to clarify the meanings of “social impact” and “urban regeneration”, which are widely used terms, and to deepen the concept of “spatial justice” that will be the framework of the research project. The literature review will provide a clear and unambiguous definition within the thesis. Additionally, the research explores how the concept of social impact assessment in urban regeneration projects is addressed in existing literature and which is the link between urban regeneration projects, spatial justice

and community participation. This exploration includes scientific literature, reports, case-studies and articles from agencies to establish a solid theoretical foundation.

The theoretical framework contributes to read the city through the lens of spatial justice. The analysis aims to deepen

- How the decision-making process in the field of urban regeneration is led, with a specific focus in understanding if and how the promoters (public or private) set up the monitoring and the spatial and social evaluation plan;
- Examine the role of the community in the context of these transformations, starting with an understanding of which communities are involved;
- Analyse the presence of social hubs as factors that can facilitate the participation and involvement of specific targets.

In this context, a significant aspect of this work will be focused on constructing collectively and participatively a set of indicators, capable of assessing spatial justice within the realm of urban regeneration projects. Once a set of indicators has been previously constructed based on case studies and existing literature, the aim is to engage communities, mapping and identifying those who are typically excluded from the participation process. The main objective of the research is to develop social impact indicators in a shared and participatory manner, creating an effective tool to measure the impact of these transformations.

Urban Regeneration, Spatial Justice, Social Impact Assessment, Community Participation, Housing Prices

What is the relative effectiveness of different pedagogies for teaching conceptual and methodological approaches to spatial justice benchmarking?

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As mitigations and adaptation to a changing climate continue and increase, there are pressing requirements for delivery of radical responses in the built environment to these natural environmental impacts. The authors anticipate these emerging changes will be better dealt with through the filter of an agreed and measurable framework of spatial justice (SpJ). Initiatives that have clear and mutually accepted targets to support social justice spatially require impartial knowledge – lessons that can be learned and shared.

Earlier research into a values-led framework for assessing regeneration outcomes (BissettScott, 2018) benchmarked SpJ in terms of needs; current practice requires sharper and faster assessments of moral and philosophical understandings that can be included in professional planning education. The line-up of technological, bio-diversity and climate change require excellence, efficiency and effectiveness for relevant and focused teaching practice.

Our research frame will be developed as an outcome of Symposium debates. As the Spatial Justice Network aims to share research and educational practices that integrate spatial justice concepts, we propose exploring how to best impart and increase knowledge of benchmarking Spatial Justice good practice into urban design and planning courses. The aim is to improve a pedagogy that builds a circle of excellence into postgraduate teaching of the topic, particularly to new planners. The exploration will be into the comparative success of imparting and embedding knowledge about the complex concept of spatial justice.

Collaboration and reflective learning, an integrative approach and an inquiry-based approach will be examined at a point in time and compared.

A cohort of Masters students in their second trimester will provide a base survey on benchmarking spatial justice indicators. Some students work in local authorities or private planning practice, others are full-time and some are international students. All participants will have had lectures and readings on methodologies for implementing spatial justice and may have considered the challenges of a measurable framework for spatial justice.

Year Groups are given different projects; each with different approaches (collaborative, reflective, integrative, inquiry-based). An end of term interview of each group will compare their understandings about Spatial Justice from that initial response. It is anticipated that these interview results might identify differences and strengths in learning outcomes. The results would be shared with other universities to

(a) enhance the practical linkages between practice-based learning and conceptual understandings of spatial justice

(b) find optimal methods of assisting students to absorb and apply concepts of spatial justice during their post-graduate degree courses; and

(c) identify ways to share best practice with other Universities on spatial justice pedagogy that may emerge from this research.

Results from research would be edited and presented as an online seminar and interactive workshop, open to members of the Spatial Justice Network convened by TU-Delft. Student presentations would be encouraged together with experienced practitioners and academics. The likely date of the seminar would be May 2024, and a summary of the research would be edited for broader dissemination – perhaps as an article in the next Manifesto for a Just City 2024.

Spatial Justice, Urban Design, Planning Education
Pedagogy, Benchmarking

Gentrification around Metro Stations in Bengaluru: A Report and Toolkit

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6 Mega-urbanisation', marked by a growing need for urban land and infrastructure, is a common trend in numerous Indian cities. A prime example is Bengaluru, where the IT industry and software services have driven the city's swift urban expansion over the past thirty years (M, 2018). In situations where rapid urban growth is primarily propelled by capitalist motives, it becomes crucial for government authorities, urban planners, and residents to comprehend the fair distribution of public infrastructure. In this context, the focus on urban mobility takes centre stage as a factor that can instigate gentrification and should be thoroughly examined (Padeiro, Louro, and Costa, 2019). This research paper which was done as my Thesis Project as an Undergraduate Student at Srishti Institute of Art, Design and Technology, primarily focuses on understanding gentrification dynamics triggered by Mass Rapid Transit Systems, specifically Metro Stations ('Namma Metro') in Bengaluru, India, and their role in perpetuating disparities in urban access. Since, most gentrification toolkits are designed for the Global North, leaving a gap in gentrification studies in the Global South, this study introduces a unique methodological approach to explore gentrification, particularly in the context of urban mobility and its relation to informal and formal street vending, complexities associated with informal economies and unlawful gratifications between private parties and governmental bodies. The study unfolds in three key dimensions:

- Gentrification Assessment: Employing diverse datasets, including census data (tracking changes in mean household income levels and literacy rates within demographics), alongside spatial data (shifts recorded in land use maps and mapping changes in vertical development), the study assess-

es whether gentrification is occurring within the selected study area.

- Socio-Economic Stratification: In the absence of micro-level income data to stratify the sub-neighbourhoods in my site of study, the study employs alternative methods. Street Auditing to examine details such as the state of urban infrastructure, serves as a proxy to gauge the socio-economic status of each neighbourhood. Additionally, the study explores alternative methodologies by mapping each neighbourhood's access to infrastructure, recognising that affluent neighbourhoods typically exhibit greater access to such amenities.

- Stakeholder Perspectives: Finally, insights were gathered from a diverse range of stakeholders directly impacted by gentrification, as well as those wielding authoritative and monetary power within the context. Semi-structured interviews with these stakeholders, identified through comprehensive mapping efforts, provide an understanding of the gentrification process and its multifaceted implications. This paper introduces a novel approach to quantifying gentrification induced by transportation infrastructure and the degree of impact on marginalised communities' access to urban amenities. It culminates a holistic framework for NGOs, researchers, and policymakers to identify affected demographics, propose compensatory measures, and implement policy interventions, thus mitigating adverse effects. In conclusion, this study introduces methodologies tailored to the unique context of the Global South enhances our understanding of gentrification dynamics and empowers stakeholders with actionable information to foster inclusive urban development. It underscores the critical role of large-scale urban projects, like MRT development, in shaping urban equity and calls for informed interventions to ensure equitable urban futures.

Gentrification, Urban Mobility, Mass Rapid Transit Systems
Urban Access, Global South

MULTIDIMENSION

16:20-17:20

BELAGEZAAL 1

16

Climate adaptation imaginaries in translation: international collaboration in Chennai

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Cities around the world are seeking to balance economic growth agendas with protecting citizens from the impacts of climate change. This challenge has spurred an international exchange of planning approaches to climate adaptation via global city networks. However, many of these approaches face serious pitfalls in terms of distributive and procedural spatial justice. Guided by literature of policy translation, this article follows the journey of climate adaptation ideas to Chennai in order to examine how global imaginaries are made local and mobilised through design-based planning approaches. In this process, we are particularly interested in uncovering the political role of design imaginaries in addressing climate vulnerabilities under the context of neoliberal urbanization. Such critical examinations are necessary given the growing global portfolio of design-based techniques for adaptation planning and the increasing incidences of social and environmental injustice linked to associated interventions. Drawing from a qualitative methods design, we investigate the Dutch Water as Leverage (WaL) funding programme to trace the substantial efforts that are made in the context of Dutch development cooperation to generate the need for climate adaptation in Chennai. By triangulating the methods of document analysis, participant observation and key-informant interviews, we find that the actors and processes related to the WaL initiative have facilitated a renewed imagination for the city of Chennai. Under the pretext of urgency to address climatic challenges, two design teams were commissioned to synthesise the complex socio-ecological problems of Chennai into more manageable and bankable solutions (e.g. nature-based solutions) with the support of stakeholder workshops. Landscape ar-

chitecture designs were used together with cartographic exercises and proposals for new public infrastructure to recast the imagination of stakeholders. To bring actors on board, new strategic alliances were built where global and local actors were designated with new roles. The Dutch Ambassador for Water was central to organising seemingly apolitical associations around the new climate adaptation imaginaries that emerged from the design process. With design reports in hand, global ideas of climate adaptation were mobilised to provide an authoritative orientation for Dutch actors to access channels of global climate adaptation finance and obtain local government buy-in in Chennai. Throughout the process of policy translation, this design-based method of climate adaptation planning framed and instrumentalised experiences of climate vulnerability in a way that undermined the need for deeper reforms to address socio-spatial disparities in Chennai. For example, under the pretext of inclusion, designers were challenged to consider past experiences of caste segregation and inequality in the city's previous resilience and adaptation strategies. However, these perspectives only made it into the final design propositions insofar as they did not question the exclusionary processes that condition urban governance and capital accumulation in the city's metropolitan area. The climate adaptation imaginaries promoted by The Netherlands' development cooperation problematically aligns adaptation with Dutch development interests. Rather than addressing the drivers of socio-spatial vulnerability, the tendency is that WaL's way of working results in the speculation and re-appropriation of urban territories since this is the way in which underlying economic development goals are achieved.

Spatial Justice, Renovation, Socio-Spatial Vulnerability,
Energy Poverty

Towards a Sustainable and Equitable Future: Queer Mobilities, Climate Change, and Spatial Justice.

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The intricate interplay between transportation, climate change, and spatial justice carries profound implications for marginalised communities, particularly gender and sexual minorities. Disparities in transportation accessibility, compounded by the evolving impact of climate change on infrastructure, necessitate a multifaceted examination of these interwoven issues. Transportation serves as a critical lens through which to analyse and redress multifaceted inequalities, leading to a stark reality: inequitable access to mobility reverberates across our geographical landscapes and significantly impacts various facets of daily life. In this context, the significance of queer intersectionality becomes evident, acknowledging the compounding forms of oppression experienced by individuals across intersecting identities.

Queer individuals, navigating a complex interplay of intersecting identities encompassing race, gender, sexuality, and socioeconomic status, provide unique insights into the multifaceted challenges central to spatial justice. To comprehend these nuanced experiences, a research project examining the Impacts of Gendered Inequalities in Latin America was undertaken. Employing a qualitative approach grounded in queer and postcolonial theory, this study delved into the multifaceted dimensions of spatial inequality in mobility systems. Interviews conducted among transgender individuals in Colombia and Mexico illuminated a narrative steeped in adversity. Queer individuals regularly face differentiated challenges within transportation systems, severely limiting their ability to navigate urban spaces with freedom and security. This unjust reality not only hinders their access to essential resources such as employment, healthcare, and education but also mirrors the distributive aspect of spatial justice. Further analysis uncovers additional systemic barriers deeply ingrained in mobility poli-

cies, stemming from factors like social class and ethnicity, which disproportionately impact queer communities. Additionally, the fear of violence often leads to altered behaviours that result in the avoidance of public transportation and a preference for alternative, potentially less sustainable modes of transport. This not only heightens their vulnerability but also contributes to environmental impacts. Moreover, the repercussions extend beyond the individual. Transportation policies and planning processes often neglect the needs and experiences of queer communities, reflecting systemic failure. This failure to incorporate gender-sensitive approaches and foster inclusive public spaces perpetuates the marginalisation of queer individuals, aligning with the procedural and recognition dimensions of spatial injustice. However, this narrative also presents an opportunity for transformation. Recognition of these challenges has sparked the spatial justice movement, advocating for more inclusive and equitable mobility systems. These policies champion practices prioritising safety, accessibility, and the voices of queer communities in transportation planning and decision-making. This transformative approach aligns with the core principles of spatial justice, offering hope for a more just and equitable urban future. In summary, the intricate interplay between transportation, climate change, and spatial justice forms the backdrop for an exploration of the differentiated experiences of queer communities. The urgent need for an intersectional approach, as highlighted by the research project, underscores the complex web of inequalities faced by queer individuals. Their experiences not only underscore the significance of spatial justice but also serve as a call to action for a more inclusive and equitable future – a future where transportation acts as a platform for justice for all communities.

Spatial Justice, Participation, Co-creation
Well-being Indicators, Cultural Sensitivity

The space of justice. Disentangling the notion of “spatial justice” and rediscussing the “spatial turn”

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1. The concept of “spatial justice” is widely employed in contemporary literature: for instance, in the fields of urban studies, planning theory, and human and political geography. The widespread shift of attention to spatial justice has occurred in parallel with the recent “spatial turn” in many disciplines.

2. The notion of spatial justice is usually deemed decisive for a radical change in urban policies and planning. However, there is no agreed definition of spatial justice. This is so also because the idea, while obtaining an immediate and widespread success, still lacks certain necessary conceptual and analytical explorations and clarifications. Any attempt to formalise or even model the issue of spatial justice needs a preliminary specification of its possible meanings and scope. This paper aims to disentangle the idea of “spatial justice”. Indirectly, it will also reconsider what the spatial turn is and can be.

3. The paper is organised as follows. The first section clarifies what justice is, and social justice in particular. To do so, it makes three preliminary clarifications in regard to: (i) the primary subject of justice; (ii) the distinction between the general concept of justice and specific substantive conceptions of justice; (iii) the circumscribed meaning of the notion of distributive justice as a mere component of the more general notion of social justice. The following section discusses five cases in which space is involved in justice issues: (i) as an influencing factor; (ii) as a unit of allocation; (iii) as a privately owned asset; (iv) as a publicly controlled realm; (v) as a precinct.

Spatial Justice Definition, Spatial Turn, Primary Subject of Justice, Substantive Conceptions of Justice

SYMPOSIUM

DAY 2

ONLINE SESSION

Online

Keynote

Caroline Newton

Associate Professor and Van Eesteren Fellow at the Department of Urbanism at the Faculty of Architecture and the Built Environment at the TU Delft.

I am an urban planner, architect, and political scientist. My work and research are deeply rooted in exploring the social and political dimensions of design. I am particularly intrigued by the intricate interconnection of architecture and planning in post-colonial contexts, and I am passionate about understanding and integrating intersectionality in and for design and planning. Additionally, my research interests include participatory planning and using design approaches for knowledge production. As an advocate for revitalised urban professional engagement, I firmly believe in bringing advocacy back to the forefront of planning and spatial practices. I pursue a critical and participatory approach to strategic planning, thinking about planning techniques as acts of resistance that unlock alternative spatial possibilities and imaginations. Through this lens, I endeavour to create avenues for more inclusive and transformative spaces.

MULTIDIMENSIONAL

16:25-17:25

ONLINE

17

Methodological Approaches for Measuring and Assessing Perception of Urban Safety Among Women, case study of Kazakhstan

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Harassment in urban spaces is a rising issue in contemporary Kazakhstani society, which is polarized among victim-blaming from one side, and urging calls for urban justice, from the other side. In cities of Kazakhstan, women and girls encounter harassment in public places, which includes unwanted visual, verbal, and physical advances, as well as sexually aggressive behavior. The legislation practically does not punish for sexual harassment; currently, punishment falls under Article 123 - "Coercion to sexual intercourse, homosexuality, lesbianism, or other actions of a sexual nature." Thus, urban design is perceived to be unfair to females because it does not provide a sense of safety on the streets. Harassment in cities includes not only open spaces but also public transportation. To address these concerns, robust methodologies are required to assess spatial injustice in terms of women's safety perceptions.

Global experience suggests the use of regular safety audits in cities, which will not only help identify gender-sensitive urban spaces but also raise public awareness of women's safety issues. Safety audits include elements such as lighting, signage (helping people understand their location), visibility, isolation, escape routes, and the maintenance of the area.

Thus, development of safety audit tool methodology is also advised for evaluating women's perceptions of safety within urban spaces of Kazakhstan. The survey among citizens of major cities of Kazakhstan (Almaty and Astana) has shown the indicators, based on which they measure safety in the urban spaces, which include:

1. Adequate lighting levels ensure good visibility in urban spaces. For example, construction sites often raise concerns among women.

2. A sufficient number of surveillance cameras

3. Strategically placed throughout the city. In some cities, increasing the number of cameras has helped reduce crime rates.

3. Development of a mobile application where individuals can report safety issues in specific locations or send a signal for police/security assistance. Additionally, the app could allow a woman to connect with a volunteer for virtual accompaniment while moving around the city alone. Representatives of the Ministry of Internal Affairs in Almaty shared information that there is already a mobile application called "102" with an SOS button. However, none of the interviewed women were aware of it, indicating the need for advertising this application.

4. Urban design that avoids large (<1m) garbage containers, very tall (no more than 1m) and dense vegetation (e.g., trees should not block light from streetlights) and similar architectural elements, as they obstruct visibility for potential victims while allowing potential criminals to pursue them unnoticed.

5. "Help" buttons and police call buttons placed throughout the city.

6. Public transportation stops are perceived as safer by women when they are adequately populated and gender-diverse. This can be achieved by locating bus stops in areas with shops, cafes, and other public places or vice versa.

In conclusion, measuring and assessing spatial justice in the context of women's safety is a multifaceted challenge that demands a combination of research methods. This abstract underscores the significance of adopting a certain holistic approach to develop a safety audit tool in Kazakhstan, thus, raise awareness among citizens, and also address the spatial injustice faced by women in urban environments.

Spatial Justice, Women's Safety, Methodological Approaches, Perception, Urban Environment; Kazakhstan.

Role of Spatial Frameworks in Spurring Climate Justice and Responsible Investment

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A joint proposal between Jacobs, and the Port of San Francisco explores the different scales at which spatial frameworks are instrumental in spurring climate justice and responsible investment. The proposal focuses on three key areas:

- The San Francisco Waterfront Resilience Program (WRP), led by the Port of San Francisco, as a case study on collaborations with the United States Army Corps of Engineers (USACE) and coordinating on spatial frameworks to ensure environmental justice communities are foregrounded in the adaptation planning and investment allocation process.
- How stakeholder engagement and local expertise are central to informing the application of spatial justice frameworks, in order to nuance investment and planning discussions.
- Novel techniques to measure social value in terms of benefits and 'dis-benefits', drawing on methods developed by Simetrica-Jacobs in the United Kingdom, and how this analysis can improve investment decision-making.

San Francisco Waterfront Resilience Program (WRP): The WRP is a multi-year planning effort to protect the San Francisco Bay Area from seismic risks and flooding hazards. It is leveraging federal and local planning frameworks, including the USACE Comprehensive Benefits Planning (CBP) framework, to inform decision-making and identify priority areas for investment. The planning team is using a combination of data-driven storytelling and local planning expertise to elevate the heavily underinvested community of Bayview-Hunters Point (BHP) that may otherwise not be advanced for further investment.

Jacobs: Jacobs is exploring novel techniques that help us understand who is benefiting, as well as who is experiencing dis-benefits, from adaptation and resilience measures. These techniques allow for potential unintended consequences to be understood, such as negative environmental impacts or community disruptions. They also provide a way to robustly measure and monetize outcomes for society, thereby allowing for better-informed investment decisions.

Participants will:

- Learn about the availability of public climate hazard data to assess the risk of damage from extreme weather events.
- Discover specific examples of how spatial frameworks are being used to inform decision-making and investment in adaptation and resilience, considering the importance of stakeholder engagement and local expertise.

Spatial Frameworks, Climate Justice, Responsible investment, Stakeholder Engagement, Social Value

Just Participation or Just Participation? Assessment of Community Participation in Heritage Planning Process in Tanjungpinang, Indonesia

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Community participation has emerged as a prominent global subject in the field of heritage management due to the increasing adoption of an inclusive approach. The inclusion of participatory approaches in heritage management is considered crucial in order to facilitate the engagement of all relevant stakeholders in the decision-making processes, as well as to distribute responsibility for and draw benefits from heritage initiatives. In the Indonesian context, the significance of community involvement in historical preservation has been acknowledged since the early 2000s, in response to the government's emphasis on monumental assets. The conservation method in Indonesia has undergone a transformation towards a more dynamic approach, resulting in an increased involvement of local communities in heritage planning as active participants in the conservation process. Tanjungpinang, a multi-cultural heritage city in Riau Island Province in Indonesia, was chosen as a case study due to the presence of substantial community participation in the planning process. However, limited study has been conducted thus far on the examination of the quality of community engagement in heritage planning in Tanjungpinang, as well as the comprehensive understanding of the roles played by the community in this context. The objective of this study is to assess the degree to which the current heritage planning process in Indonesia, with a specific focus on Tanjungpinang, has facilitated equitable community participation. Additionally, it seeks to investigate alternative strategies for enhancing the fairness of community participation in heritage planning. The study will employ qualitative methodology. The primary research methodology employed in this work is qualita-

tive case study with primary data collection using semi-structured interview and secondary data from desk research. The study also undertakes a comparative analysis between Tanjungpinang and Kotagede, with the aim of addressing the strategies to enhance justice in community participation in heritage planning process. The selection of the post-earthquake restoration project in Kotagede, Yogyakarta, Indonesia, was based on its reputation as a model example of community engagement in the conservation of cultural assets. Using three key indicators in procedural justice - representativeness, information provision, and decision-making power, the study's results suggest that heritage planning processes in Tanjungpinang have promoted community participation to different degrees, depending on the specific planning type, governance framework, and involvement of key stakeholders. The conclusion acknowledges Tanjungpinang's high community participation in utilization planning process of heritage resources but suggests improvements in spatial and revitalization planning process. It emphasizes the need for clear objectives, legally binding guidelines, expanded stakeholder engagement, consensus-based representation, effective communication tools, use of local translators, intergovernmental collaboration, capacity-building, and monitoring teams to enhance justice in community participation. The complex dynamics of heritage cities require careful planning and continuous efforts to ensure equitable and just community involvement.

Community Participation, Heritage Planning, Justice,
Tanjungpinang, Kotagede, Indonesia

Spatial Justice on Indonesia Housing Policy and Program

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Housing, as one of the basic necessities of livelihood, has gained increased importance since the global pandemic. Therefore, the equality of its policies and programs has become crucial. The housing ecosystem will be utilized at different levels to analyze the elements of spatial injustice within the system. This analysis will be complemented through cases from Surakarta City, West Java Province, and national housing program to illustrate the primary actors in promoting social justice in housing.

The concept of spatial justice encompasses the fair and equitable distribution of resources, opportunities, and services across different geographic areas within society. It extends beyond mere legal and procedural fairness, encompassing access to resources and amenities that profoundly influence people's lives and opportunities.

Spatial justice in housing related with:

- Shelter provision and access to particular neighborhood
- In equality on urban pattern growth
- Inter relation of urban dynamic of urban decay and gentrification
- Exposure to neighborhood crime

The housing policy backlog primarily focuses on providing housing units rather than tailoring shelter options to suit the preferences and cultural background of individuals or families within their desired neighborhoods. The three cases above shows there are issues of connecting the different layers and requires adjustment to reach the adequate spatial justice in housing can be promoted through equitable urban planning, affordable housing initiatives, and inclusive community development that ensures fair access to housing opportunities and ame-

nities for all residents, regardless of their socio-economic background or demographic characteristics.

Housing, Spatial justice, Equality, Housing policy, Urban planning

Just affordances: a framework for spatial justice

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Spatial justice is a concept often associated with various spatial aspects such as the rights of presence, environmental quality, and mobility (Soja 2009). These aspects are central to understanding the fairness and equity in spatial arrangements and human inhabitation. In this paper, the author proposes a novel analytical framework for investigating spatial justice, one that focuses on a relatively underexplored dimension of inhabited space: its affordances.

The term “affordances” is derived from the work of ecological psychologist James Gibson (1977) and refers to the promises, implications, and opportunities for action that an environment offers to an organism. It connects the capacity of individuals or groups to act within a given spatial context to the objective conditions of that environment. Earlier interpretations of urban space have referred to it as a “texture” and a “system of affordances” (Burte 2008). Extending this understanding, Dokumaci (2023) argues that urban space can “shrink” for disabled individuals due to its ableist structure. The paper suggests that this “shrinking” of affordances affects various disadvantaged groups along dimensions like gender, caste, and class, making it an empirically researchable aspect of spatial justice.

To facilitate qualitative and possibly quantitative research on spatial justice, the paper outlines a framework comprising five affordances that represent dimensions of urban space, originally developed by Burte (2008). These dimensions correspond to five general categories of habitational practices: pausing, moving, thinking, connecting, and claiming. The corresponding affordances, framed in relation to the actions of inhabitants, are: occupiabili-

ty, penetrability, legibility, sociability, and possessibility. These affordances collectively form the system of affordances that shapes an individual’s and a social group’s spatial practices within a city.

The author intends to apply this framework to analyse recent spatial changes in housing and public spaces in Mumbai, demonstrating that the differential alteration of the urban affordance system along class lines constitutes a fundamental spatial injustice resulting from Mumbai’s ongoing spatial transformation. Additionally, the paper aims to illustrate how the actions of urban inhabitants and the institutional framework of physical urban space can be coordinated to analyze the transformation of the city’s affordance structure. The author hopes that this approach will offer a specific conceptual and empirical method for examining the justice of urban spatial production while acknowledging its potential limitations.

Affordances, Urban space, Inhabited space, Spatial transformation, Empirical research

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Practicing Social Justice Impact in Spatial Design Work: Venting Practices in Neo-Apartheid Cities

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In South Africa, urban development still perpetuates divisions and segregation despite political reforms that have taken place over the decades. The city's divisions are not only evident in its physical built form but are also exacerbated by socio-spatial practices that span from individual interactions to high-level policy-making and resource allocation. These practices are deeply entwined in the infrastructure, shaping local and global perceptions of self and others. Given the current context of climate emergency, social inequality, and rising nationalist sentiments, the significance of socially responsible spatial design cannot be underestimated. Whether through activist or conventional approaches, engaging with one's own intersectional positionality within developmental work is crucial.

Numerous important conversations are taking place in South Africa concerning NGOs, development practices, and social justice work since the political shift in 1994. These discussions address concepts such as intersectional privilege, systemic injustice, structural poverty, and identity dynamics in the post-Apartheid rebuilding efforts. Drawing insights from Jordan Flaherty's critique on the developmental-industrial complex in the USA's post-Katrina disaster, where Vietnamese mothers urged working together for post-war reconciliation, the importance of shared responsibility in complex socio-political conflicts is emphasized. This insight sheds light on the significance of interpersonal dynamics in the 'development sector.'

This paper delves into the dynamics of spatial design practitioners and related disciplines within the built environment, focusing

on their involvement in addressing spatial inequality. It draws from recorded conversations among a small group of South African socio-technical spatial design practitioners during the 2020 Covid19 lockdown. The objective of this contribution is to make tangible the interpersonal dynamics prevalent in socially engaged built environment work at the grass-roots neighborhood scale within the contemporary neo-apartheid city context. Furthermore, it aims to link these concerns with the broader discourse on city-making practices and spatial justice in South Africa's built environment.

Socio-Technical Design, Grass-Roots, Neighbourhood Design,
Positionality, Critical Practice, Benchmarking Social Justice Impact

The Equitable Development Data Explorer

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In April of 2022, the NYC Department of City Planning (DCP) launched a first-of-its-kind tool that visualizes and measures displacement risk factors across all the city's five boroughs. The Equitable Development Data Explorer, [<https://equitableexplorer.planning.nyc.gov>] was developed in a joint effort DCP and NYC Housing Preservation and Development (HPD) to represent NYC's efforts to quantify and analyze neighborhood-based displacement risk, as well as to provide essential data across a variety of factors to be included in the newly mandated Racial Equity Reports (RER) as part of the City's Uniform Land Use Review Procedure (ULURP) process. Critical to conception and success of this project was the on-going partnership with community stakeholders in the Racial Impact Study Coalition (RISC), which championed the efforts to put more meaningful data in the hands of the communities.

This effort came partly in response to Local Law 78 of 2021, which outlined a set of indicators to be included in the Equitable Development Data Explorer, but directed the NYC Departments of City Planning and Housing Preservation and Development to determine the complete list of data points and specify methodologies for how the data points should be incorporated into a displacement risk map. The tool provides a statistically-calculated risk index map that evaluates displacement risks for NYC at the Neighborhood Tabulation Area (NTA) geography level, as well as provides a wide array of open data on Public Use Microdata Areas (PUMAs), which are roughly analogous to Community Districts.

To date, this new public-facing tool has been used by thousands of New Yorkers, and data collected from the app has been integral to

the Racial Equity Reports of at least 74 major rezoning proposals across the city. The Equitable Development Data Explorer has two main interfaces. The Displacement Risk Map, which provides a visual and statistical breakdown of assessed risk for displacement by Neighborhood Tabulation Areas (NTA) which approximate neighborhoods, provides needed statistical analysis and map-based visualizations to empower communities to understand the risks present in their neighborhood to gentrification-driven displacement. The Community Data Portal, organized by Citywide, Borough, and Public Use Microdata Areas (PUMAs) which approximate Community Districts, organizes a wide variety of synthesized demographic, workforce, and health indicators that can be tabulated by total population or race/ethnicity. These two functions provide deeper analytical and visual tools for developers, planners, advocates, and members of the public to understand where they live and what some of the pressures that may exist on their communities.

As part of that effort, much thought went into the project conceptualization to ensure that the ui/ux design process as well as the data engineering decisions implemented would maximize usability and accessibility to the site. As part of this abstract, I propose a deep dive into the data engineering and ui/ux design processes, including the various datasets used to build the risk index and how our engineering team utilized innovative management strategies to implement the user-centered design strategies efficiently. I will demonstrate use cases through an interactive demonstration, showcasing how a user can learn more about their neighborhood, and how to generate data for a Racial Equity Report.

Equitable Development Data Explorer, Displacement risk, Racial Equity Reports, Neighborhood Tabulation Areas (NTA)

The Basti Project of Delhi

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Nations in the global south with dense populations struggle with tackling issues on placemaking within informal settlements. Delhi, the capital city of India has more than half of its population living in Bastis (a colloquial term for informal settlements) with a density peaking at 32,000 people per sq/km making it one of the highest urban concentrations in the world. Therefore addressing the needs of more than 50% of the population of any city is crucial for planning a sustainable future.

Our practice EMARA was engaged in creating a report for 9 Bastis of the city in collaboration with IGSSS (Indo-Global Social Service Society) to highlight their role in the Masterplan 2041 document of Delhi. The fieldwork was done in June and July 2023 when we were also able to document challenges such as dealing with heat waves and flooding. The field work was curated such that people of the Bastis are capable to drive change with direction and assistance from architects and planners who can help them evolve their own local solutions.

The Bastis of Delhi showcased unique challenges that not only involve the citizens but also migrants who come from across the country making these settlements have their own shared history and culture. We conducted multiple site visits for documentation, consultations with the Basti people. We worked closely with the youth volunteers, and Basti Representatives to come up with a LAP (Local Area Plan) which can be considered as the first step in the Regeneration of Basti. The report recognizes the Bastis by making them seen and heard in the Masterplan 2041 Document by acknowledging their history, their needs, and their aspirations, especially the youth and women, who are sometimes not

heard in mainstream community development discussions.

Architects and Urbanists too often struggle to practice in such challenging areas. It may be because of a lack of resources or a lack of planning instruments that help facilitate it. We hope that through working on such projects, we make the community of built environment experts more accountable. The project overall recognises the potential of spatial transformation by addressing infrastructural gaps through collective thinking, a methodology that can be adapted in cities across the world.

Informal settlements, Basti, Local Area Plans, Collective thinking

Gender Perspectives in Vienna's Parks: Understanding Inclusivity and Spatial Justice

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With the implementation of gender mainstreaming measures, Vienna has emerged as a best practice example for the implementation of gender-responsive policies and urban design, earning itself an international reputation as a “city of equality.” (Förster et al. 2021, 3) Based on the objective of sharing the city fairly, the city has set itself the ambitious goal of contributing to a gender-equal society in which opportunities, possibilities and obligations are distributed equitably.

This commitment to gender equality has been unwavering for over two decades, beginning with the implementation of the Gender Mainstreaming Strategy (2000) and Gender Budgeting (2005) (Förster et al. 2021). Here, the promotion of gender equality encompasses a broader and intersectional perspective, that includes the needs and social roles of different user groups, including factors such as life phase, cultural background, and socio-economic situation.

Vienna's recognition that the built environment exerts a significant impact on the quality of life of its residents has led to the strategic use of its roads, paths, squares and parks as a leeway to reinforce spatial justice. Furthermore, urban green spaces (UGSs) such as parks, serve not only as vital venues to foster social equity and a sense of belonging but also play an indispensable role in climate adaptation and mitigation strategies.

This research project explores the intricate dynamics of gender within Vienna's parks, with a specific emphasis on the influence of the political climate, including patriarchal values, on the experiences and sense of belonging of different gender identities. The chosen research methodology consists of a comprehensive literature review and a survey encompassing four key areas:

- Amenities and inclusivity to assess the range within Vienna's parks and their potential to cater to diverse gendered needs;
- Perceptions of belonging to explore the subjective experiences of different population groups in Vienna's parks;
- Patriarchal values to identify their influence on the allocation of space within parks; and,
- Policy implications to identify needed strategies to address gender-based spatial injustice and promote greater equity and inclusivity in Vienna's parks.

This research is expected to reveal disparities in Vienna's UGSs, despite the presence of diverse amenities catering to different gendered needs. Anticipated findings include a notable male predominance, respectively a scarcity of spaces tailored to the subjective feeling of safety of women and feminine-presenting individuals. Statistical data indicates that certain amenities, such as ball game fields, outdoor gyms, and skate parks, tend to be more popular among male individuals. On the other hand, female park visitors tend to prioritize amenities like swings, climbing and balancing equipment, areas for privacy, access to toilets, and well-lit footpaths. However, these preferences may not guarantee equitable park usage, and ultimately, spatial justice.

Moreover, this research recognizes that the challenges posed by climate change are inseparable from the quest for spatial justice. Thus, this research project offers a focused examination of the complex interplay between political climate, patriarchal values, and gender dynamics in urban parks, providing insights into the role of governance and political discourse in shaping equitable and climate-resilient public spaces.

Gender mainstreaming, Gender-responsive policies, Spatial justice, Urban green spaces (UGS), Patriarchal values

Women-friendly bicycle system in Turin: assessing requirements, strategies and potential influence on air quality

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The research focuses on the gender-specific aspects of cycling mobility in Turin, Italy, with a particular emphasis on women's experiences and needs within the cycling infrastructure. While cycling has gained popularity in urban areas, the study recognizes that the implementation of cycling networks has often overlooked the specific requirements of women. To address this gap in knowledge, the research aims to provide insights into creating a more woman-friendly cycling system that encourages women's active participation and promotes environmental sustainability. The study investigates women's perceptions of cycling and the necessary improvements in bike infrastructures to make them more inclusive. It also identifies strategies, such as communication initiatives, to enhance women's access to bike lanes. The research goes further to explore the environmental benefits of reduced air pollution through a gender-inclusive cycling system.

The research employs a comprehensive approach, incorporating various methodologies to gain a better understanding of the diverse needs and preferences of women regarding cycling. This includes collecting 360 questionnaires to assess the requirements for improving cycling conditions in Turin, conducting observations in local bike lanes to evaluate their accessibility and use, and interviewing mobility experts to gain insights into strategies for promoting gender-inclusive mobility. Additionally, the study utilizes vehicle-emission factors to estimate the potential environmental benefits of a gender-friendly cycling system in Turin. The findings highlight that women are motivated to cycle primarily to feel comfortable and contribute to a more environmentally friendly city. They perceive cycling as an ef-

icient mode of transportation rather than just a means to save money. Women's concerns about cycling are more related to their sense of security, with factors like high car speeds being more discouraging than the fear of potential harassment.

The research underscores the importance of developing a woman-friendly cycling system that enhances safety while cycling. This may involve implementing physical separators and mobile apps indicating the most secure bike lanes. Such measures are likely to encourage women to switch from using cars to bicycles, ultimately promoting the transition toward a more bike-friendly city for everyone.

In terms of environmental impact, mobility strategies and infrastructures designed to create women-friendlier bike lanes have shown to significantly reduce emissions from private vehicles, including CO₂, CH₄, and N₂O, by approximately one-third. The high willingness of women to shift from private vehicles to cycling further highlights their essential role in fostering an environmentally sustainable city.

In conclusion, the study emphasizes the importance of aligning mobility strategies with women's needs to create a more inclusive and environmentally sustainable city in Turin. It promotes the principles of inclusivity and sustainability as integral components of the city's identity.

Cycling Mobility, Women's Experiences, Inclusive Bike Infrastructures, Environmental Benefits, Gender-Inclusive Mobility

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Leveraging Community Data for Spatial Justice

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The Community Data Platform (CDP) is an innovative digital tool developed by Yeme Tech that aggregates, analyses, and visualises community-specific data. Through geospatial mapping capabilities, the CDP offers valuable insights into local patterns and needs. This provides a foundation for informed decision making that promotes spatial justice.

At Ryder, we collaborate with Yeme Tech to deepen our understanding of people and place. The CDP provides a framework for Ryder's engagement with communities, identifying who we should engage to ensure our designs address genuine community needs. Technology provides a roadmap to understanding the heart of a place, which is best told through the stories of the people there.

This abstract presents two case studies demonstrating the use of the platform to advance spatial justice in design: Stockton Urban Park and Waterfront, and Culture on the Headrow, Leeds.

Stockton Urban Park and Waterfront

Working with Stockton Borough Council, Ryder have drawn proposals to transform a former shopping centre into a new urban park, ensuring it meets the needs of current and future generations. CDP is helping to inform the programming of the park and town centre.

The CDP highlighted high levels of loneliness in Stockton-on-Tees, with 10.5% of adults in Stockton-on-Tees aged 16 years and over feeling often or always lonely. Data also showed a high proportion of young people but few amenities or activities for young people. As a result, the project will provide new events and social spaces, with an outdoor amphitheatre, natural play spaces, and active areas for sports.

Data driven insights help Ryder identify gaps in the provision of amenities and services in relation to the local demographic. Interventions can seek to address specific issues, promoting greater spatial justice across the community.

Culture on the Headrow

Based on our clients' (Leeds City Council and the Henry Moore Foundation) aspirations to diversify their audience base, the Community Data Platform mapped event and activity provision across the city of Leeds and compared this to the local demographic, which showed opportunities to fill gaps in the provision of activities for specific groups. Data showed a disparity between audiences within, compared to beyond, the 20 minute walking distance of the Headrow, with more diverse communities living outside of the 20 minute area. Engagement findings from our visitor surveys further confirmed the demand for a greater diversity of learning programmes, art exhibitions, events, and outreach to appeal to a wider audience.

These insights have informed our proposals and recommendations for the next phase of engagement, which will ask people from surrounding neighbourhoods, what activities and services would attract them to the Headrow - encouraging greater social integration and creating more equitable access to the city.

Spatial tools are redefining the landscape of design and urban development. At Ryder and Yeme Tech, these tools are used as instruments of engagement, design and spatial justice. Ryder will use Yeme Tech's Social Fulfilment Scoring platform on upcoming projects, a tool which calculates and monitors social performance.

Community Data Platform (CDP), Geospatial mapping, Spatial justice, Case studies, Data-driven insights

Towards a Fair Housing Space Standard: Rethinking Housing and Public Realm in the Densification of Zurich

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The city of Zurich, like many urban centres globally, is confronted with a complex set of challenges stemming from population growth, shifting demographics, and changing housing demands, taking place in the context of climate change and overconsumption of common resources that drives the worldwide ecological crises. To prevent further urban sprawl and encourage more efficient land use in times of high demographic and economic growth, Zurich has committed, in line with the Spatial Planning Act (SPA) to “inward densification” in urban centres and along public transportation infrastructure.

The issue of housing shortage is not an unprecedented phenomenon, and yet transnational research centres such as Eurofound (2020), EuroStat (2021) and OECD (2021) identify a “new housing crisis” further aggravated by the sub-prime mortgage crisis (2008) and the Covid-19 crisis (2020). What distinguishes this housing shortage is the altered landscape of a financialised housing market in the neoliberal era on the supply side, coupled with shifting housing needs and functions on the demand side. These changing dynamics within the housing market have contributed to a continual increase in per capita housing consumption, further exacerbating preexisting housing deficiencies.

This thesis critically questions the notion that the city of Zurich is exclusively grappling with a scarcity crisis, arguing instead that the predominant issue revolves around a question of distribution. The perceived lack arises from a general retreat in housing policy allowing social housing privatisation and a housing supply dictated by for-profit real estate market forces, leading to the creation of increasingly unaffordable or misfit housing for

more and more households. The associated commercialisation of the housing supply has an impact on equal access to the housing market and the socio-demographic structure of the city.

In response, this research project sets out the horizon for urban planning to prioritise equitable social densification by defining a qualitative and reasonable maximum housing space standard to be applied in densification projects both within existing built structures and in new developments. It hypothesises that an ecologically sustainable and socially inclusive way of accommodating a growing population within the municipality of Zurich requires the establishment of a “fair housing space standard” alongside a compensation strategy for space consumption exceeding this standard. This attempt envisions alleviating the housing challenge by nurturing a more resilient, diverse, and equitable urban landscape in Zurich.

Urban densification, Housing shortage, Distribution,
Social housing, Housing market forces

Understanding the 'Just City': Benchmarking Spatial Justice in the Transportation

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The concept of 'Just City' emphasizes the importance of fairness, equity, and social justice in urban planning and development. One of the key components to achieve the just city is through developing equitable transportation or 'Just Transportation'. Just transportation is a concept that emphasizes the importance of creating a transportation system that is equitable, sustainable, and accessible to all members of a community.

In today's rapidly urbanizing world, the need for a just city and just transportation has never been more urgent. As urban populations continue to grow, there is a pressing need to create urban spaces that are equitable, sustainable, and inclusive. India has an exponential population growth rate of 3%. Those living in unplanned, low-income settlements have "limited access" to affordable public transport, resulting in 1.5 times to 3.5 times increase in their monthly cost of transport. Less than 7% of public buses in the country were fully accessible to wheelchair users as 2020 which indicates the lack of universal accessible infrastructure in India and 'injustice' within transportation. For understanding the linkages of the spatial justice with the transportation, case study was conducted for the city Bhopal, the capital of Madhya Pradesh, India. The aim of the study was to frame the indicators and understand transport related spatial disparities. For understanding the same, the research was conducted at two levels; city level and local (micro) level. Indicators were identified for analysing the Just Transportation both at city level and local level. The city level analysis was based on 4 indicators (Availability, Affordability, External Cost, Accessibility) and 13 sub-indicators. For the local level, it was done on 4 indicators (Availability, Accessibility, Safety and Inclusivity, Affordability) and 8 sub-indicators.

The pan city analysed focused on the availability of the public transport for the high-income area and slums as well. Through Network Analysis and Statistical Tools, it was found that only 26% of the people have the 5 min walking accessibility to bus stops while this percentage is as low as 17% in slums. The walkability analysis conducted through road densities provided the insight that CBD area has the highest walkability score unlike the low-income residential areas. Under the external cost, the research focused on the exposure of vulnerable population to pollution due to transportation. Through mapping the pollution exposed population, the results provided that 80% of Bhopal has more than 5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ of PM2.5 concentration making it second city having greatest number of deaths due to PM2.5. The v/c ratios and LOS level analysis indicated that the non-availability of public transportation forced people to opt for private vehicles which in turned increased the v/c ratio of almost 50% road of Bhopal to more than 0.8.

For conducting local level analysis, three areas were selected based on land value, density, income and land use pattern. They are: Old City Area, CBD (high-income) and Peripheral area (low-income) of Bhopal. The network analysis interlinked with accessibility to medical and educational was conducted. The infrastructure availability in line with the spatial location of the settlement suggested that the CBD has the abundance of transportation facilities opposite to peripheral low-income settlements who, in turns, face 'spatial injustice'. The periphery area lacks basic accessibility to the services and connectivity. This is the area where the lower and middle income resides. Thus, it has a direct impact on the people's expenditure and quality of life. The results derived from the indicators established the direct link of spatial justice with the income and transport facilities.

Just City, Just Transportation, Spatial justice,
Transportation disparities, Accessibility and affordability

Schools for the transformation of Public Spaces that promote a good start in life and are references for healthy bonds: “Escuelas Limeños al Bicentenario I y II” Program

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Urban design and planning are closely related to the search for spatial justice in our territories. This approach is based on reflections on the spatial justice's concept, such as those of Edward W. Soja (2010), who argued that justice is intrinsically linked to the geographical space in which we live, since space influences processes such as inequality, exploitation, racism and sexism. Therefore, it is the duty of political and social action to address these problems strategically. Furthermore, university professor Erik Swyngedouw (2006) stated that social justice cannot be separated from the urban dimension of human inhabitation.

In this context, the “Escuelas Limeños al Bicentenario I y II” Program, organized by the Metropolitan Municipality of Lima and led by the interdisciplinary team of Anidare, is presented as a relevant case study in the search for spatial justice in Lima. It focused on the transformation of public spaces through participatory tactical urbanism and involved children, young community leaders, and local neighborhoods' residents.

Anidare, in line with UN-Habitat's principles (2020), recognizes public space design as a crucial element in promoting spatial justice, with a focus on gender equality, accessibility, and citizen participation. Various authors like Jian et al (2020). emphasize the importance of considering socio-spatial factors, such as access and social interaction (according to age, gender, etc.), especially for vulnerable groups like children. Therefore, Anidare employs tactical urbanism with an early childhood perspective to democratize public spaces for children, acknowledging the critical role of the first five years' life in child development,

as an extremely fast period of time with rapidly changing needs. So, we develop tools like the Typology of Urban Interventions with Relational Approach (TIUER in spanish) to diagnose the spatial scale interactions between children and caregivers in spaces to be transformed, and also certain urban design criteria (such as movement, expression, identity, routines, and framing), to create and build friendly and safe public spaces for early childhood.

The framework of action of this “urban acupuncture”, translated as intervention projects that affect limited areas, with fast - low budget execution; it's intrinsically linked to the participation of local citizens. To achieve this, our own project methodology is applied based on a “Training-Practical School” that consists of seven stages, from social-urban diagnosis to execution and community support, with citizen participation throughout the process.

As a result, the project carried out 14 urban interventions in 9 districts of Metropolitan Lima, involving environmental promoters and local youth organizations. This had a significant impact on citizen life in these public spaces, for example multiplying female spatial occupation by 2.8 times and the occupation of early childhood and childhood (0 to 15 years) by 2.7 times on average, compared to the pre-existing interventions situation. Finally, the time spent in the public space multiplied by 8 on average in the interventions, some even without prior time occupation.

Spatial justice, Urban design, Participatory tactical urbanism, Public space design, Early childhood perspective

Using Place-Based Reviews to Inspire Spatial Justice

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The creation of resilient, empowered and economically viable communities with sustainable futures is essential to tackling inequalities and amplifying local voices to ensure spatial justice. Applying a place focused and locally responsive approach to the delivery of public services can create a fair and equitable distribution of resources. This abstract delves into the outcomes of Place Reviews developed by Ryder Architecture. Using examples of Place Reviews in Scotland, this abstract presents a framework for identifying shared needs, ambitions, and opportunities to promote spatial justice.

Place is where people, location and resources combine to create a sense of identity and purpose, and it is at the heart of addressing the needs and realising the full potential of communities. Preserving and enhancing place identity ensures contextually appropriate responses that are mindful of history, culture, climate, landscape, and resources. Places are further shaped by the ways in which resources, services and assets are directed and used by the people who live and invest in them. They can often offer various unrealised assets, which, when tapped into, can unlock places, and create synergy, alignment, and positive change. Place Reviews utilise a place based approach to maximise opportunity, improve asset bases and services, and identify future asset strategies for their relevant locations.

These reviews use cascade approaches to tap into the benefits the state and its assets can offer, while also involving local communities and stakeholders to develop the project vision. They appraise the context on a national level, identify opportunities from a regional and local perspective and later engage with

stakeholders, including the public, private and third sector parties. Place Reviews follow a process of analysing a place, agreeing on objectives with stakeholders and communities, and developing proposals in line with the objectives. This creates a framework against which projects are validated at each stage and assessed at the end.

Dunoon and Rothesay Place Reviews demonstrate the potential of using anchor investments to create catalysts for local development. Following the analysis of existing assets and engagement with local stakeholders, a Place Brief is generated to reflect how current needs and ambitions could be achieved through collaborating with partners, or through using spaces to enable the transformation of services. A Place Diagram is then developed to appraise the Place Brief in the context of the existing infrastructural and geographical fabric of the place and to understand constraints and opportunities for using existing assets or creating new ones. This is followed by the development of a Place Programme, which creates a timeline for the implementation of developments based on tactical, opportunistic, and transformational opportunities.

In conclusion, Place Reviews present a proactive and cascade approach to collaboration between various stakeholders, maximising the opportunities for achieving spatial justice through understanding the key priorities for a community and applying them to existing and potential assets.

Spatial justice, Place Reviews, Community development,
Resource distribution, Stakeholder collaboration

MULTIDIMENSIONAL

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ONLINE

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Women's Perception of Safety in Public Space: The STEP UP Project

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This contribution is part of the scientific research project “STEP UP - Walkability for Women in Milan” (Grant No. 2022-1643), awarded by Fondazione Cariplo under the call for proposals “INEQUALITIES RESEARCH”, the aim of which is the definition of relevant factors related to women’s perception of safety while walking alone in public spaces, as affected by the risk of physical and verbal aggression. Developed by means of an intersectional approach, the contribution is the result of a scoping review conducted on some of the most relevant scientific contributions and policy guidelines about this topic. The first part of the review focused on findings from 23 scientific references revolving around the keywords gender, safety and walkability. This led to the establishment of three main Safety Factors - Level 1 (SF_L1): (i) Spatial Features (space characteristics/ morphological features); (ii) City Use (traces of behavior and presence of city users); and (iii) Hotspots (safe havens and no-go areas); further resulting in 19 sub-factors or Safety Factors - Level 2 (SF_L2). The second part of the review covered a collection of 20 reports and 10 guideline documents focused on diverse geographical scales, areas of interest and target audiences, as well as data collection methods for reports containing an original study on the topics of safety and walkability for women. This involved the selection of multiple case studies, which are also presented, maintaining a geographically diverse sample. The outputs of the proposed

review will be exploited to select a series of relevant geolocated datasets, to be retrieved, sorted, and filtered from open data repositories, geoportals, and census databases for the city of Milan, Italy. Spatial analysis results will help identify challenging areas of the city, as samples of analysis to develop a set of policy recommendations to enhance the level of walkability for women in Milan. The contribution is part of a spatial justice paradigm, falling specifically within the areas of procedural justice and recognition, as defined by the Department of Urbanism at TU Delft. It seeks to strengthen existing literature on the topic of gendered mobility and extract relevant data to be applied in practical GIS-based methodologies designed to measure the relationship between women’s perception of safety in the city and various influential factors related to the built environment. By mapping the city from a gender-based perspective, the STEP UP project aims to shed light on the disparate realities of walking in the city based on a person’s gender and the geographies of fear associated with it.

Walkability, Gender, Safety Factors, Inequality, Milan

The spatial justice as an analytical and territorial tool: readings from Portugal

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The concept of justice, when applied to space, underpins a comparison with other spaces or a deviation from a predefined standard, which gives us a relative rather than an absolute dimension (Hay, 1995). According to a synchronic approach, spatial justice stems from poor performance in significant dimensions of a territory, when compared to others. Similarly, a diachronic approach can reveal positive developments (Nyamai, 2022), juxtaposing different variants on the same reality.

Adopting a synchronic and diachronic analysis around the spatial justice, that is, comparative and combined in time and space, the Território.Justo.pt project (www.territoriojusto.wordpress.com) seeks to materialise and translate this concept in a comprehensive territory - Portugal -, from the municipal scale. To this end, in a first phase, three specific dimensions were listed, associated with the space and the actors that produce and transform it, specifically: (i) mobility (physical, virtual, social, personal), which allows us to know the ease with which people move to access personal and professional needs; (ii) governance, which penalises the territories with the greatest difficulty in mobilising the dynamics, wills and energies of those who inhabit them; (iii) economic assertiveness, which integrates the degree to which the economic base is able to assert itself through its innovation, competitiveness, added value, etc. In addition to these more structuring dimensions of the analysis, we include a dimension across the various municipalities analysed, which consists of a more general characterisation from a socio-demographic, economic and territorial point of view, defining a specific territorial point of view.

In a second phase, the main indicators associated with each dimension and best analysis model were discussed and selected by the team project and a group of experts at a workshop organised for this purpose, following a transdisciplinary approach. The result is an overview of Portugal, that shows the concentration and fragmentation of the spatial justice - read as an analytical and territorial tool - in the country, as well as the distance, and particularities between their 308 municipalities. A first analysis of this portrait, which will be presented at the symposium, constitutes an opportunity to strengthen and create new synergies, seeking to build and adopt a transdisciplinary and integrated approach around the spatial (in)justice, but also to inform the national public policies, their limits, and future challenges, at the light of current global and European agendas.

Spatial justice, Synchronic and diachronic analysis,
Territorial point of view, Transdisciplinary approach

Developing a Restorative Justice Master Planning Framework

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What makes a master plan “just?” In the past years, restorative justice has become a pillar of spatial justice and inclusive urban planning. Yet few practitioners have developed actionable frameworks to integrate its principles into neighborhood and master planning processes. To address this gap, the Community Health team at Public Works Partners developed a dynamic, and evolving, restorative justice framework for municipal master planning. The restorative process lays out a path to spatial responsibility and healing, centering them as key components of spatial justice. Our four-part framework begins with the co-creation of a Justice Index with the stakeholders most impacted by historical planning injustices. The Index is unique to each municipal context and offers broad guidelines on what a “just” city or region could - and should - include. It serves as a guiding compass for the master planning process, enumerating ~10 visions structured as justice statements: “A Just _(city)_ should...”

The participatory process to create the Index includes workshops that explore the city and region’s historical contexts and geographies of exclusion. However, our approach is not merely about identifying shortcomings. Rather, drawing on trauma-informed planning, it is centered on strengths-based and healing-oriented restorative practices. The workshop’s goal is to co-create a set of visions for the city. Once finalized, the Index is transformed into a checklist that planners, urban practitioners, and other stakeholders can use to ensure that their ideas and proposed solutions align with the city’s vision for spatial justice. The checklist’s strength is its simplicity. It transforms a set of visions into not only a ‘formal’ planning document, but also into an advocacy tool through which residents can hold municipal officials accountable throughout decision-making processes.

To complement the Index, we next develop Restorative Justice Case Studies and Best Practices. There is a notable lack of implementation-oriented literature on the ways in which municipalities have recently incorporated restorative justice into spatial justice planning processes. Using documentary sources, interviews, and roundtable discussion with key stakeholders, we document urban planning best practices on the implementation of restorative justice policies, procedures, and design in urban spaces.

We then pair the Best Practices with the Justice Index to develop concrete, actionable Restorative Justice Master Planning Strategies. These may include, as examples, justice zoning overlays, anti-displacement plans, public space design guidelines, and/or the creation of reparations committees, among other strategies. The recommendations translate historical findings and community visions into actionable strategies.

Ensuring that the master plan’s impact on restorative justice can be measured is a key component of our framework. In collaboration with city planners, we develop a set of Justice Metrics (KPIs) through which planners can evaluate the master plan’s alignment with the Justice Index and impact on addressing spatial injustices. The benchmarking tool can be adjusted and replicated in other municipal arenas, positioning master planning teams as leaders in the city’s equitable development.

We are working to further refine the Restorative Justice Framework for Municipal Master Planning. Our approach expands spatial justice planning by providing an actionable, implementation-oriented restorative justice framework. We believe that a just master planning process must include co-creation, strategy, and evaluation. Most importantly, though, it must be community-driven and actionable.

Restorative justice, Spatial justice, Master planning,
Justice Index, Best practices

The paradigm of citizen participation: Slum parliament, a convergence model

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Participatory approach - the most celebrated model in city building- by definition, it uses the expertise of all stakeholders to aid the development and decision-making processes. This paradigm can become just a ritual, where the beneficiaries are frequently passive spectators who are only informed but not involved and thereby failing to serve the communities' aspirations. Although there are many successful examples of participatory models around the globe, not all models are truly participatory; many are merely representative. How open this paradigm is to hearing marginalized people's voices, needs, opinions, disagreements, and suggestions is the question. Can the participatory model be a tool for social engineering and mobilization? These inquiries marked the beginning of the exploration of this multifaceted model through research and practice.

Objectives:

The objective of the intervention is to ensure spatial justice in slums through a participatory model of Slum parliament and thereby deriving a humanitarian and equitable model of slum redevelopment.

Method:

In a system where liveability and livelihood are frequently overlooked in the haste to discover solutions to narrow the gap between housing demand and housing supply, 'Life-line project' challenges the widely held belief that slums are a matter of habitat. The social framework that enables the convergence model in the Project is Slum Parliament, which fills the enormous gap between power holding government institutions, social institutions and the urban poor communities. Slum parliament, first of its kind, was established in Pumping station slum at Chintadripet in August 2021, which comprises

a council, an executive committee, and a working committee. Council consists of concerned stakeholders from 20 state and local government agencies, NGOs and civic groups. The committee has elected representatives of all genders from slums, and anyone above the age of eighteen. The parliament meets every month at the slum to discuss the issues faced by the community with the representatives of respective government authorities, take instant actions to solve them and review the progress of work from previous meetings. For instance, replacing damaged water pumps, renovation of community toilets, formation of self-help groups, organizing weekly classes and art festivals for children, free health camps, construction of community centre were some of the work done.

Key findings:

This model has actively represented the urban poor's voice over the past two years, attempting to incorporate their in-depth knowledge of the settlement, insights, and inputs in order to completely comprehend the nuances of their day-to-day lives. Here, participation served as a tool not only for the effective execution of projects but also for social engineering, crowd-sourced data collection, citizen mobilization, awareness-raising, and instilling a sense of civic duty among citizens. The community is involved throughout the processes of development from ideation, framework formation, iterations, activity planning, and implementation of the verticals. It resolves the disparities at the grass root level by ensuring equitable access to resources and opportunities. Slum parliament restored their faith in the city's governance structure and enabled more leaders to emerge from the community. Hence, they become the stewards of their own development.

Participatory Approach, Spatial Justice, Slum Parliament,
Social Engineering, Livelihood

Picturing spatial justice through multimodal collaborative ethnographies

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The paper shows examples of collaborative research carried out by children in their neighbourhood in multiple contexts across Europe and the urban conflicts and inequalities that arise in them. The examples include two stigmatised peripheries and two neighbourhoods passing a gentrification process.

Based on these multimodal ethnographies carried out by children, we can identify a series of lived experiences that can shed light on complex questions of spatial justice in changing urban contexts, however in a format/language radically different from what one might envision. By showing the practice of carrying out multimodal research, fully accessible to children, in terms of design, implementation, analysis, and dissemination, the paper problematises epistemic justice in relation to spatial justice. Who is allowed to produce knowledge on the city? Whose knowledge is being considered when we define and plan interventions on spatial justice? What formats of knowledge do we consider when analysing spatial justice?

The questions and practical examples of the paper aim at situating multimodal ethnographies in the debates about spatial justice and their potential in collecting, analysing and presenting the lived experiences of the various groups that make a neighbourhood 'alive'. At the same time shows how groups usually excluded from knowledge production - including but not limited to children - can create important knowledge on the cities.

Collaborative Research, Children, Urban Conflicts, Inequalities, Multimodal Ethnographies

MULTIDIMENSIONAL

17:35-18:35

ONLINE

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Equality opportunities-based social and spatial distributive justice of online-offline public services

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The concept of justice plays a central role in research on the distribution of public goods and services. It serves to determine how the burdens and benefits of our lives must be shared in society and distributed. The problem of how best to assess the distribution of the public resources, and the relationship between freedom and opportunity, have been discussed for a long time. To combine the discussion, Rawls (George Sher, 2012) introduced 'justice as fairness' and principles of justice. In the context of distributive justice, the principle 'fair equity of opportunity', corresponds closely to distributive justice, emphasizing each individual with the equal potential opportunity, or chance to enter the procedure and obtain advantages. Various research has extended the concepts and principles of justice according to their developmental characteristics, research scopes and subjects. Within the realm of urban studies, the spatial dimension, and its intricate interplay with the social dimension of justice have been expanded to comprehensively address the urban challenges. However, with the rapid development of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) affected public goods and services, there is a critical need for research, integrating social and spatial justice, to solve new curing forms of conflicts and contradictions in the online-offline resources distribution, especially where an integrated assessment method from empirical studies is lacking.

Therefore, this research will develop a method for assessing the spatial and social distributive justice, with a specific emphasis on the influence of ICT on the existing spatial disparities, using the government to citi-

zen (G2C) e-governance as an example, utilizing communities as research spatial units. To achieve this, an opportunity-based distribution justice evaluation framework is constructed, grounded in three foundational principles, similar to the Rawl's principles of justice, which are the 'fair equality of opportunity principle', the 'difference principle', and the 'maximizing the use of opportunities' (Jinping Zhou, 2011; George Sher, 2012). Furthermore, the definition of distributive justice in this research means the fair and inclusive distribution of opportunities to obtain offline and online burdens and advantages when accessing G2C governance services. And the framework comprises two main segments: (1) Equality: the goal of this part is fairness, that is, to ensure that everyone is treated equally in the distribution of the offline-online services. More specifically, we need to ensure that every community has the same opportunities to enter the procedure, and access the services. (2) Equity: the goal of this part is inclusive, that is, the worst do not get worse, and the better can use their opportunities effectively. This study contributes to the discourse on public goods and services distributive justice and offers a practical methodology for evaluating ICT-induced impacts.

Distribution justice, Spatial justice, Public services, ICT-led

Accessibility-Based Land Value Change Leading to Unjust Distribution of Rights Through Planning

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Public investments in “mass transit systems” should demonstrate that the “right to Public investments in “mass transit systems” aim to provide equal “right to accessibility” to various land use types and economic and social opportunities, as part of the broader concept of the “right to the city.” However, such accessibility can lead to value fluctuations along the transit line and within the areas surrounding the stations, often amplified by new land use developments seeking to benefit from improved accessibility. Planning and non-planning actions further influence these value fluctuations. This study focuses on the Istanbul Metrobus System as a case study to examine how planning and non-planning interventions have impacted the equitable or inequitable distribution of value arising from improved accessibility.

The research question central to this study is, “What role has planning/non-planning played in the equitable/inequitable distribution of the value that emerges as a result of accessibility?” The study employs extensive and intensive analysis methods within the Critical Realism Approach to assess the value increase before and after the opening of the Istanbul Metrobus System.

In the extensive analysis, it is found that the value increased by 28% along the metrobus line, with varying rates of value increase within the accessible distances of the stations, ranging from 20% to 280%. The study highlights how increased accessibility led to changes in property prices and rents and impacted users along the line.

The Cennet Mahallesi Station is selected for intensive analysis, revealing the reasons for value fluctuations. Interviews, observations, and planning decisions taken after the metrobus

system’s opening are examined. The study uncovers that despite the equal distance to the station, different value fluctuations created three distinct character areas at the same access points in Cennet Mahallesi. These variations resulted in rent and sales value increases, urban transformation, and allocation of land for housing and commerce, demonstrating the role of planning as a tool for social justice or injustice.

This study underscores the importance of managing the value creation process generated by accessibility through proper planning to ensure social justice and benefit the broader public. The example of the Istanbul Metrobus System provides insights into how public investments can be harnessed to promote equitable urban development.

Mass Transit Systems, Right to the City, Accessibility, Social Justice

A Futures-driven Approach to Design for Spatial Equity in Cities

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Imagineering of cities, or the process of translation of creative and imaginative ideas into a real input to be designed in urban places, is a task to be tackled. Yet another question, whose imagination it is, and how exactly it is produced? Modern urban design has been highly professionalised, as well as largely following the logic of normative and predictive path of city visioning. Following the normative approach to urban design implies using available data for planning which is based on big sets of data and knowledge available. Contemporary challenges of urban transition require us both to rethink the ways we think about urban places and inhabitants, as well as adopt new methods of engagement in city visioning. Design and futures studies have the potential to aid the design of urban places to become more exploratory and imaginative and find ways how to “engineer” and put into practice the imaginary output. On the other hand, there is a need to ensure that cities are designed to accommodate the needs of diverse groups of living beings - human or non-human, to enhance spatial equity. Design discipline can provide an opportunity to face both challenges and give a direction of a futures-driven and more-than-human perspective to the design of urban places. In this work, it was explored how a design futures-driven approach can inform urban design methodologies to create more inclusive urban futures. As a result, the JUSThood methodology was developed and implemented in five pilot studies on different spatial scales to design for spatial equity. The process of the participatory methodology consists of creating, immersing, and developing ideas in various scenarios and mapping them on the masterplans with the help of three sets of cards - (i) What-If

questions cards, (ii) Agent cards, (iii) Design cards. Finally, it was revealed that imaginary output of the methodology can be used in the format of masterplans for planning long-term transformations, as well as it enhances the inclusion of diverse users and species in the design of the space in a creative way.

Imagineering of Cities, Urban Design, Futures studies,
Spatial Equity, Participatory Methodology

Spatial Justice in Urban Landscapes: The Relationship between Accessibility Improvement and Residents' QOL in Singapore

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With the rapid pace of global urbanisation and the growth of urban populations, improving the quality of life for residents has become a focal point in urban research. Numerous studies underscore that sustainable transportation modes, particularly walking, have the potential to enhance people's quality of life by promoting physical activity and social connections. However, there is limited knowledge about the influence of various factors of walkability on the specific quality of life across different functional urban areas, particularly in previously road-oriented Asian cities.

Singapore's Chinatown is selected as a sample for its rich history and diverse social context, rapid urbanization and socio-economic shifts have brought forth pressing issues related to quality of life for such areas. The goal of this study is to reveal the mechanisms linking the improvement of accessibility and local residents' perception of quality of life in Singapore's Chinatown, determine whether all residents have equal access to essential amenities. This research employs a mixed-methods approach, combining individual insights, evaluations of quality of life from questionnaires with Geo-spatial data from GIS. And utilizes descriptive analysis, structural equation modelling (SEM), and correlation analysis to analyse the relationships between the overall quality of life of the residents and the demographic characteristics and perceptions of different destinations.

The findings of the study mainly indicate that: (1) Residents' overall quality of life are influenced more by the combined perception levels of accessibility to different amenities (including healthcare, social care, recreation and transportation) than the type of residen-

tial area. (2) Different types of amenities may have different levels of impact on resident's quality of life. For Chinatown residents, recreation is identified as the most crucial environmental requirement, and its quantity directly impacts residents' perceptions of quality of life, indicating the role of the number of destinations in connecting accessibility and quality of life. (3) In highly commercialised areas, factors related to the degree of commercialisation, such as price levels, service diversity, may have a greater influence on residents' perceptions of quality of life and accessibility compared to the assessment of amenities' quantity. The results underscore the importance of a holistic approach to urban planning. While accessibility remains crucial, it is not the sole determinant of QOL. Residents' perceptions are shaped by a myriad of factors, from the tangible (e.g. infrastructure accessibility) to the intangible (e.g. economic factors). The findings challenge the traditional notions of spatial justice, advocating for a more inclusive understanding that takes into account the diverse needs and aspirations of residents. It will contribute to improving the social inequities and informing the direction of future urban planning.

Social Equity, Quality of Life, Walkability, Accessibility, Residential Area

A Place-based Conceptual Framework for Studying Green Gentrification: The Case of Toronto

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Urban parks serve as valuable public resources, providing access to nature and spaces for community activities and gatherings. During the pandemic, their importance as primary meeting spaces was highlighted. However, certain urban parks have inadvertently led to the displacement of vulnerable communities, a phenomenon known as green gentrification.

The primary objective of this research is to understand and address green gentrification while emphasizing the need to reclaim urban parks as places of respite and rejuvenation. Green gentrification is defined as a process in which capital investment and greening efforts result in landscape changes benefiting higher-income residents while displacing marginalized households. The complexity of green gentrification and its context-dependent nature require researchers to consider the entire experience rather than individual indicators.

This research aligns with the Symposium's objective, offering methodological approaches to study spatial justice in the context of green gentrification in Toronto. The methodology includes a literature review on the history of gentrification in Toronto to identify mechanisms shaping local spatial inequalities. Using a poststructuralist lens, accomplished city planners' experiences were leveraged through semi-structured interviews to develop a place-based approach for studying green gentrification in Toronto's specific social, economic, and environmental context. Subsequently, interview data was analyzed using conceptual framework analysis to derive key findings.

The proposed approach will be place-based, tailored to Toronto's social, economic, and environmental context. For the Symposium's

purpose, the research will create a flexible conceptual framework for studying green gentrification. Unlike a rigid model, a conceptual framework offers an interpretive and indeterminate approach to studying social reality, making it adaptable based on the specific context.

The proposed conceptual framework comprises five categories: (1) Park Planning and Development Policies, (2) Gentrification and Displacement (3) Economic Development and Neighborhood Stabilization, (4) Community Engagement and Inclusivity and (5) Policy Tools and Approaches; each offering questions to stimulate inquiry and discussion. These categories aim to guide investigations and foster meaningful discussions in the study of green gentrification and spatial justice.

Urban Parks, Green Gentrification, Conceptual Framework, Displacement, Community Engagement

MULTIDIMENSIONAL

17:35-18:35

ONLINE

How Digital Planning Stimulate Spatial Justice

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Background: The government decision-making process over the property development proposals planning applications requires a better site context determination, efficient planning information distribution, and communicative stakeholders' consultation process.

These requirements are the main spatial justice measurements, and it is extraordinarily complex in terms of information types, communications methods, and development stakeholders' interests. Thus, it is difficult to manage development proposals planning application without making use of the planning websites, online mapping programs, case management software, and document management systems.

Moreover, the paperwork planning process led to lack of communication process, management coordination and community involvement, along with increased time consuming, and invalid planning applications. On the other hand, literature on the urban planning systems have not yet address the impact of the IT programs on city making process, which is the main purpose of the paper. Method: Based on interpretative, subjective, and qualitative research methods along with previous digital planning experience; the paper will examine the impact of IT programs on spatial development, with reference to two pillars that stimulate sustainable spatial justice, which are the involvement of the spatial information and the planning stakeholders' interest during the planning application process of the property development proposals.

Result: The paper therefore reveals important sub-topics that would contribute to the impact of digital planning on spatial development. First, it highlights how to prepare planning application using planning website informa-

tion. Second, the paper addresses the impact of spatial data software on planning application management process. Lastly, the paper examines how case management software determine inclusive consultations processes.

Conclusion: Sustainable urban development requires broad information distributions, multi stakeholders' involvement, and complex planning applications process. Hence, the planning systems become a crucial study on urban development studies. In that since, the planning systems shall question the digitalization of planning process, not just to stimulate spatial justice, but also to ensure sustainable built environment.

Spatial justice, Planning applications, IT programs,
Digital planning, Urban development

The visual dilemma of spatial (in)justices: Presenting The Need for Urban Visualisation Annotations to Inclusively Visualise New City Visions

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In this entry I would like to share the mid-range theory of 'Spatio-visual' justice that I developed during my PhD project to examine the ways in which planning visualizations become a question of social and spatial justice in cities. I propose this theory as an interdisciplinary approach to interrogate city imaging and branding that aims at opening questions about the diversity of city and place branding. This approach builds on urban studies, media studies, political science, and philosophy of justice. It provides a modern understanding of justice in the highly mediatized visual world. To understand the implications of spatio-visual interactions, I take the example of relocating the capital of Indonesia. Visualizations are widely used to promote the idea of relocating capitals across the world to a new location. For this purpose, diverse media, computer, and digital tools are used to visualize the newly planned city. I noticed that the visualization of new capital cities with the use of digital tools in the contemporary world highlights and addresses only exclusive parts of cities that target the elite populations, probably to attract investment and make the newly planned city look "better." Taking the case of capital relocation in Jakarta to the new city of East Kalimantan, Borneo, the article illustrates the need for another form of urban visualization to inclusively communicate the new planned cities. I argue that including linked invisible data to the communicated urban visualizations -which can be called urban-visualization annotations -would make this invisible information visible and, in turn, could be an effective counter-strategy to exclusive and non-democratic urban visions, especially if they include opportunities for excluded voices to dissent and join the conversation. My thesis focused on the intersection between the communication and visualization of urban visions and the spatialization of justice in the mediatized world. Addressing the problem of exclusive visualization of planning in the mediatized world, planning visualizations are understood as façades that obscure power asymmetries and matters of justice, revealing the political economy of cities. Taking Cairo as a glocal case, the study interrogates how urban planning becomes communicated and visualized in the maintenance of the prevailing polit-

ical and economic agendas of the ruling elite. The research fills three gaps in the literature regarding the ways in which planning visualizations relate to, reflect, and re-construct (1) the planning of cities, (2) the roles of actors involved in the planning communicative situations, and (3) the urban environment. I posit that the rise of digitalization and mediatization, and its effect on visualizations of the urban, creates a need to explore the ways in which the visual can create a problem of social and spatial justice. Therefore, the study's purpose is to develop a ground-up understanding of how and why planning visualizations in the mediatized world become a question of social and spatial justice. To this end, the mediatization of urban planning is explored through an examination of its products (planning visualizations) and its process (media tools employed to produce these visualizations) via a cumulative dissertation of five communicative situations among planners or between them and others. Starting with planning education, the papers move onto planning practice, politics, context, and culture. I argue that a theory of Spatio-Visual Justice explains the ways in which planning communication, digitalization, and visualizations provoke the perpetuation of exclusivity in planning and cities; thereby co-constructing spatio-visual (in)justice. Spatio-visual (in)justice is thus exemplified via exclusive planning visualizations, defined as the inquiry of 'who and what is made visible by whom, how, and why'. Practically, it represents the ratio of what is represented visually versus what is lived spatially and how each is mediatized through planning visualizations. The main proposition of this theory is simply that what (visually) provokes, perpetuates. It is suggested that it is not the communication, digitalization, and visualization of planning per se, but rather the provocation of exclusive planning visualizations that leads different participants in the different communicative situations to perpetuate exclusivity. In this process, exclusive planning visualizations affect and change the planning process, the role of other actors, and the lived ordinary cities. It follows, that whilst originally used as tools, exclusive visualizations become powerful participants/actors in the planning communicative situations.

Spatio-visual justice, Urban visualization, Social justice,
Mediatization, Planning visualizations

Porosity as a figure of spatial justice: strengths and critical issues from the case of pedestrianisation of via Andrea Costa in Mestre and Altobello 'Neighbourhood Contract' urban transformation.

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This contribution intends to discuss the strengths and critical issues of the concept of urban porosity as a design figure of spatial justice.

The research started from the case study of the urban regeneration process that took place between 2005 and 2015 in Altobello in Mestre, the Venice mainland, within the urban planning policy of the "Contratto di Quartiere" (Neighbourhood Contract). It is a significant case study of national policies that started in the early 2000s in Italy, based on a place-based and integrated approach to urban transformation. The research started with the report of the 'monitoraggio' - a moment to observe the transformation of the neighbourhood while it was still in progress, to 'monitor' how the spatial transformation (pedestrianization, renovation of some abandoned public housing buildings, implementation of new services like kindergarten and a civic centre) has affected on lifestyles of the marginalized Altobello neighbourhood.

The case study shows how space transformation can be seen as an opportunity to involve inhabitants and reduce the conditions of marginality of an urban block through public space transformation. Inhabitants' participation in goal-setting and co-design activities during the design phase has become an opportunity for people empowerment that contributes not only to the improvement of spatial conditions but also to social cohesion strengthening. The pedestrianization transformation has been the result of the participation of the inhabitants which promoted a more radical vision than the initially planned 'restricted traffic zone' towards a full via Andrea Costa Street pedestrianization. The project can be seen as an attempt to make the city more accessible, porous and

inclusive. The pedestrianization project looks to re-connect the most fragile and isolated part of the neighbourhood to the network of the city's public space to reduce its condition of marginality. The research also investigates how the transformation process was constructed and the relationship between the institutions and some private investors involved in the initiative. To increase the social mix of the neighbourhood, new private residences were built, and the research discusses the criticalities generated in the long term in the management of public space accessibility.

The main hypothesis of the "monitoraggio" research was that pedestrianization and the transformation of public space into a more 'porous' space could have improved the living conditions of the marginalized neighbourhood. Porosity has been intended as an attribute of space, as a potential quality of openness to passage (Viganò 2018), of extreme permeability for urban practices (Stavrides 2020): the reverse of the presence of closures, gates, and negation of use also due to the overwhelming presence of cars.

The research has been based on various survey instruments: 1) direct observation of urban practices and their description through photographs and interpretative schemes and mapping; 2) semi-structured interviews (about 40, to inhabitants, daily city-users and economic actors such as shopkeepers) starting from selected topics but leaving the possibility for interviewees to take the conversation to the issues that are important to them; 3) Short interviews on the use of renovated spaces during neighbourhood events and festivals.

Gender-Inclusive Space, Equal-Spatial Sequence Methodology, Urban Planning, Emotional Impact, Spatial Experience

The Sad Story of Sistan & Balouchestan: Evaluation of the province's position in development and inequality indicators

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Despite its strategically advantageous geographic position along Iran's southern border, the Sistan and Balouchestan province faces long-standing inequality challenges. This region, with its proximity to the Oman Sea, pivotal location on international trade routes, particularly the eastern axis, its role as a thoroughfare connecting Iran to the Indian subcontinent and East Asia via the Indian Ocean and the opportunities of foreign trade, re-exports, maritime industries, and fisheries, grapple with persistent inequalities and deficiencies. Despite notable progress in other Iranian provinces, statistics reveal a discouraging state of affairs in Sistan and Balouchestan.

This article aims to comprehensively assess Sistan and Balouchestan's standing among Iranian provinces concerning various socio-economic inequality and deprivation indicators, including unemployment rates, migration patterns, education, healthcare accessibility, disability rates, female-headed households, out-of-school children, uninsured individuals, and basic infrastructure like water and electricity in households. Additionally, we analyze the underlying causes contributing to this situation.

These disparities stem from a complex interplay of environmental factors, political-economic dynamics, deficiencies in spatial planning systems, a lack of integrated territorial management, and inadequate coordination among responsible organisations for spatial development.

Our analysis employs various models and coefficients, such as the Gini coefficient, relative poverty rate, coefficient of spatial concentration, shift and share analysis, labour productivity, and other assessments across multiple dimensions. The findings of this study reveal

that, despite being the focal point of land development initiatives, development plans, and charitable efforts over the past decades, this province continues to grapple with poverty and deprivation. It consistently ranks among the least developed provinces in the country across a range of indicators. Enhancing developmental metrics, particularly in terms of employment, is not just a regional priority but also a matter of national significance and security.

Furthermore, given the province's youthful demographic profile, investing in and prioritising healthcare, medical services, and education is imperative to elevate human development indices at the provincial level. Failure to address the challenges faced by the province's youth could turn this valuable demographic asset into a regional and, ultimately, national liability.

Socio-Economic Inequality, Deprivation Indicators, Sistan & Balouchestan, Spatial Planning, Youth Demographic Profile

The Post-Participation Phase: Strategies for Enhancing Data-Driven and Inclusive Urban Design and Planning

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The increasing emphasis on citizen involvement in policy and decision-making necessitates more democratic, inclusive, and diverse participatory mechanisms. However, traditional methods of citizen participation often perpetuate inequality by marginalizing specific groups. In contrast, digital technologies like e-participation and crowdsourcing platforms promise to broaden citizen engagement and include those who have historically been underrepresented or excluded from conventional participatory processes. While these digital platforms enhance the representativeness of decision-making, they also pose challenges, particularly in the analysis of large volumes of textual data.

Focusing on this intersection of technology and civic engagement, the present research aims to address the role of digital technologies and computational methods in urban design and planning. Specifically, it concentrates on participatory analytics and large-scale digital engagement. The overarching objective is to convert extensive digital participation data into actionable insights. These insights are intended for a diverse array of stakeholders, including architects, urban designers, planners, and policymakers, who are involved in urban transformation at various scales. To achieve this, the study employs a multi-methodological approach that integrates thematic coding, Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA), and Artificial Intelligence (AI)-enabled computational linguistic techniques such as topic modeling and sentiment analysis.

The research is substantiated by empirical evidence from three geographically diverse case studies: Singapore, Madrid, and Hamburg. Each case study offers unique insights into different scales and contexts of citizen participation. One of the novel contributions of this research

is the introduction of the “post-participation”, a critical phase that lies between data collection and its practical application. This phase necessitates a rigorous evaluation of participation processes, the effective management of large textual datasets, and the development of an integrated workflow for data analysis and interpretation.

To further enrich the analysis, the study introduces advanced techniques for visualizing and interpreting large-scale participation data. These techniques utilize multi-layered visualization methods and AI-enabled analytics, such as Natural Language Processing (NLP), topic modeling, and sentiment analysis. These analytical methods are complemented by a comprehensive set of interpretation criteria, both quantitative and qualitative, to ensure that the perspectives of all stakeholders, including marginalized and minority groups, are adequately represented in decision-making processes. On a practical level, the research also focuses on the design aspects of user interfaces and instructional modalities for digital participation platforms. It proposes a post-participation toolkit for assessing the quality and effectiveness of digital participation, particularly focusing on data analysis and interpretation. Taken together, these contributions provide a significant advancement in the field of urban design and planning support as they offer robust analytical tools and methodologies that aim to create more sustainable, equitable, and inclusive urban environments. Consequently, this research not only enhances the utility of participation data but also facilitates more equitable and inclusive decision-making processes. It thereby makes a significant contribution to the evolving landscape of urban design and planning.

Digital Technologies Participatory Analytics, Urban Design
Computational Methods, Inclusive Decision-Making

MULTIDIMENSIONAL

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ONLINE

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Understanding Urban Environments from a Maternal Perspective: Exploring Maternal Experiences and Spatial Justice

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The configuration of urban space, influenced by the prevailing social and cultural systems aligned with the global patriarchal framework, continues to contribute to urban deprivation within cities. These urban spaces, integral to our lived experiences, must be thoughtfully planned and designed to embrace the diverse needs of individuals, irrespective of age, race, gender, economic status, or social situation.

Despite previous literature examining women's experiences in urban spaces, the inclination to treat women as a monolithic group risks overlooking their nuanced requirements and needs related to physical spaces.

With the aim of investigating the dynamic interplay between gender and maternity, the research employs an intersectional perspective. Intersectionality is a framework that recognizes how various aspects of identity, such as gender, race, class, and other social categories, intersect and interact to shape individuals' experiences and opportunities within a given social context. This lens allows us to explore the unique challenges and needs that emerge at the intersections of different identities, offering a more nuanced understanding of the complexities faced by marginalized individuals within urban environments. Using an urban ethnographic approach, this research deeply explores the challenges and experiences mothers face while utilizing public spaces, whether with infants/toddlers or during pregnancy. The study's foundation rests on in-depth interviews with mothers, aiming to capture their narratives and specific needs within the public spaces of Amman Downtown, Jordan.

In the pursuit of spatial justice, it is important to provide a platform for mothers

to express their needs and aspirations. This fosters a comprehensive understanding of the urban environment through the lens of marginalized communities. Integrating these insights into the planning and design process shouldn't be seen as supplementary; instead, they offer innovative opportunities to foster inclusive spaces. Shedding light on mothers' needs can help policymakers, landscape architects, and urban planners frame a new, inclusive narrative for the built environment.

Urban space configuration, Gender and maternity, Intersectionality, Urban ethnographic approach, Spatial justice

Theories of spatial justice: the case for an engagement with racial capitalism

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Urban Studies has long omitted race from discussions about how the urban is formed (Dantzler and Korver-Glenn, 2022; Pulido, 2016). Instead, race has only been contended with when examining outcomes of urban processes (Korver-Glenn et al., 2021). This is because Urban Studies has sought 'universal' theories of urbanism that have treated race as a time and space bound phenomenon that is not present across all urban processes (Dantzler and Korver-Glenn, 2022). Consequently, scholarship demonstrating the inseparable nature of racism and capitalism have been excluded from 'over-arching' theories of urbanism (Robinson, 1983; Du Bois, 1935). This has resulted in an abundance of racial erasures within Urban Studies, whereby the work of predominantly black scholars has been dismissed from mainstream studies (Danewid, 2020). This has had consequences for how academics have come to conceptualize urban forms of justice, how it can be achieved and the extent to which racialised communities are able to benefit from justice focused initiatives. In recent years, however, there has been a growing number of scholars who have called into question the validity of urban theories as a result of this (Dantzler, 2021; Dantzler and Korver-Glenn, 2022). Such scholars have sought to conceptualise urban processes as part of a larger process of racial capitalism, which "is a way of understanding the role of racism in enabling key moments of capitalist development" (Bhattacharyya, 2018: ix; Robinson, 1983).

This presentation will consider how race structures the urban form and how theories of racial capitalism should be intimately bound with theories of spatial justice. It will use Birmingham, UK as a case study to examine the relationship between race and housing regen-

eration programmes under the Big City Plan, which is a 20-year (2010 - 2030) development plan that aims to position Birmingham as "a leading world city" (Birmingham City Council, 2011: 11). It will demonstrate how Birmingham's racialised inner city housing landscape, a product of past and present forms of racism, has been fundamental to the success of housing regeneration programmes in Birmingham. The presentation argues that without an engagement with the theory of racial capitalism, the ability to conceptualize, measure and achieve spatial justice will be limited. As such it calls for scholars working in the field of spatial justice and seeking to create effective benchmarks of justice, to divert from historic trends of omitting the role of race in structuring the urban form from academic studies, and instead engage with the theory of racial capitalism to bring about effective forms of justice.

Race, Urban Studies, Racial Capitalism, Spatial Justice, Housing Regeneration

Enhancing commuting experience in Almaty's suburbs: strategies for improving public transport accessibility

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Commuting plays a pivotal role in the development of urban agglomerations, facilitating the expansion of cities and contributing to economic growth. In Almaty, Kazakhstan, public transportation is the primary mode for 37% of the Almaty population. However, a shortage of public transportation in the city's suburbs poses serious problems, resulting in long waits, crowded buses, and longer travel durations. These problems have a negative effect on suburban inhabitants' quality of life and impede the Almaty agglomeration's overall growth. With an emphasis on the Talgar and Enbekshikazakh districts, this study examines the accessibility of public transportation in Almaty's suburbs. Based on the interviews with experts and commuters the study highlights the necessity of cooperation between regional authorities and the Almaty City Mobility Department as well as the significance of integrating suburban and urban transportation systems. The implementation of light rail transportation, the development of passenger transfer hubs, and the relaxation of criteria for bus drivers are some of the long-term suggestions made by experts to improve accessibility to public transportation. It is crucial to continuously monitor developments and conduct additional research to build a more efficient and sustainable transportation system in Almaty's suburbs. The city might enhance commuter experiences, ease traffic congestion, and promote economic growth over time by putting the suggested initiatives into practice.

Commuting, Public Transportation, Almaty, Suburbs, Accessibility

Towards a More “Spatially Just” transition in Urban Transport System: The Capability Approach as a Framework for Action

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The proposal aims to improve the accessibility of pedestrian footbridges in Nakuru City, Kenya, using a mixed-methods approach. The study will collect qualitative and quantitative data, contextualizing the Socially Just Public Transport Pillars (SJPTP) (Kamau, A., & Manga, E. 2020) notions as best practices. The capability approach will be applied to evaluate the fairness and equity of urban transport systems, focusing on individuals' ability to achieve their goals and lives. The paper will assess whether the footbridge meets the pillars of socially just transport systems, including availability, inclusivity, safety, accessibility, and sustainability. The findings will be analyzed for the design and implementation of urban transport systems in Kenya and other countries. The capability approach is a valuable tool for ensuring fair, equitable, and accessible urban transport systems.

3.0 Background and the Motivation of the Project.

Introduction and study motivation: The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) was adopted by 193 UN General Assembly member states, with cities customizing them for local conditions. SDG 11 aims to make cities inclusive, safe, resilient, and sustainable. Cities are customizing the SDGs to address social exclusion and inequality, focusing on access to safe, affordable, accessible, and sustainable transport systems. Public transport systems play a crucial role in driving inequality, affecting health and well-being. Nakuru municipality faces severe public transport problems, including poor road/ street conditions, inadequate terminal facilities, inadequate traffic management and pedestrian infrastructures. Social-spatial just public transport concept. Social-spatial justice aims to create equity and fairness in society for all, particularly disadvantaged groups. It is based on five interrelated dimensions of environmental justice; distributive, recognition, public deliberation, re-

sponsibility and capability. A socially just public transport system should focus on Availability, Safe and Affordable Access, Inclusion, Human Rights and Equity, and Sustainability. These pillars emphasize adequate space for expansion, mode shifting from private vehicles to public and non-motorized transport, and reducing air and noise pollution.

4.0 Specific Objectives:

To assess the accessibility of pedestrian footbridges in Nakuru City, Kenya, using a mixed-methods approach. To analyze the findings for the design and implementation of urban transport systems in Kenya and other countries.

5.0 Project Design/Methodology. Study Design.

This study examines a pedestrian footbridge suspended along the Nairobi -Nakuru Highway in Nakuru, Kenya, focusing on social justice principles in urban mobility infrastructure and transport policies. The study analyze the holistic conception of the Socially Just Public Transport Pillars. (SJPTP) value proportion in matters that influence the wellness and well-being of city residents. The study uses quantitative and qualitative approaches to assess public participation, process value proposition, and participants' perspectives.

Target population and Sampling.

The study involves stakeholders in urban mobility projects, including citizens, policymakers, regulators, planners, public transport provider, community leaders, and civil society. Finalized sampling procedures and techniques ensure representativeness and data comparability.

6.0 Ethical issues.

The study aims to maintain ethical standards by obtaining ethical clearance from relevant agencies, such as NACOSTI in Kenya. Participants will be informed of the study's purpose and roles, and participation will be voluntary. Confidentiality, anonymity, and privacy will be maintained throughout the research process, with individual identification and no monetary compensation.

Nakuru City, Pedestrian footbridges, Social-spatial justice, Socially Just Public Transport Pillars (SJPTP)

MULTIDIMENSIONAL

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ONLINE

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Assessment of socio-economic embeddedness of Urban green space in Delhi: A micro-level study using geospatial techniques

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As cities across the globe are growing with time, the contestation of land among built infrastructure and green spaces is also increasing. Urban Green Spaces (UGSs) such as forest, parks and other natural environment provide various kind of benefits to the urban population but due to urbanisation, these spaces are rapidly shrinking. Hence, the demand for UGS has become an important issue globally wherein citizens are asking for its provision and alignment with their 'right to city'. It has also been observed that the intra-city availability of UGS depends on the socio-economic characteristics of the neighbourhood population throughout the world. In the Global South, and especially in India, various kinds of socio-economic inequalities exist depending upon the caste, gender, and economic status of the people. Delhi, being the capital as well as one of the greenest cities of India having a green cover of 23.06%, has thus become an important area of interest to understand this dynamic. The objective of this study was to assess how socioeconomic characteristics of the population determine the quality, availability, and accessibility of urban green spaces in the wards of Delhi. This was done by, first, exploring the availability (including quantity and quality) and accessibility of UGS in different neighbourhoods (census wards) of the city using satellite data-derived geospatial matrices. Indicators related to quantity, quality, and accessibility of UGS were generated from NDVI image of Delhi in Fragstats 4.2 software. Then, the assessment of socioeconomic status (SES) of wards was carried out using 11 census variables such as the population of scheduled caste, the population of working women, sex ratio, ownership of house, ownership of vehicles, etc. of the respective census wards. Principal component analysis (PCA) of above mentioned 11 variables was performed and an SES index was generated to obtain clusters of Socioeco-

omic Status (SES) of wards. Using 'partition around medoids' (pam) function by NbClust package in R, 6 socioeconomic status clusters of wards were generated (i.e. 1 to 6, where cluster 1 represents Very Low socioeconomic status and cluster 6 represents Very High socioeconomic status cluster). A further probabilistic link analysis of the relationship between the socio-economic characteristics of the population and matrices related to quality and accessibility of UGSs was done to understand if these two have any correlation in our study area. The probabilistic links between UGS matrices and socio-economic status of wards were then analysed using Multinomial Logistic Regression (MLR) based on respective p-values. As a result, it was found that for SES clusters 2, 3 and 4 (representing Low SES, Moderately low SES, and Moderately High SES clusters), there were no probabilistic linkages of quality, accessibility of UGS and SES of wards as the p values of respective UGS matrices were not significant. There was a significant relationship between quality and accessibility in SES cluster 5, which represents High SES. In SES cluster 6, which represents Very High SES, a significant relationship between accessibility to UGS and SES of ward cluster was found. The MLR analysis showed that clusters belonging to High SES and Very High SES have a greater quality and accessibility of green spaces in comparison to Very low SES, Low SES, Moderately low SES, and Moderately High SES clusters. This is probably due to poor planning of UGS and bourgeois environmentalism in Delhi where gated communities have restricted the access to UGS for wards falling in lower SES cluster. Hence, planning and policy interventions are required so that the city can become environmentally 'just' where people from every strata can enjoy the benefits of UGS. This study, thus, provides policy directions to the urban planners for an equitable planning of UGS across socioeconomic strata in the city of Delhi.

Urban Green Spaces (UGS), Socioeconomic characteristics, Socioeconomic Status (SES), Multinomial Logistic Regression (MLR)

Evaluating Practices Producing Collective Services in Maputo through the Spatial Justice Lens

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Besides being an imperative guiding principle for urban policy and planning towards reducing uneven development in cities, spatial justice is recognised as a tool to address exclusion in postcolonial urban realities. In contexts like Maputo, where there is a discrepancy between planning and the processes and practices of urban transformation, spatial justice presents itself as a perspective to overcome spatial inequalities solidified by colonial legacies and address contemporary inequalities. A particularly important aspect is access to urban services and (social) infrastructures. However, while pursuing values of just cities is important, there is a need to establish planning systems that meet the local sociocultural and institutional reality in contexts such as the Global South. Considering the inadequacy and the ineffectiveness of planning in many Southern contexts, when investigating spatial justice - authors have raised three important analytical dimensions to understand spatial justice of 1) rules 2) process and 3) outcomes (Uwayezu & de Vries, 2018) - it is important to grasp the perception of 'justice' within and beyond existing language and vocabulary. This paper aims to analyse 'collective' service provision (i.e., social infrastructures such as schools and public spaces) in Maputo through the lens of spatial justice. Additionally, the paper explores how institutional processes embody and how local actors perceive spatial justice. Little research exists that aims explicitly to measure and develop a set of indicators for spatial justice in the context of service provision in Global South cities. Here, I argue that procedural injustices materialise through how different actors represent

(Lefebvre, 1974) spatial justice, which challenges us to reimagine indicators for assessing service accessibility. This investigation will address the following question: What are the most relevant criteria to evaluate spatial justice in access to collective services? This will be explored through a review of the framework of rules regarding the selected service(s), an examination of the procedural reality of providing services, and actors' roles and responsibilities (through interviews and review on planning and management instruments). Moreover, spatial justice processes (the outcome) are mapped (through participatory mapping and GIS). A set of existing indicators for measuring accessibility to services will be used as a baseline to build on more just measuring criteria. This paper is part of PhD research that examines the production of 'collective' infrastructure and services in the Maputo Metropolitan area to reflect on more inclusive and equitable approaches to urban planning and policy. The results are expected to lead to an understanding of concrete aspects to be considered in improving service accessibility indicators.

Spatial justice, Collective service provision, Global South cities, Service accessibility, Urban planning

A Planner's Quest for Identifying Spatial (In)Justice in Local Communities: A Case Study of Urban Census Tracts in North Carolina, USA

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For the past several decades, spatial justice has been presented as a conceptual framework to understand and address geographic inequalities. To date, most work associated with spatial justice has been qualitative and case study based. This paper seeks to explore the issue of spatial justice through the development of a Spatial Justice Index (SJI). The SJI quantitatively explores geographic based variables of urban census tracts in North Carolina to apply the underlying concepts of spatial justice in the real world. Using a principal components analysis approach, the SJI incorporates variables related to the following categories that comprise the concept of spatial justice: Public Goods, Basic Services, Cultural Goods, Economic Opportunities and Healthy Environments and are explored across the following spatial measures: spatial density, spatial proximity, spatial diversity, and spatial connectivity. The results highlight the benefits of dense, mixed use development patterns, that are well connected in achieving higher levels of spatial justice. The development of a Spatial Justice Index can be applied by urban planners and government officials across the entire Country to help communities comprehend, accept, and combat spatially injustices.

Commuting, Public transportation, Almaty, Suburbs, Accessibility

Spatial Justice: Unravelling Distributive Spatial Disparities, A Multidimensional Methodological Frameworks Approach to Distributive Justice with a Focus on Kumirmari in the Sundarbans

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In the realm of urbanism and sustainability, the notion of spatial justice serves as a critical guiding principle, reflecting the imperative to ensure the fair and equitable distribution of resources, burdens, and benefits across diverse regions and communities. The essence of distributive spatial justice lies in the equitable allocation of resources and opportunities, underpinning the very fabric of societal harmony and sustainable development. To discern and benchmark the degree of distributive fairness, a multifaceted approach combining quantitative and qualitative methodologies has been proposed. The research will focus on a specific case study area to exemplify the practical application of these methodologies. The chosen case study area is Kumirmari in the Sundarbans region, where the intricate interplay of environmental vulnerability, economic disparities, and social well-being is particularly pronounced. By delving into the unique challenges and opportunities presented by Kumirmari, the research aims to provide insights that can inform targeted interventions and policy measures to enhance distributive spatial justice in this vulnerable region. The research leverages geospatial analysis, drawing upon advanced Geographic Information Systems (GIS) techniques, to dissect the spatial distribution of key assets, services, and disadvantages. This research employs a spatially explicit dataset encompassing economic indicators, environmental quality metrics, and social well-being indices. By dissecting these dimensions through a geographic lens, the research gains a granular understanding of how spatial inequalities manifest on the ground. This multidimensional perspective allows for a nuanced assessment of distributive spatial justice beyond simple income or resource allocation metrics. Beyond quantitative assessments, advocacy for a qualitative exploration of lived experiences to complement our understanding

of distributive justice. Qualitative data, gathered through interviews, focus group discussions, and ethnographic observations, provides a vital perspective on the tangible impacts of spatial inequalities on marginalized communities. This holistic approach transcends statistical abstraction, revealing the human dimensions of distributive injustice. The research seeks to develop a comprehensive spatial justice index, amalgamating quantitative and qualitative data to provide a holistic measure of distributive fairness. This index not only identifies disparities but also informs the formulation of targeted policy interventions. By evaluating the impacts of past policies on the distribution of resources and opportunities, we pave the way for evidence-based decision-making in urban planning and policymaking. The implications of the research extend far beyond academia, resonating deeply with policymakers, urban planners, and grassroots advocacy groups. The findings offer a practical roadmap for redressing spatial injustices by identifying areas where intervention is most urgently needed. Moreover, the spatial justice index provides a tangible benchmark against which the effectiveness of policy measures can be evaluated, ultimately guiding the development of more equitable and sustainable urban landscapes. The research endeavours to unravel the complexities of distributive spatial justice through a rigorous and multifaceted approach. The research objective seeks to bridge the gap between theory and practice by offering actionable insights for policymakers, urban planners, and advocates committed to fostering equitable and sustainable urban environments. Through the lens of distributive spatial justice, the research contributes to the overarching goals of the symposium and advances the discourse surrounding the pivotal role of spatial justice in the pursuit of a more just and sustainable future.

Spatial justice, Distributive justice, Geospatial analysis, Geographic Information Systems (GIS), Distributive fairness

Thinking at Intra-city Scale to Promote Spatial Justice: Reflections from Cape Town, South Africa

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The field of spatial planning has been increasingly concerned with the idea of a just city.¹ However, in practice, such ideals and intentions of planning practice(s) do not necessarily translate into realising socially just outcomes on ground. Given that there are more brownfield than greenfield cities across the world, central to this tension is the complexity of underlying layers of spatial inequality in these cities stemming from their legacies of exclusionary socio-spatial systems and planning practices.

More often than not, designing for socially just outcomes ends up reinforcing pre-existing spatial inequalities and hierarchies of access and use of urban infrastructures. The nexus is so complicated that plans (and practices thereof) that are focused on addressing socially desirable intentions are not guaranteed to have desired outcomes. In this context, how can we align these intentions and outcomes better?

In this paper, I examine whether reading spatial justice in cities through the lens of spatial inequality and welfare can aid in such an alignment. I build on an analytical framework that defines a set of contextually normative principles for spatial organisation at the intra-city level, addressing spatial inequality and welfare outcomes. Using this framing, I propose a more nuanced and granular reading of spatial justice. I suggest that using a multi-dimensional framework, to assess the implications in which the different dimensions of spatial inequality interact and intersect in cities, could open up pathways to reading (and designing) policy that realise spatially just outcomes across scales within the city.

This study builds on illustrations from the City of Cape Town, which allow us to define a

benchmark to understand these paradoxes of intent versus outcome, thereby acting as a reference point for any other city that is grappling with similar challenges of spatial injustice and inequality. The case of South African cities is of particular value to these discourses of spatial (in)justice in cities, as they also speak to the growing evidence from other geographies of the global South that are navigating similar complexities of historical exclusionary planning practices and continuing unequal and unjust forms of spatial outcomes.

Commuting, Public transportation, Almaty, Suburbs,
Accessibility

SYMPOSIUM

DAY 3

ONLINE

Online

Keynote

Behnam Taebi

Full Professor of Energy & Climate Ethics and Scientific Director of the Safety & Security Institute at Delft University of Technology. He further leads TU Delft | The Hague, which aims to bring engineering knowledge closer to the heart of (international) public policy and politics.

Taebi studied Material Science and Engineering (2006) and received his Ph.D. in Philosophy of Technology (2010). He was affiliated with Harvard University's Belfer Center for Science and International Affairs (2014-2020) and a member of The Young Academy of the Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and Sciences (DJA-KNAW, 2016-2021). He is the co-Editor-in-Chief of Science and Engineering Ethics, and co-editor a volume on The Ethics of Nuclear Energy (Cambridge University Press, 2015) and the author of a monograph on Ethics and Engineering. An Introduction (Cambridge University Press, 2021). Taebi is also a Member of the Netherlands Scientific Climate Council. His research interests are in energy ethics, nuclear ethics, responsible innovation and engineering ethics.

ACADEMIC

16:25-17:25

ONLINE

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Climate x Spatial Justice: measuring the impacts of the 2019-2028 São Paulo Cycling Plan on climate change mitigation and spatial inequalities

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Modernity has been intrinsically structured into patterns of ongoing colonialism and ecological devastation. The IPCC report (IPCC, 2022, p. 11) recently recognized that reality. Many authors have emphasized that social inequalities are not only reinforced by the differential impacts of climate change, but they also feed it (Green and Healy, 2022). On the other hand, certain climate policies can reproduce and enhance spatial and social injustices (Green and Healy, 2022). To account for that dialectic, new theories and epistemologies address climate and spatial justice concomitantly through new understandings, methodologies, and calls to political action - as is the case of the decolonial ecology (Ferdinand, 2022). Using urban data science methods, our research enters a dialogue with such understandings and analyzes the 2019-2028 São Paulo Cycling Plan, which foresees adding nearly 1,300 km of bike lanes in that city to reach 1,800 km by 2028. We measure and correlate the existing infrastructure and the plan's potential impact on greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and socioeconomic inequalities. First, using socio-demographic data from the 2010 Brazilian Census (contained in the hexagons provided by the Institute of Applied Economics Research survey on Inequality of Access to Opportunities), we calculated the Euclidean distances between the current cycling network and citizens, also considering the social markers of income, race, and age. The results show that the average Euclidean distance in 2017 was 997.5m. When race is accounted for, the distance was 836.0m for white people and 1293.8m for Blacks. We also found significant income inequalities: a distance of 369.6 m for the 20%

wealthiest, and 997.5m for the 29% poorest 20%. Within age groups, the distance was 2,950.0m for 0-5 year-olds, and 1,161.0m for 70 years and above. Second, the same methodology was applied to evaluate the scenario considering the 2019-2028 São Paulo Cycling Plan goals. In 2028, even though there would be a 93% improvement in access to the network for the population as a whole, inequalities would be amplified by 9% on average (with a peak of 19% in 2021): 5.2% for Black people, 13.6% concerning people with the 20% lowest income, and 9% for the age group 0-5 years in comparison to 70 year-olds and above. Third, using 3D graphs, the results were interpolated with originally obtained data from the São Paulo's 2020-2050 Climate Action Plan (PlanClima SP), whose ambitious scenarios predict the full implementation of the 1,800 km bike lanes in 2028, as well as 2.82% annual reduction in emissions (switching from other modes to cycling), and decreasing CO2 emissions by 238,887 thousand tons until 2030. We find that the total network expansion plan promotes decarbonization and improves general accessibility but amplifies income, race, and age inequalities. Finally, we compared these results with the Business as Usual scenario from PlanClima SP, which does not foresee any measures to mitigate climate change, including the cycling system. In that case, the GHG would double by 2050.

Cycling Infrastructure, Climate Justice, Socio-Ecological Inequalities, Urban Data Science

Environmental Justice in Italy: A Geo-statistical Analysis of Environmental Hazards and Socioeconomic Factors

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The analysis of environmental issues and the pursuit of environmental justice within the broader framework of spatial justice have gained significant attention in modern times. While progress has been made in understanding environmental impacts, the need to examine environmental inequalities persists. This becomes particularly important when the burden of environmental 'bads' (Damery et al., 2008; Chakraborty et al., 2011) is borne disproportionately by disadvantaged or minority individuals, groups, and populations, whose greater vulnerability to negative effects generates further inequalities. Our study aimed to propose a methodology to identify and analyse potential 'sacrifice zones' within a region of interest using: (i) Exploratory Spatial Data Analysis (ESDA), (ii) Municipal Risk Indicator, and (iii) Spatial Autoregressive (SAR) models. As a case study, we focused on the Campania region of Italy, due to its significant relevance in the field of environmental justice, particularly in the context of the illegal dumping of hazardous waste, prolonged waste management issues, and the environmental and health disaster that have disproportionately impacted its marginalized population. The relationship between environmental hazards and social disadvantage in the Campania region of Italy was estimated and the findings of this preliminary study in this area are presented. Our preliminary results (i) reveal a non-random distribution of contaminated sites and waste management plants, (ii) localize the 'sacrifice zones' predominantly located in specific municipalities, and (iii) show a disproportionately burdened higher environmental risk and greater social vulnerability in some specific areas, providing empirical evi-

dence of spatial injustices. Further investigations are required to replicate the results of this study under different environmental conditions. The adaptability of our methodology to diverse spatial contexts and data sources underscores its potential for advancing spatial justice benchmarking initiatives. Future research will attempt to combine quantitative assessments with qualitative analyses to comprehensively grasp the complex and multidimensional aspects of environmental justice in the identified 'sacrifice zones'.

Environmental Justice, Geo-statistical Analysis, Socio-spatial Inequalities, Waste, Italy

Understanding Disparities of Public Green Spaces Accessibility in Urban Fringe Areas: A Comparative Analysis Based on Gravity-based and Ga2SFCA Methods

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In the context of architecture and urban planning, there has been a historical tendency to design cities with a one-size-fits-all approach, leading to non-gender-neutral urban environments. Women, girls, and public green spaces play a crucial role in maintaining the natural landscape within cities. These green spaces, categorized as natural, semi-natural, or artificially designed, enhance urban sustainability by filtering pollutants, reducing noise, and improving overall environmental quality. Access to these spaces positively impacts the well-being of urban residents. However, the distribution of these green spaces within cities is often unequal, with disparities linked to factors like race, age, and socioeconomic status. Recognizing the importance of equitable access to these spaces has become a key concern in recent years, particularly within the realm of environmental justice.

The term accessibility denotes the potential for individuals to participate in or access a service or facility. This concept was originally introduced in a rigorous, quantified way by Hansen in 1959 and has since been extensively discussed in the realm of spatial equity. More recently, accessibility is considered a significant indicator that reflects the equitable distribution of social resources, such as PGS (Wu et al., 2020). Despite this, there is abundant evidence showing the significant inequality in access to these valued green spaces throughout the UK and in the wider world. For the UK cities, the paradox appears to be that often the fringes of the historic cities are less well provided with PGS, and this has not been systematically examined. To address the above

concerns, this study aimed to develop a quantitative approach by comparing the Gravity-based measure with the Gaussian Two-step Floating Catchment method (Ga2SFCA) to investigate the current provision of PGS in urban fringe areas in order to determine the level of difficulty in accessing green spaces. To achieve this aim, the research has three objectives: (1) review different definitions and measurements of accessibility; (2) identify appropriate methods for measuring PGS accessibility; and (3) based on the selected methods, assess the distribution of PGS in Cambridge's urban fringe areas and the challenges related to accessing green spaces, as a demonstration test of the comparative analysis.

This study develops a toolbox to measure the accessibility of publicly accessible green spaces in cities, with a view to examining the issues of PGS inequity among the urban fringe areas of Cambridge. While previous studies have provided valuable insights, this study aimed to optimize the data collection and calculation methods to generate more systematic and accurate results. The comparative analysis and measurements show that the location, planning, and configuration design of PGS are the main factors that result in PGS inequity. This points to an urgent need to reconsider the approach to the planning and design of PGS, especially when laying out new neighbourhoods on the urban fringe areas.

Public green spaces, Accessibility, Urban ecosystems
Environmental justice, Inequality

Processes and patterns of structural violence and spatial (in)justice in housing production within a complex geopolitical border context

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The present research, an integral component of a doctoral thesis, primarily focuses on discerning socio-spatial disparities inherent in the frameworks perpetuating structural violence and spatial injustices. This investigation centers on two distinct models of housing production within the border region of Ciudad Juárez, Mexico.

The establishment of new real estate developments, with the aim of providing alternative housing solutions to salaried workers, particularly those employed in the manufacturing industry, represents a unique approach to urban development in the border region. This approach contrasts with conventional city formation methods, such as self-production, informal settlements, and occupation.

However, the northwestern peripheral zone of Ciudad Juárez, marked by its informal layout and the concentration of low-income neighborhoods, faces challenges with the emergence of new real estate developments, leading to conflicts and tensions within these peripheral and contested spaces.

The absence of essential services, amenities, and basic infrastructure surrounding this new city model has led to a process of urban consolidation characterized by stigmatization, marginalization, segregation, and the degradation of the housing environment. These factors significantly contribute to the perpetuation of pronounced social inequalities, disproportionately impacting the most underprivileged members of society.

It is worth noting that such challenges are not unique to Latin American cities but are prevalent in various urban areas across the region.

The methodology of this study was conducted using geographic information systems, involving a multicriteria analysis that examined the following variables: urban sprawl, urban decay, environmental degradation, exposure to crime and violence, and urban segregation. Each of these variables encompasses various indicators to gather data, which were then mapped for analysis. This approach enabled us to clearly identify socio-spatial inequities and their components.

Nonetheless, it's crucial to recognize that Mexican border cities face distinctive circumstances due to their proximity to the world's largest economy, the United States of America. This proximity introduces unique dynamics and considerations that further shape the urban landscape and its associated challenges. In this context, our research identifies processes and patterns of structural violence and spatial (in)justice within the geopolitical conditions of border regions, significantly influencing the social production of habitable urban spaces. By doing so, we aim to deconstruct the abstract notion of the right to the city and explore alternative housing production practices in Ciudad Juárez.

Structural Violence, Housing Production, Ciudad Juárez
Urban Inequalities, Geographic Information Systems

Socio-Spatial Injustice: Analysis and registration of its manifestations in Barrio Sinaí

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Inequalities perpetuated and normalized over time are consolidated as manifestations of injustice with both material and symbolic implications that especially affect people living in informal settlements, due to the permanence over time of structural problems (in economic, social, environmental, and political matters). Also, the lack of institutional support, as well as collective imaginaries, result in shortcomings in terms of access to the benefits of the city.

These inequalities increase the social and economic gap between social strata and due to these and other conditions. Some people resort to informal labor, migration or building in non-recommended places, in order to satisfy their basic food and shelter needs.

On this premise, we came with the question: "How are socio-spatial (in)justices manifested in informal settlements, taking into consideration social, economic, environmental and political dimensions?" This led to the development of a study in Barrio Sinaí, an informal settlement in the outskirts of San Jose, the capital of Costa Rica. It was based on a theoretical framework that articulates the structural and systemic approaches that determine social and spatial relations. These concepts and ideas, on the approach to inequalities, allowed us to understand and analyze the complex processes and dynamics that underlie socio-spatial injustice in an integral manner.

Based on the initial findings, an analytical framework was created which made it

possible to obtain a graphic-narrative register containing findings about injustices in the community. This analytical framework was

subdivided into four dimensions and its manifestations of socio-spatial injustice -which are identify in parentheses-: social dimension (socio spatial segregation), economic dimension (economic exclusion), environmental dimension (socio environmental degradation), and political dimension (misrepresentation) along with a cross-cutting gender focus. Additionally, it was structured based on multiple qualitative criteria (for example variables such as: spatial behavior patterns, housing conditions, self-management strategies, citizen participation, among others, and sub-variables

such as: public infrastructure, overcrowding, water resource management, political omission, etc.)

To apply the analytical framework in the community, a series of information gathering instruments were built, including structured interviews, non-participant observation, site analysis, documentary review, collective mapping, among others. The implementation of the analytical framework in Barrio Sinaí provided an opportunity to identify how injustices are manifested materially and symbolically. Our instrument could be adjusted for use in other communities by multiple stakeholders and enable, for example, the implementation of improvement initiatives, or territorial management decisions.

Informal Settlements, Analytical Framework, Manifestations
of Injustice, Community Assessment

ACADEMIC
16:25-17:25
ONLINE

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Spatial Justice and Education Equity: Analysing the Factors Shaping Basic Education Access in São Paulo

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Ensuring equitable and inclusive education is widely recognized as a priority at policy agendas (United Nations General Assembly, 2015), but providing a proper distribution of resources to guarantee universal access to schools is a complex task. This challenge is closely tied to the arrangement of transport networks and to the spatial distributions of population (demand) and educational amenities (supply). In Brazil, the matter of access to opportunities (including education) accounts solely for the transportation component (Pereira et al., 2022) or applies a place-based methodology between capacity of and competition for resources (Moreno-Monroy, Lovelace & Ramos, 2018).

To advance the discussion in the field and present a local-scale analysis of accessibility, I explore to what extent the spatial distributions of supply and demand hinders equity on basic education access in the city of São Paulo, given a multimodal mobility environment. This research addresses the questions of: (i) where is the gap in access to basic education, (ii) how do the transport network and supply-demand factors impact accessibility and (iii) who bears the most significant effects of educational accessibility inequalities.

A multi-dimensional approach is required to measure access to education regarding transportation features, school enrollment and demographic patterns. The “Two-Step Floating Catchment Area” (2SFCA) method is a spatial analysis originally developed to evaluate inequalities on health care services and, since then, it has been applied in urban planning and amenity access issues (Chen & Jia, 2019). As Wang (2014) presents, the 2SFCA results are intuitively

interpreted as a composed ratio of supply-demand, in which a larger value in a spatial unit represents better (or greater probability of) access to the amenities under analysis. From the distribution of probabilities, I will estimate a Lorentz curve and Gini indexes (its traditional aspatial form as well as its spatial variant, proposed by Rey & Smith (2013)). Those methods are able to spatially and statistically evaluate whether the inequality of education access is systematic or not. Besides that, understanding how the accessibility levels vary across groups and territories is fundamental to ensure equitable and inclusive education. Regarding existent income disparities and race segregation, an intersectional discussion will be provided to answer if the gap on education access is concentrated on specific groups, which could be a mechanism that perpetuates and reinforces inequalities (Pereira et al., 2019).

The critical challenge in ensuring equitable and inclusive access to educational amenities lies in overcoming socioeconomic and spatial disparities, especially in complex cities such as São Paulo. To promote spatial justice and egalitarian distribution of opportunities, effective resource allocation is needed. By localizing areas and people with poor access to educational services, evidence-based and targeted interventions on amenities provision (e.g. improvements on transport connectivity or the increase of supply of schools/openings) can be designed by policy makers.

Educational Equity, Access to Education, Distributive
Justice, Transportation Networks, Intersectionality

Introducing Equity in the Planning of Bicycle Lanes

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Addressing the urgent climate crisis has driven a profound shift towards environmental sustainability in urban development. This transformation has led to a heightened focus on reducing pollution and greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, recognized as key contributors to global warming. Consequently, urban transport planning has prioritized cleaner modes of transportation, notably cycling, as a means to reduce car dependency and GHG emissions. However, this intense emphasis on environmental concerns has inadvertently marginalized equity considerations, a vital facet of social sustainability. Cities are characterized by intricate and multifaceted inequalities that tend to worsen with urban expansion. Transport infrastructure can either perpetuate or ameliorate these inequalities, underscoring the importance of an integrated approach to urban transport planning that addresses both GHG emission reduction and equity concerns. This necessitates a departure from the utilitarian principles that traditionally underpin policy-making. This research endeavors to initiate the integration of equity into transport planning by examining the trade-offs that arise when seeking to maximize the number of cyclists while accounting for equity considerations. The central research question is: “How does the inclusion of equity affect the development of bicycle infrastructure?”; This question is explored through an analysis of the Grand Paris Metropolis in France, serving as a representative case study. The study combines the automated gap detection methodology developed by Vybornova (2022) with equity criteria devised by Yap (2021) and Jafino (2021). This integration enables the identification of priority areas for future bicycle infrastructure development based on the degree of emphasis placed on equity. Vulnerable populations are integrat-

ed into the analysis, focusing on two commuting scenarios: children commuting to school and adults commuting to work. These scenarios were selected based on research indicating that cycling infrastructure is most effective in reducing GHG emissions when used for commuting purposes. Vulnerable populations, in this context, include children living in neighborhoods with lower average educational attainment and adults residing in neighborhoods characterized by lower median income. The findings reveal that incorporating equity considerations influences the prioritization of infrastructure projects without fundamentally altering the existing hierarchy. Regardless of the scenario or equity emphasis, the most critical gaps requiring attention are situated along the main ring road encircling Paris, followed by the lengthy road connections linking suburbs to this ring road. The introduction of equity variables leads to the reordering of some smaller gaps on the ring road, prioritizing larger gaps in outlying areas, often in neighborhoods with lower median income. This subtle shift in priorities, even with the inclusion of equity considerations, is promising, suggesting that only some adjustments to current transport planning approaches are required to integrate equity and better serve underprivileged communities. In conclusion, this research holds two key implications: Quantitative models can have unintended adverse societal consequences, underscoring the importance of scientists and modelers considering the broader societal impacts of their work. Elevating vulnerable populations from disadvantaged circumstances aligns with utilitarian objectives, the prevailing norm in policy-making. Thus, this study urges policy-makers to accord equity the attention it deserves in their decision-making processes.

Transport Planning, Cycling Infrastructure, Grand Paris Metropolis, Social Vulnerability. Environmental Sustainability

Spatial justice for food security in São Paulo

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Spatial justice for food security in São Paulo, Brazil, is a critical concern in the discourse surrounding sustainable food systems. Achieving Food and Nutritional Security and Health Promotion hinges on ensuring equal and equitable access to quality food establishments. However, the spatial issue of providing equal access to quality food remains unresolved in large cities, presenting a challenge in urban areas. This spatial injustice has been categorized scientifically as “food deserts” and “food swamps.” Food deserts refer to areas with a shortage of stores selling fresh foods, while food swamps are characterized by an abundance of stores selling ultra-processed products.

Spatial justice, as defined by Soja (2009), involves the fair and equitable distribution of socially valued resources and opportunities in space. Recent studies in São Paulo, the largest city in Brazil, have shown that peripheral regions, predominantly inhabited by low-income communities, can be classified as food deserts, while business and corporate regions are identified as food swamps.

Addressing spatial injustice can be achieved through various means, including public policies, government actions, academic research, and grassroots social initiatives. Urban agriculture, as practiced in São Paulo, plays a role in combating spatial food inequalities by converting underutilized urban spaces into productive vegetable gardens.

A qualitative study conducted in São Paulo examined how urban gardens contribute to a consumer food environment that enhances access to healthy and adequate food. The research encompassed five urban gardens in different parts of the city, spanning areas with varying Human

Development Index (HDI). The study found that urban gardens positively impact their neighborhoods by facilitating access to natural and ecological foods. This access extends to both affluent and lower-income areas, influencing dietary habits and increasing vegetable consumption. Additionally, urban gardens follow ecological principles, enabling low-income individuals to access higher-value produce.

In this context, urban gardens are regarded as food environments that promote health and well-being. Gardeners' efforts to create appealing spaces foster changes in consumption and mindset among visitors while nurturing trust-based relationships between consumers and producers.

Spatial Justice, Food Security, Food Deserts, Urban Agriculture, Consumer Food Environment

Towards a Mobility Just City: The Taiwan Pedestrian Rights Movement

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Urban mobility is a pivotal aspect of urban planning, drawing significant attention in both theory and practice. However, despite global efforts to transform urban landscapes, many cities worldwide continue to grapple with the adverse consequences of car-dominated environments. Taiwan, a rapidly growing and urbanizing country in East Asia, has made significant progress in various cultural, social, and political aspects in recent years. Notable movements like the “Sunflower student movement” and the legalization of same-sex marriage have marked its journey. Nevertheless, at the city scale, Taiwan faces challenges related to outdated urban design and a flawed mobility system that hinders its path toward a more sustainable, inclusive, and just city.

A pivotal moment, known as “Vision Zero Taiwan,” occurred on August 20, 2023, with the launch of Taiwan’s first Pedestrian Rights Parade. In 2022, Taiwan earned international notoriety as a “living hell for pedestrians.” This label shed light on Taiwan’s historic neglect of pedestrian rights on its streets. Over the past decade, the grim statistics have spoken for themselves, with an annual toll of 2,000-3,000 lives lost in traffic accidents, equating to an agonizing average of eight daily deaths. In response to this grim reality, civil society and authorities initiated a significant paradigm shift. Notably, this was a decentralized civil movement, organized by a coalition of netizens, social media influencers, parent participation education associations, and civil experts, driving a grassroots co-creation movement aimed at rewriting the rules.

This article delves deeply into Taiwan’s ongoing pedestrian rights movement and its poten-

tial to reshape the future. The introduction section provides a comprehensive overview of the pervasive injustice within Taiwan’s mobility infrastructure environment. The subsequent literature review contextualizes the study within the framework of a “just city.” Through in-depth interviews, valuable insights are gained into the motivations of key players and their unique contributions to this transformative movement. These interview findings are then analyzed within the context of the “just city” framework introduced in the literature review. Finally, the article aims to conclude with reflections on the potential implications and lessons that other cities can draw upon, offering inspiration for the reimagining and reorganizing of equitable mobility environments in the foreseeable future.

Vision Zero, Co-creation, Just City, Inclusive Mobility,
Taiwan

Assessing EU Policy Framework for Spatial Distributive and Procedural Justice

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Achieving climate and a just transition through the implementation of the European Green Deal (EGD) necessitates inclusive decision-making and active citizen participation. However, there is limited understanding of the EGD's effectiveness in promoting experimental governance processes at the local level. In this context, our study draws upon an interdisciplinary debate on spatial and environmental justice to critically examine the operational framework of EU policies, highlighting their potential strengths and weaknesses in realizing a spatially and procedurally just transition.

To address this, we initially provide an overview of the policies and initiatives defining the objectives, methodologies, and tools for EGD implementation at the local level. Subsequently, we delve into the EU Mission on 'Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities' as a key case study to evaluate the effectiveness of the EU's operational framework in facilitating democratic innovation and achieving the EGD's just transition goals at the local level. While this mission opens up avenues for citizens' participation and engagement of private stakeholders in local planning processes, it lacks clear criteria and methods for assessing democratic outcomes.

To fill this gap, we analyze the mission's guidelines using insights from the broader academic literature on 'just transition' and 'democratic innovation.' We identify key ambiguities and challenges within this framework, particularly concerning the integration of distributive, procedural, and recognition spatial justice concerns. Our aim is to contribute both theoretically and practically to understanding how the EGD's local implementation can effec-

tively foster democratic innovation, reconsider existing tools, and pave the way for a more equitable and inclusive transition.

We have identified three main gaps and limitations in the current approach versus our proposed conceptual approach to support a new line of interdisciplinary actions for achieving spatial procedural justice. Firstly, we emphasize the need to analyze the innovation in participation and deliberation practices within specific contexts and considering outcomes from different actors' perspectives. Secondly, there is a call for integrated monitoring and evaluations of democratic processes, incorporating both participatory and deliberative practices and the role of technological tools. Lastly, we stress the importance of assessing the EGD's implementation through a site-specific approach, accounting for governance differences between cities, the capacity-building of involved stakeholders, and the implications for planning actions. The risk of climate-oriented practices exacerbating gaps with traditional planning actions remains significant. While European climate policies offer potential for innovation and democratic inclusion, our goal is to highlight knowledge gaps that hinder a comprehensive assessment of their actual achievements in local planning practices.

European Green Deal, Just Transition, Democratic Innovation, Procedural Justice, Climate Policies

ACADEMIC

16:25-17:25

ONLINE

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Developing a Social Justice Assessment Tool for Public Green Spaces of Istanbul

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Urban green spaces serve as essential components for promoting social and environmental sustainability within cities. They contribute to enhancing social well-being and conserving natural resources. However, the planning, execution, and management of these public spaces are intricate tasks, often entailing multifaceted challenges. From the standpoint of urban justice, various issues may lead to injustices in these areas, including disparities in quality, distribution, and accessibility, the presence of exclusionary elements, inadequate facilities, and more. Achieving and preserving justice within urban green spaces requires a comprehensive approach capable of addressing the diverse needs of different population groups.

Scholars from various disciplines, including social sciences, health sciences, and architecture, engage in discussions regarding justice in public spaces. These conversations have given rise to a burgeoning justice literature characterized by diverse definitions, evolving principles, and various measurement methods. In this body of literature, concepts of environmental, spatial, and social justice, often interconnected and overlapping, are associated with urban green spaces. The theoretical framework of Social Justice developed by Setha Low serves as the foundation for this study, offering a multi-dimensional structure for evaluating public spaces. This model encompasses six social justice dimensions and features indicators designed to address well-defined justice concerns. These dimensions include the redistribution of resources, recognition and acceptance of differences, encouragement of social interactions, care for others and the repair

of space, participation in procedural processes, and the provision of adequate information and signage. A comprehensive consideration of all these dimensions is indispensable for ensuring social justice in urban green spaces. Istanbul, as Turkey's most populous and complex city, possesses unique social, economic, and demographic dynamics. However, it is evident that the justice literature pertaining to urban green areas in Istanbul is rather limited. Consequently, the primary motivation of this study is to develop a multi-dimensional justice assessment tool specifically tailored for urban green spaces in Istanbul. The research comprises two distinct sections. Initially, the goal is to explore the relationship between urban green spaces and the dimensions of social justice. In this context, two analytical models designed for evaluating these dimensions, namely the "Ecological Model of Environmental Justice" and the "Classification of Institutional Barriers of Urban Green Spaces," have been adapted as analytical methods for research on Istanbul's social justice. Subsequently, the aim is to initiate a discourse on social justice within public spaces in Istanbul, focusing on addressing contemporary issues guided by the dimensions of justice. In this regard, academic sources, newspapers, and social media platforms have been examined with regard to the topic.

The study developed a multi-dimensional social justice assessment tool for urban green spaces, tested through an Istanbul case study, serving as a guide for promoting justice among stakeholders.

Social justice, Urban green spaces, Istanbul, Green Infrastructure

Smart Cities or Smart Neighborhoods?

The case studies of three South American Smart Cities

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This research explores the concept of the Smart City through a lens of social inclusion in Buenos Aires, Montevideo, and Santiago de Chile. It aimed to analyze the impact of Smart City initiatives on social inclusion by examining the spatial distribution of Smart City outcomes within cities and observing relationships between these distributions and socio-economic realities. It analyzes the extent to which Smart City policies reflect and exacerbate realities of splintering urbanism and rising inequality. Observed differences in the literature between Smart City rhetoric and observed realities implied a need for empirical research into this topic. This research attempted to address this gap in the research by constructing a Smart City Composite Index that assessed the variability of outcomes within the chosen cities, and geo-processing indicators of Smart City policy outcomes to analyze the spatial distribution of these outcomes. This was then analyzed against the spatial distribution of multi-dimensional poverty in the chosen cities and used as a proxy for social inclusion. The research found that Smart City policy outcomes are often unequally distributed through cities, with business and historical centers prioritized over residential areas, indicating that Smart City focuses on a knowledge economy and global markets rather than reducing inequalities. It also found that in Montevideo and Santiago, there is a negative and significant relationship between Smart City outcomes and multidimensional poverty, which is taken to imply that the outcomes of Smart City policies are conditioned by the previous socio-economic levels of neighborhoods, which confirms previous findings of path dependency in the literature. It is argued in the research that SC

policies do entail splintering urbanism based on pre-existing inequalities. It is recommended that in order to prevent this in the future, SC policies should explicitly incorporate equity and reducing inequality into the goals of the policy.

Smart City, Social inclusion, Spatial distribution, Multi-dimensional poverty

Redefining Urban Safety: Exploring Gender Intersectionality and Temporality in Young Women's Experiences of Urban Spaces

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My PhD research project focuses on analysing gender-based violence and urban safety in the lives of young women living in middle-class and low-class districts of Córdoba, Argentina. This research examines how intersecting social factors such as gender, age, and living environment influence young women's perceptions of urban safety and their strategies to enhance it in the context of gender-based violence. In this presentation, I will discuss the gender dimension of spatial justice in conjunction with age and social class.

The presentation is based on preliminary results from a 16-month fieldwork conducted in Argentina between 2017 and 2022. The empirical data comprises 36 qualitative semi-structured interviews, including 29 with girls and young women below 30 years old, and 7 with experts and activists in urban planning and women's rights. Additionally, the dataset includes 430 visual documents depicting daily urban life in Córdoba and ethnographic materials gathered through participatory observations at the non-governmental organisation CISCSA from 2017 to 2022.

My research initially aimed to identify how girls and young women utilise urban spaces and define safe or unsafe areas. However, during the analysis of in-depth interviews and ethnographic data, the binary division between safe and unsafe urban spaces was challenged. The boundaries between what participants deemed safe and threatening were found to be blurred and context-dependent. The feminist mobilisations in Argentina, such as the Ni Una Menos movement and the social struggle for reproductive rights, played a significant role in shaping young women's perceptions of gender-based

violence in cities. As a result, the existing framework of safe versus unsafe spaces became inadequate to explore these complex processes, given the scale of violence against women and the impact of feminist interventions.

In my presentation, I will propose a new analytical approach that shifts from a binary understanding of safe and unsafe spaces to a more complex examination of risk management and negotiating visibility. This approach focuses on how girls and young women navigate urban risks and their visibility in public spaces. It also incorporates the dimension of time into the analysis, acknowledging the changing and evolving nature of urban safety experienced by these women. Time operates on two levels: the impact of life course events on safety perceptions and the significance of specific, context-driven moments in time for gendered experiences of fear and safety in cities. This fresh perspective holds promise for more intricate research on spatial justice and urban safety.

Gender-based violence, Urban safety, Gender intersectionality, Feminist mobilisations

Socio-spatial resilience in the Indian city: the case of Newtown, Rajarhat

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The advent of globalization in the 1990s brought about significant transformations in the Indian subcontinent, permeating the daily politics, practices, and spatial configurations of its cities. This wave of globalization not only introduced a dominant hegemonic worldview but also gave rise to a counter-culture that actively resisted these dominant ideologies. This counter-culture often manifested through urban practices that were often stigmatized as public nuisances by both the State and the market. Central to this research is the question of whether the spatial arrangements that emerge from these 'public nuisance-based urban practices' have the potential to foster socio-spatial inclusion. The study further delves into the intricate web of interdependencies between social groups labeling these practices as nuisances and those who actively engage in these resistant practices. With a clear emphasis on amplifying the voices of marginalized urban populations, this research project serves as a starting point for broader discussions on socio-spatial justice and inclusivity.

The research primarily centers on the case of Newtown, Rajarhat, a new town conceived during the post-liberalization era and now designated as a 'global city.' In recent times, Newtown Rajarhat has experienced a surge in evictions targeting homeless individuals, auto-constructed dwellings of construction laborers, street hawkers, and local vendors from neighboring urban villages. These evictions are orchestrated to make way for more formalized public space projects, which, crucially, do not cater to the displaced communities. The study embarks on an extensive exploration of the concept of public nuisance in this context, aiming to comprehend

what is classified as a nuisance and the underlying reasons. This investigation is particularly relevant in a city like Kolkata, where the tolerance for public nuisance appears to be higher compared to other cities. Moreover, the research aspires to shed light on whether the global ambitions of Kolkata's urban elites have led to a diminished social acceptance of public nuisance. The research methodology involves the collection of data through semi-structured interviews and the acquisition of insights from Resident Welfare Association (RWA) social media groups based in Newtown.

A critical approach to understanding the city from the vantage point of public nuisance and the evolving dynamics of urban culture emerges as a driving force in the production of a global city. Furthermore, this research is poised to make significant contributions to unraveling the intricacies of the politics surrounding the aestheticization of public spaces and the cultural dynamics that evolve within this transformative landscape.

Globalization, Urbanization, Public Nuisance, Socio-spatial Inclusion, Resistance, Global City, Kolkata

Spatial justice indicators centred on the body-space perspective

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The concept of the built territory was originally conceived to serve communities and address the social and spatial needs of its inhabitants. However, the models of spatial and social territory have often used an idealized human figure as their metrical and conceptual reference, a figure that does not accurately represent the diversity of human attributes. This reference to an idealized human has led to the materialization of urban utopian paradigms. The diverse anatomical features, abilities, and (dis)abilities of human beings make it impossible to fit them into these standards. As a result, cities and territories have been deeply influenced by this reference figure, creating what Beck Rails (1998) refers to as an “apartheid architecture,” not based on racial prejudices but on the security and needs of “productive elites.” Such territories, designed for a specific idealized figure, have reinforced inaccessibility and dependency, limiting freedom, identity, autonomy, and independence.

The advent of powered transport modes has added complexity to this process, presenting new challenges, claiming space, and introducing new metrics and infrastructural demands. In response to these issues, contemporary reflections and strategic documents on public policies and urban planning emphasize the need to re-humanize the territory, with a focus on sustainability, resilience, and inclusion. International agendas and conventions also call for the reinterpretation of the human figure, acknowledging its diversity and specific needs, especially in terms of accessibility. Human accessibility, regardless of physical, sensory, neurodiversity, and communication characteristics, significantly affects fundamental rights, the Right to the City, and spatial justice.

Despite the progress made in developing methodologies and tools for monitoring the Sustainable Development Goals, there is a notable absence of indicators that relate to the space-body dimension. Additionally, there is a lack of a universal accessibility certification model. These gaps have compromised the effectiveness of spatial inclusion and spatial justice indicators in cities and territories. These shortcomings are further exacerbated by the absence of clarity around fundamental concepts, such as “spatial justice,” “universal accessibility,” and “inclusive territories.”

To address these challenges, the research introduces the concept of “inclusive territories,” which aims to achieve structured urban planning through “universal accessibility” and “spatial justice.” Two complementary tools are being developed for this purpose. First, an analytical framework of spatial justice and inclusion indicators, focusing on the body-space perspective, will be applicable to the planning and management of cities and territories, along with methodologies for their implementation and monitoring. Second, a universal accessibility certification model will be created and correlated with the framework. The ultimate goal is to provide a methodological tool that promotes public policies fostering a more spatially just environment, designed with a focus on sustainability, prosperity, and socio-territorial cohesion.

Built Environment, Inclusive Territories, Universal Accessibility, Sustainable Development Goals

ACADEMIC

16:25-17:25

ONLINE

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Marka Camp (Jordan): An Evolving Definition of Refugee Camp and Hosting City. Employing Mental Mapping Dissecting the Conceived, Lived, and Perceived Spaces.

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Refugee camps, as defined by UNHCR, are established as temporary facilities to offer immediate protection and assistance to individuals compelled to leave their homes due to war, persecution, or violence. However, the extended presence of displaced populations in these facilities has transformed refugee camps into continuously evolving socio-spatial entities, surpassing the fixed definitions associated with them. This evolution extends beyond the conventional notion of refugee camps as spaces of exception, as proposed by Agamben. Over the years, the development of refugee camps has become closely intertwined with the development of their host cities. This complex relationship necessitates a continual reevaluation of the definition of these camps as temporary settings.

In the context of Jordan, more than 2,000,000 Palestine refugees sought refuge after the 1948 and 1967 events, constituting approximately 40% of the total registered refugees across UNRWA's five fields. Nearly 20% of these Palestine refugees reside in one of the ten official camps in the country. Various governance dynamics have contributed to the transformation of many Palestine refugee camps in Jordan into spatial agents deeply integrated into the overall spatial structure of their hosting cities. Despite this evolution, the roles and significance of refugee camps in these cities are often overlooked and receive limited consideration in national decision-making processes. This research endeavors to shed light on the refugee camps' central role as developmental hubs in the region.

To achieve this objective, the study focuses on unraveling the co-evolving definitions of refugee camps and their hosting cities. Specif-

ically, it employs the method of mental mapping to investigate the perceptual definition of Marka camp and Russeifa, its hosting city. The study involves the participation of eighty key informants residing in either the camp or the city, ensuring gender balance, and selecting individuals born between 1950 and 2000.

Participants from both groups are asked to define the borders of the camp and the city, including key landmarks. The study subsequently compares these findings against the official borders of the two spaces established by the state and humanitarian organizations such as the United Nations. By doing so, it reconstructs the scale of conceived, lived, and perceived space, as understood through the lens of Henri Lefebvre, within both the city and the camp. The study goes further by connecting the perceived definitions of the camp and the city with their officially established borders. This comparative approach allows for the empirical delineation of the actual extent of the camp and city domains. Furthermore, it aims to explore the level of spatial interconnectivity between these two settings. This investigation aligns with the primary focus of the ongoing doctoral study, which is dedicated to unraveling the spatial agency of the refugee camp.

In conclusion, the research interprets its findings and conducts comparisons based on the gender of the respondents and their place of residence, aligning this narrative with Henri Lefebvre's concepts of spatial representation and experience.

Refugee Camps, Spatial Evolution, Hosting Cities,
Palestine, Mental Mapping

Landscapes of Inequality: Exploring the Determinants of the Urban Landscape that Perpetuates Inequality in Southern Madrid

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The contemporary urban landscape, once a mechanism for social integration, is grappling with an increase in territorial inequality within globalized metropolises. This inequality is the result of complex interactions between economic, social, environmental, and natural systems, which should ideally contribute to the well-being of urban inhabitants. However, the urban landscape has inadvertently become an agent of inequality, most acutely observed in vulnerable urban areas. This shift has been propelled by unplanned processes and actions informed by traditional academic and practical divisions among disciplines like architecture, engineering, urban planning, and landscape architecture. The prevailing conceptual disconnect among these disciplines fails to address the essential interrelation and complementarity needed to counter urban socio-spatial segregation and environmental imbalances. To rectify this issue, an integrative perspective is imperative. This perspective, along with its methods and tools, seeks to bridge these disciplinary gaps and facilitate a comprehensive understanding of the urban landscape's role in perpetuating or mitigating inequality. This research endeavors to establish a methodology for analyzing and diagnosing the patterns of inequality within the urban landscape. While significant progress has been made in developing methodologies and indicators for evaluating urban inequalities, there is a dearth of emphasis on understanding the causal relationship between these disparities and the components of the urban landscape. In this context, the research provides an analytical framework to explore the intricate relationship between inequality (both urban and environmental dimensions) and the urban landscape (both physical and social dimensions). The

approach involves a comprehensive exploration of various components of the urban landscape, assessing their impact on existing inequalities within urban areas. By defining and evaluating specific indicators, the research aims to pinpoint the variables in the urban landscape that contribute to perpetuating inequality and assess the magnitude of their impact. Through this analysis and diagnosis methodology, the goal is to create a versatile tool that can be applied to different urban areas to formulate strategies and policies aimed at mitigating the consequences arising from the growing inequality within cities. The case study for this research is situated in the Region of Madrid, particularly in the urban territory of the Southeast. Madrid is notable for its high levels of segregation and social inequality when compared to other European capitals. Within the Region of Madrid, clear disparities exist between the North and South, with the South housing the most vulnerable areas, according to parameters established by the Vulnerability Atlas of the Ministry of Development. This makes the Southern region of Madrid a critical area for the development of methodologies for analyzing and monitoring inequalities within the urban landscape. Methodologically, the research proposes the creation of an Atlas, which serves as a visual and quantitative tool for assessing sector-specific issues and aids in prioritization and decision-making through a multi-criteria evaluation. By constructing a landscape Atlas as an analytical and research tool for urban conditions, the aim is to shift the focus toward a more comprehensive understanding of the city as a network of networks, employing methodologies that scrutinize the morphotypological and topological aspects of the urban landscape.

Urban Landscape, Inequality, Case Study, Madrid, Atlas

Addressing Climate Equity Concerns and Environmental Justice in Urban Planning through Citizen Science

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The relentless expansion of the global economy, driven by an ever-increasing population, has placed a substantial environmental burden on the planet, resulting in growing conflicts over the distribution of resources. Disturbingly, the consequences of climate change disproportionately affect societies least responsible for its causes. These marginalised communities, often lacking the resources and capacities to address climate-related hazards, face profound social and environmental inequities. Meanwhile, those contributing most to climate change tend to possess the means to mitigate its impacts. This research aims to tackle the pressing issues of climate equity, environmental justice, and social inclusion. Central to this approach is the development of a climate equity assessment framework, bolstered by robust public participation, with the goal of fairly allocating resources among communities and identifying the most vulnerable groups. A significant challenge in addressing climate equity lies in the absence of comprehensive, localised models and a well-defined set of indicators to effectively map disparities. Furthermore, the lack of suitable and accessible datasets for localised decision-making underscores the importance of incorporating citizen science methodologies. The primary objective of this study is to localise the United Nations Sustainable Development Goal 11 (SDG 11), “Make cities and human settlements inclusive, safe, resilient, and sustainable,” as a cornerstone for addressing climate equity within urban planning. This involves leveraging citizen science to map vulnerabilities and facilitate participatory decision-making. The research outlines four key objectives that delineate three distinct research phases, forming

the research methodology. The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) provide a robust framework complete with indicators relevant to climate equity concerns. The research utilises the SDG India Index developed by NITI Aayog, which focuses on implementing and measuring SDGs at the state level. The study emphasises the critical importance of localising SDGs to effectively combat climate change and enhance resilience. The United Nations roadmap for localising SDGs highlights the central role of public participation and democratic accountability in driving this process. Through the integration of citizen science, stakeholders, and communities, this research aims to comprehensively map vulnerable communities, monitor SDG progress, and promote sustainable development at the local level.

The expected outcome of this research is a robust framework for monitoring and implementing localised SDGs through citizen science and collaborative platforms. This framework not only addresses climate equity concerns in urban planning but also enhances the capacities of both formal and informal institutions, promotes governance convergence, and provides spatial strategies for climate change adaptation. Viewed through the lens of spatial justice, this framework recognises the significance of equitable access to resources and opportunities in various urban locations. Integrated spatial justice principles into conventional planning processes, this assessment will serve as a critical layer for identifying challenges and prioritising solutions based on assessment findings.

Climate Equity, Citizen Science, Sustainable Development Goals, Environmental Justice

A vocabulary of spatial justice in practice- migrants' engagement with space in Kolkata and Perth

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Migration, as a spatial event, is embedded in the concept of Spatial Justice. People move from one space to another in aspiration of spatial justice. This is because of a lack of either or both distributive (opportunities, demographic, social, and sociological parameters) and recognitive justice (aspiration) at places of origin which propels out migration to places of destination. However, a significant body of literature holds testimony to spatial injustice in places of destination. The question that then needs to be answered is how migrants ensure spatial justice is achieved in places of destination. Or, alternatively, despite the absence of spatial justice, why do migrants continue to live at the destination.

The research attempts to answer these questions by taking up the case of migrants in the cities of Kolkata and Perth. Done by using ethnographic method, the research focuses on urban practices of forced migrants to achieve spatial justice. It uses the term 'migrants' engagement with space' as a method to understand spatial justice in practice. Here, engagement with space is theoretically situated within the triad of conceived, perceived, and lived spaces, where conceived is the cognitive conception of the space by migrants, perceived is the embodied perception in space, and lived is the production of meanings from the first two and its translation into practices in space. While the last one is more measurable, it is imperative to know that it is propelled by the first two. By documenting ethnographic accounts of migrants' everyday life in Perth and Kolkata, the paper further focuses on comparative research to create a vocabulary of spatial jus-

tice in practice. The research brings out the comparative element by creating a vocabulary of practices common to migrants in both cities.

However, based on differences in the contextual realities of the two cities, how purposive, reflexive, mutating, hinged, imitative, and temporal are individually and collectively analyzed and understood as processes of migrants' engagement with space is shown. Thus, further showing that the capitalist spaces of destination do provide opportunities of resistance, negotiating, appropriation, and engagements which in turn keep the struggle for spatial justice alive.

Migration, Ethnographic Research, Urban Practices
Conceived Perceived and Lived Spaces, Comparative Analysis

Transforming Urban Mobility for equitable and sustainable streets for all

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The mobility sector has demonstrated its contributions to sustainable and digital transitions when justice at different levels, accessibility and inclusivity among different social groups, environmental practices and security are achievable. Riding a bicycle, walking or using e-scooters can activate individual responsibility to a collective scale, increasing participation and co-creation in the decision-making process. To be out on the streets, moving or performing other activities, means to be socially interacting and engaging with diversity: this leads to an increased sense of membership, sense of influence, sense of integration. Such engagement increases levels of trust, the fulfilment of needs, emotional connections to places and people. JUST STREETS aims to transform established mobility narratives that take for granted that streets are for motorized traffic. The project we aim to present, called JUST STREETS, is part of Horizon Europe and is set to start in January 2024. Backed by a consortium of 30 partners spanning 17 countries, JUST STREETS seeks to challenge car-centric mobility narratives in cities, advocating for the promotion of walking, cycling and other active modes of mobility. The objective of JUST STREETS is to re-shape street infrastructures and induce behavioural change in mobility across 8 pilots, 4 follower and 12 twinning European cities, which have been chosen by their heavily reliance on private vehicles. The project will proactively share the generated “how-to-do-it” to facilitate rapid replication throughout Europe and Haifa (Israel). In close collaboration with citizens, policymakers, experts, and interest groups, JUST STREETS will not only develop a new vision

of spatial justice where streets become public spaces for social interaction for all, but equally important find ways to rapidly implement changes. A strong focus is on displaying how necessary transformations in the face of climate change can (and must) successfully improve social justice, accessibility, inclusivity, and security as mitigation strategies along the way. By prioritizing marginalized social groups and vulnerable mobility users who have traditionally been underrepresented in decision-making urban processes, JUST STREETS aims to reshape the dominant narrative of mobility centered around the needs of white cis-hetero men. To do so, spatial analysis, ethnography, visualizations, and simulations serve as methods to frame active users’ mobility needs and envision 3D scenarios of just and sustainable streets. Findings and strategies will be tested and validated in the project’s cities through various methods including video data collection and GIS analysis. Subsequently, the evaluation and impact assessment of alternative streets and mobilities will be calculated through interviews, questionnaires, field-observations and the employment of Environmental System Analysis tools to co-create context-specific strategies. Additionally, effective communication and dissemination strategies will be employed, incorporating policy recommendation and exploitation of results.

For the symposium, the JUST STREETS philosophy and foundational theories will be presented, with a focus on how social justice can be included in sustainable mobility planning and in shaping the streets of the future, granting equal access and usability for all, according to diverse needs and capabilities.

Mobility Sector, Spatial Justice, Sustainable Mobility, Active Modes, Social Inclusion

ACADEMIC

17:35-18:35

ONLINE

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Future Scenarios; rethinking spatial injustice and EU territorial inequalities

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In principle, the European Union (EU) upholds the aim of providing its citizens with equal rights and opportunities. However, the reality is that the ability of European citizens to enjoy these rights and opportunities is still significantly influenced by their geographical locations.

The IMAJINE project, an initiative funded through Horizon 2020, is a comprehensive research program that delves into issues related to territorial equality and spatial justice across the EU's member states. Nevertheless, this pursuit is complicated by environmental, social, political, and economic uncertainties. These uncertainties imply that the inequalities of the future may not resemble those that can be empirically studied in the present or recent past.

IMAJINE incorporates a foresight component, which involves creating plausible future scenarios for Europe in the year 2048. Each of these scenarios presents a distinct version of territorial inequality and spatial injustices. These scenarios range from a future where climate change and ongoing pandemics have led people to migrate from urban areas and coastlines to rural living, to a scenario where digitalization has given rise to forms of citizenship that are independent of geographical constraints, resulting in inequalities manifesting in virtual spaces.

This paper explores the concept of using imagined futures to gain insight into potential opportunities and threats that go beyond what can be expected, predicted, or extrapolated from the present and the past. It presents the four scenarios generated by the IMAJINE project, illustrating how envisaging potential

futures can provide valuable insights into opportunities and threats that differ from what can be foreseen or extrapolated from the past and the present. Additionally, the paper discusses how these scenarios can be employed to challenge established thinking, allowing individuals to envision a future characterized by inequalities and injustices that may be fundamentally different from those experienced today. Furthermore, it explores the process of constructing meaningful and well-defined scenarios for a broad topic and stakeholder group, emphasizing the need for an effective and time-sensitive scenario development process, particularly in an era marked by multiple concurrent crises.

EU, Territorial Inequalities, Spatial Justice, Future Scenarios, Foresight Analysis

An Understanding of Inequality Through A Comparative Study at City Scale: 'white' area (Vincent) versus 'black' area (Pefferville)

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The study will focus the spatial lens on Pefferville and Vincent, East London, South Africa to reveal the historical and social issues present within South African cities. Cities and towns in South Africa possess a distorted spatial landscape existing as a collection of inappropriately located settlements, pushing the urban poor to the periphery of a town or city. The concern for their weak civic environment evolves from a challenge unique to South Africa: poor production of civic space and civic sensibility, and an undifferentiated, homogenous urban landscape within informal and township settlements.

The main topics of research include Spatial Justice as defined by three elements - Social Justice (Edward Soja), Physical Justice, and Right to the City (Henri Lefebvre). It is within this social and spatial framework and through the lenses of Soja's spatial justice and Henri Lefebvre's notions of the right to the city and its social space that two areas of East London - Pefferville, a removed township in East London, and Vincent, a colonially established neighborhood in the heart of the city are compared. The objective is to highlight the perceived issues within the justice lens which are the absence of public amenities, civic presence, and healthy civic life.

Qualitative data will be collected by means of field notes and observations of the two communities and their nuances. The primary research method that will be used for this study is the observation method to investigate the two urban fabrics and their broader context. It is expected that the research and reflections of observations and intuitions of the two neighborhoods will highlight the planning disparities, macro division, and unequal set-

tlement structures typical of South African cities. Further, it is expected that the study will reveal the unequal distribution and unfair allocation of public amenities. Lastly, it will emphasize the continued civic trauma as a result of invalidation and lack of recognition of the victims of the Group Areas Act

South African Cities, Civic Environment, Urban Inequality
Qualitative Research, Historical Injustice

Spatial Justice and Environmental Inequities: A Multidimensional Exploration of Structured Racism in Cleveland and Detroit's Urban Landscape

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This research investigates the intricate relationship between spatial justice, systemic racism, and environmental inequalities in neighborhoods including Central, Fairfax, and Hough in Cleveland, and Boynton and Delray in Detroit. The aim is to explore and analyze the enduring impacts of systemic racism on planning policies and spatial configurations, highlighting prevailing environmental disparities. By elucidating these disparities, this study proposes avenues for equitable urban development, balancing clarity with comprehensive insight to illuminate paths towards resilient urban futures.

The research, underpinned by an objective to study the ramifications of structured racism on environmental inequalities, employs a blend of qualitative and quantitative methodologies. It investigates neighborhoods predominantly populated by communities of color, primarily African Americans, correlating racial data with environmental justice indices. Employing spatial analysis, intensive fieldwork, and comprehensive interviews with residents, the study unearths discrepancies in environmental conditions, resource allocation, and access to essential urban ecologies and amenities in areas marked by substantial environmental justice burdens, traceable to historical discriminatory practices like redlining and contemporary phenomena like gentrification.

It reveals compelling findings on the lack of green infrastructure, exposure to environmental hazards, and disparities in access to clean water and air, particularly in areas with pronounced vulnerability due to residential segregation and proximity to industrial sites. Such intricate interplays between spatial segregation and environmental conditions in these

neighborhoods manifest starkly in diminished landscape biodiversity, unequal distribution of urban ecological patterns, and prolonged exposure to hazardous materials, culminating in a range of adverse socio-environmental outcomes.

The conclusion of this research provides a valuable contribution to the academic discourse on spatial justice and environmental disparities, instigating a refined contemplation of urban development paradigms to inclusively embody equity and resilience. This study delineates the multifaceted ramifications of structural racism on spatial and environmental constructs within urban contexts, presenting nuanced insights capable of informing equitable urban planning and design reforms. The critical insights and consequential recommendations from this investigation hold the potential to guide measured alterations in spatial strategies, serving to counterbalance prevailing inequalities. By advocating for the principles of environmental and spatial justice, this study aspires to cultivate urban landscapes marked by inherent inclusivity and equity, striving towards the comprehensive improvement of living conditions in communities experiencing racial segregation and environmental detriment

Systemic racism, Environmental disparities, Urban development, Racial segregation

Evaluating Lisbon's Recent Public Space Transformations: A Spatial Justice Perspective

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The recent manual for public space design of Lisbon claims to create “a city accessible for all”. To realize this slogan, Lisbon has invested in improving public spaces to enhance accessibility, attractiveness, and heritage preservation during the last decades as the city grows to be a top touristic destination in Europe. Despite lately facing economic challenges, the significant urban and regional transformations are in order by the municipality especially to promote inclusion, to foster urban planning and local interventions and to attract a younger population (Santos, 2019). Improvement of public spaces in several scales and models was at the center of these policy implementations. Santos (2019) shows the scope of these improvements in three main systems for public open space projects: riverfront (Santos, Cais do Sodré, Ribeira das Naus); the garden and belvedere (Príncipe Real, São Pedro de Alcântara, Portas do Sol, Graça, Senhora do Monte); the street and square (Santa Catarina, Bica, Chiado, Baixa-Rossio, Martim Moniz, Mouraria, Castelo, Alfama).

Today, the underlying motivation of attracting tourists through these projects seems to be resulting in new real estate trends that fired an activism for the right to housing as well as reshaping residential and public spaces. As Lisbon upgrades its spaces, there is always a question of increasing accessibility and quality of life in the city but the question of ‘for whom’? For instance, the Martim Moniz case has been subjected to the discussions of privatization and displacement of real users of the area (Rodrigues, 2014). Public spaces should embrace diversity and welcome “a variety of people with differing cultural views and practices” (Matej & Sezer, 2017). Considering the multi-

culturality of the city and the co-existence of diverse ethnicities, the question of spatial justice arises in the sense of recognition of the specific needs and preferences of different identities. As “there is more to justice than fair distributions” (Pereira et al. 2017), the spatial, cultural and participatory lenses in urban policymaking and design processes are another aspect in the question of spatial justice.

In the context of these discussions, this study aims to analyze the (selected) recent public space projects in Lisbon, centering on the evaluation of their policy documents and practical implementations through the lens of the recognition and procedural dimensions of spatial justice. In Lisbon characterized by urban transformation and evolving socio-demographic dynamics especially for the last two decades, it scrutinizes how these projects impact the equitable distribution of resources, opportunities, and accessibility within the urban landscape from a socio-spatial perspective. Employing a spatial justice framework, the research dissects the implications of these initiatives and their influence on marginalized communities. By exploring the intricate relationship between urban development policies and spatial justice, this analysis provides valuable theoretical insights and recommendations for promoting more equitable public spaces in Lisbon.

Lisbon, Urban transformation, Urban development policies, Socio-spatial perspective, Equity in public spaces

Street Food Vendors under Siege: Reassessing Spatial Justice for Street Vendors in Soi Convent, Bangkok, Thailand.

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Between 2016 and 2018, Bangkok earned accolades as 'The Best City for Street Food' by CNN, emphasizing the centrality of street vendors. Despite this, the same period saw the military government's initiation of the 'reclaiming pavements for pedestrians plan' under Article 44. Ostensibly aiming at urban order, the plan was positioned in opposition to street vending, which the government critiqued as a sign of underdevelopment and disorder.

Historically, Thailand's policies regarding street vendors have shown a pendulum swing. There's a long-standing dualism between viewing them as urban impediments demanding regulation and endorsing them as vital economic balms during crises, as exemplified by the 1979-1982 recession and the 1997 Asian financial crisis.

The core objective of this study is to deeply probe whether the aforementioned plan aptly suits Soi Convent in Bangkok, especially recognized for its street food vendors. The research endeavors to understand the spatial, social, and economic dimensions of street vending in the area. It seeks insights into how street vendors navigate and shape public spaces and to gauge the 'reclaiming pavements for pedestrians plan' based on the area's pedestrian feedback. This is because the data on how street vendors produce their spaces, find their spots, and sustain their businesses might be necessary for Bangkok's new comprehensive plan (2023). As the plan mentions, crediting more FAR (Floor Area Ratio) for those buildings spares the space for street vendors.

Soi Convent, located in Bangkok's central business district, stands out. Unlike areas like Siam Square (Bangkok's shopping area), where the plan's enforcement is explicit, Soi Convent remains in abeyance, rendering it a

unique case study. The region's blend of offices and low to middle-income populace represents a complex urban tableau.

Having Employed questionnaires, interviews, user behavior mapping, and tracking, the research underscores the intricate interplay of street vendors with Soi Convent's urban dynamics. The study avails the Public Cleanliness and Orderliness Act B.E. 2535 (1992) to juxtapose vendor-free Mondays with other days, providing a dynamic to understand urban space utility in the presence or absence of vendors.

While the study recognizes the challenges of waste management and space allocation faced by street vendors, feedback from Soi Convent's daily users, both Thai and foreigners, overwhelmingly supports the necessity of street vendors, emphasizing their role in everyday life and urban vibrancy. Furthermore, as mentioned in the new urban

Conclusively, this research underscores the need for an inclusive strategy, appreciating the multi-faceted roles of street vendors, especially in pivotal urban zones like Soi Convent.

Street vendors, Bangkok, Urban planning, Spatial dynamics
Pedestrian feedback, Urban vibrancy

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ONLINE

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Seeking Spatial Justice in Southern Croatia: Grassroots Initiatives against Privatisation of Public Land

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This contribution delves into the exploration of two grassroots initiatives that have been at the forefront of promoting spatial justice in the southern regions of Croatia for the past two decades. Specifically, it focuses on the Pula Group and the “Srd is Ours” Initiative, both of which emerged as responses to state-imposed policies that advocate for the enclosure and privatisation of valuable publicly owned land along the Croatian coast. These policies have raised concerns about depriving local communities of access to vital spatial resources permanently, a stark contradiction to the principles of spatial justice, as outlined by Soja (2009), emphasising fair and equitable spatial distribution of socially valued resources and opportunities to use them.

These grassroots movements have been instrumental in resisting privatisation efforts and underscoring the importance of considering long-term communal interests when managing spatial resources. As a result, they have engaged in a struggle for spatial justice and achieved significant progress. This research seeks to delve into various aspects of this process. Firstly, it aims to understand how these initiatives conceptualise spatial justice in the context of their activism, examining the tools and strategies they employ, the outcomes they have realised, and the challenges associated with assessing the impact of their efforts.

Additionally, the study explores how local municipal governments respond to state-led spatial policies and the activities and demands of these grassroots initiatives. By doing so, it aims to contribute to a better understanding of how the relations between different levels of government and civic action influence the man-

agement of local spatial resources.

This research adopts qualitative methods to achieve these objectives, relying on two in-depth case studies. The selection of case studies is based on geographical resemblances, shared challenges, and the diverse outcomes they have accomplished. These case studies draw upon data gathered through semi-structured interviews and secondary sources. Moreover, the research includes an analysis of the broader policy framework in which these initiatives sought to intervene.

This contribution aims to shed light on the role played by grassroots initiatives like the Pula Group and the “Srd is Ours” Initiative in the pursuit of spatial justice. By examining their tools, strategies, and outcomes, it aims to contribute to the ongoing discussion surrounding the fair and equitable distribution of spatial resources in local communities and the policy-making processes on which it depends, particularly in the context of Southern Europe and its peripheral position within the global political and economic system.

Grassroots initiatives, Privatisation, Local communities, Civic action, Southern Europe

Resistive urban spatial practices and cultures as signs of spatial justice and resilience in India: Impact of globalisation in the restructuring of Bengali Society & urban space in Kolkata from the perspective of public nuisance

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The impact of neoliberalisation in India during the 90s exposed the Indian sub-continent to various global cultures, reflecting in the politics, practices, and spatial characteristics of its cities. Globalisation brought with it both a dominant and hegemonic worldview concerning society and the environment, as well as a counter-culture that acted as a resistance to these hegemonic ideologies and cultures.

The city of Kolkata, historically known for its diverse and inclusive social fabric, underwent rapid neoliberalisation, leading to a significant impact on the socio-cultural restructuring of Bengali society and its immediate spatial manifestations. This research critically examines the concept of public nuisance, both as a tool for purging underrepresented social groups and as a resistive socio-economic and socio-cultural production in urban space, which exhibits resilience and results in the creation of hybrid geographies. These hybrid geographies raise important questions about social acceptance and tolerance of public nuisance, particularly concerning socio-spatial justice.

In the peripheries of major Indian cities, there has been a large-scale privatisation of land and infrastructure driven by the desire to create a world-class image and transform the city into a global entity. This development often leads to the creation of exclusive spaces for the managerial and technocratic elite, promoting a new globalised lifestyle. Simultaneously, the older parts of the city have undergone significant spatial transformations as property laws and building regulations are rewritten to cater to market forces. These changes aim to rapidly convert congested and dilap-

idated sections of the old city into high-value real estate, fostering an intermixing of global elites with local subaltern cultures. This results in a new form of 'bazaar-like urbanism' that emerges outside the formal domains of the state's modes of spatial production.

This 'bazaar-like urbanism' or 'jugaad urbanism' serves as an everyday resistive urban spatial practice but is often considered a source of public nuisance by both the state and the market. Ananya Roy (2009) highlights that such resistive practices, labeled as encroachments and illegal, are often met with forceful removal. However, these arguments are not consistently applied to illegal colonies, farmhouses of the elite, or commercial properties constructed on unauthorised land within the formal purview of the state.

Asher Ghertner (2015) argues that the term 'nuisance' has evolved from a 'layman's term' denoting 'sensory disgust' to a statutory instrument used to re-order urban space, resulting in large-scale eviction drives targeting slums and other informal practices. These efforts aim to achieve a 'world-class' aestheticisation of the public realm. Therefore, the research investigates how the resistive urban practices of underrepresented groups in Kolkata have formed resilient strategies to survive neoliberalisation drives that deny spatial justice.

Neoliberalisation, Globalisation, Socio-cultural restructuring, Kolkata, Resistive socio-cultural production, Land Privatisation

Fostering Spatial Justice through Climate-Resilient Design and Planning: Key findings of UCCRN Third Report on Climate and Cities (ARC3.3) and lessons from the Urban Design Climate Workshops

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An emerging body of literature is focusing on the framing of urban climate justice, particularly as it applies to justice in specific urban contexts. This emerging literature is defining how procedural, distributive, recognitional, and restorative justice are understood within the urban context and how they can be effectively implemented in spatial planning, urban design, and architecture. A section of the Planning, Architecture, and Design Element of the Third Assessment Report on Climate Change and Cities (ARC3.3) for 2022-2024, developed by the Urban Climate Change Research Network (UCCRN), is dedicated to assessing how to incorporate environmental and climate justice into architecture, urban design, and city planning. This section aims to identify emerging definitions and practices in pursuit of climate justice within urban development processes, along with potential pathways for the implementation of climate-resilient design that addresses recognition, rights, responsibilities, distribution, and procedures. The work presented here seeks to synthesize key findings from the ARC 3.3 assessment and practice-based insights gained through the UCCRN Urban Climate Design Workshops, which have been developed by UCCRN experts since 2015. These workshops aim to integrate and scale up climate change mitigation and adaptation within cities through knowledge sharing, collaboration, and action planning.

The key findings of the assessment underscore the significance of transformations within the built environment as a means to reduce existing socio-spatial inequalities and address the root causes of vulnerability. In essence, spatial transformative processes that incorporate justice and equity objectives entail both physical changes and procedural adjustments in how

spatial decisions are made and executed. This includes a revision of the rights to be upheld and the delineation of responsibilities for action. Such participatory processes are characterized by their multi-actorial, multilevel, and context-based nature, demanding high levels of engagement from the community and various stakeholders. These processes also involve the implementation of co-production models that engage policymakers, decision-makers, local communities, researchers, and both public and private sectors.

To facilitate climate-resilient design and planning, collaborative tools have been developed by UCCRN as part of the implementation of Urban Design Climate Workshops (UDCWs). These tools aim to explore synergies between the quality of life, community priorities, and evidence-based climate considerations. The UDCW Facilitation toolkit is designed to promote the co-production of knowledge among different interest groups, resulting in an alignment of climate priorities and community demands. This toolkit provides valuable resources for recognizing the tacit knowledge held by local communities and the inclusion of vulnerable groups. Various tools, including Participatory Geographic Information Systems (P-GIS) and co-design methods, have been tested in diverse geographical and institutional contexts. They contribute to the proposition of viable approaches to operationalizing climate justice in planning and design. These methods contextualize climate design and planning measures to specific locations, enhancing the resilience and equity of urban environments.

Urban climate justice, Climate-resilient design,
Participatory governance, Co-production models

The Just City in Kenya: From Conceptualisation to Implementation

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This paper tracks the conceptualization and development of the Just City in Kenya. This was an initiative of the Just City Working Group supported by the Friedrich-Ebert-Stiftung (FES). The paper elaborates how the Just City Working Group appropriated the international conceptualization of the "Just City" based on seminal works of Henry Lefebvre, the Charter of the Right to the City, David Harvey, the UN-Habitat Quito's declaration on the "social function of the city," Feinstein's Just City, among others. The paper explicates a unique collaborative process of domestication of the concept by a group of intellectuals, practitioners, social change activists, and the mass media, among others. Kenya's conceptualization of the Just City is anchored on African Socialism of "ubuntu," the progressive Constitution of Kenya 2010, and subsequent legislation - with a raft of socio-economic and environmental rights. This is the basis of the four-pillar conceptualization of "The Kenyan Right to the City" based on:

- Dignity;
- Equity and Diversity;
- Rights and responsibilities; and
- Democracy.

The paper explores different dimensions of the application of the Just City Concept in Kenya by the Just City Working Group. In "urban invisibles," the paper explains how the mainstream media was used to bring to the surface the predicaments of groups that have been "made invisible" through historical and current urban interventions, with a focus on disabled people. The paper argues that this group and other "invisibles" are missing in the urban realm not because they are not there but rather because the space has been designed to be hostile and to exclude them - an act of "invisibilization."

Further, the paper discusses how urban institutions can be used to democratize policy discourses on urbanization and the need to have inclusive processes as provided for in Kenya's Constitution and legislation. The paper discusses public transport in Kenya from a just public transport perspective, explicating the pillars of just transport, namely: availability; safe and affordable access; inclusion; human rights and equity; and sustainability.

The paper also elaborates on "just housing," arguing that this can only be achieved by focusing on the homeless and rental housing, which constitute between 70-80% of all homes in Kenya, representing inadequate housing and weak security of tenure.

Beyond individual studies, the paper delves into an elaborate application of the Just City Principles in Nakuru City. It explains how just city principles have been applied in social planning through the application of technology. It elaborates the U-Code and how it was applied in planning informal settlements in Nakuru City, achieving inclusivity in informal settlement planning for upgrading.

The paper concludes that just cities are more sustainable socio-culturally, institutionally, financially, and environmentally, and should therefore form the basis of future urban development in Kenya.

Just city in Kenya, invisible urbanism, just public transport, inclusive planning, sustainable human settlements, U-Code

Spatial Justice in Low-Income Settlements in the Global South – Using Grounded Data from Ahmedabad and Lima to Explore Thermal Comfort and Wellbeing

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Scholars have examined various aspects of spatial justice, including its theoretical foundations, measurement and practical implications. This paper contributes to studies that focus on capturing and explaining spatial inequalities and social exclusion by adopting a longitudinal lens to understand how, in the face of climate change, planning and policies on low-income housing in the Global South can lead to lock-in scenarios that maintain vulnerability and perpetuate spatial injustice. With a focus on energy and housing, it addresses a gap in knowledge regarding how housing trajectories of the urban poor relate to their energy needs over time, and the implications for vulnerability to energy poverty. There is a prevailing assumption that, with connection to electricity, a household can satisfy its energy needs and move out of energy poverty. However, this overlooks several factors at the nexus of housing and energy that can trap inhabitants in energy vulnerability and have health and wellbeing implications. Thus, this research recognises that spatial arrangements can have significant impact on people's quality of life, opportunities and well-being, and focuses more specifically on measuring thermal comfort and understanding inhabitants' practices to cope with heat stress, as well as any implications on energy consumption.

Drawing on primary research in low-income settlements in Lima and Ahmedabad, we investigate two housing processes, auto-construction and in-situ redevelopment, to critically evaluate the hypothesis that, with time, the urban poor will climb the poverty ladder, improve their living condition and wellbeing, and in turn reduce their overall vulnerability. This

research adopts quantitative and qualitative methods to capture different aspects of spatial justice: in Lima, data on indoor environmental conditions from a sample of auto-constructed houses were used to construct a calibrated urban building energy model using an open-source tool which can perform dynamic thermal simulations of multiple buildings. This model was then employed to forecast spatially distributed indoor environmental conditions across all houses in the settlements, and investigate the spatial injustice in terms of exposure to health hazards due to poor indoor thermal conditions. In Ahmedabad, household surveys, transit walks, and focus group discussions with female residents in three settlements were conducted to capture perceptions of thermal comfort and energy use behaviors of women in particular. Through this, a gendered lens could be applied which is especially relevant as women typically spend more time indoors, bearing the disproportionate burden of thermal discomfort and related issues.

By examining thermal comfort and the implications on energy access and consumption as well as social and physical wellbeing, this paper seeks to contribute to spatial justice debates as well as draw lessons for more just and sustainable futures. The institutional silos from which energy and urban planning are conventionally approached mean that critical linkages between vulnerability to energy poverty and the built environment remain overlooked. Yet, they have important lessons to offer for spatial justice debates. The findings of this research will help to inform policy and planning which seeks to improve the living conditions in low-income housing in informal settlements such as in Lima and Ahmedabad.

Spatial Justice, Energy Poverty, Low-Income Settlements
Thermal Comfort, Vulnerability

ACADEMIC

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Exploring Gendered Spatial Justice: An Analysis of Women's Safety and Urban Space in London

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This research focuses on the intricate relationship between gendered spatial justice and women's perceptions of safety within urban environments, with a specific emphasis on the city of London. Safety in urban spaces encompasses feelings of comfort, belonging, and commitment, which are influenced by both the physical environment and the interactions between individuals and their surroundings. One of the key findings highlighted in this study is the profound impact of fear on women's experiences and the perpetuation of gender disparities. Fear often results from women's unequal status within society, making it an essential aspect of understanding gender-based spatial justice. The research delves into the interplay between women's safety concerns, experiences of victimization, and their movement patterns in urban spaces. This nexus has been infrequently examined in existing literature. The study aims to shed light on pivotal events that disrupt women's spatial relationships and emphasizes how gendered power dynamics manifest in spatial exclusions. Women's subjective emotions are recognized as central in shaping the intersubjective power-related processes that influence the production of urban space. Therefore, urban design emerges as a vital tool for fostering inclusion and addressing gender-based spatial justice. By considering the impact of women's fear of violence on urban design, this research provides valuable insights into the complex interplay of socio-spatial dynamics. The research emphasizes the need to view the urban environment through a gender lens and underscores the importance of contextualization. It reveals that 'feeling unsafe' comprises descriptions of insecurity in public spaces and personal fear experiences, challenging the notion that such fear is a natural state. Despite its significant impact on women's mobility, gender-based vulnerability is often over-

looked in urban planning and design, necessitating structural changes to address women's experiences of violence. The study critically examines how women navigate public spaces while coping with messages that portray men as potential threats, despite domestic partner violence being the primary form of violence faced by women. Moreover, the research explores the spatial dimension of fear, highlighting the spatial limitations that women often face, such as staying indoors after dark or avoiding specific areas. Rather than merely identifying unsafe areas, it delves into the gendered aspects of spatiality and the production of urban space, emphasizing that women's inherent fearlessness should not be reduced to being labeled as mere 'victims.'

To achieve its research objectives, the study employs various analytical methods, including Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and KMeans analysis of geospatial data from London. The research focuses on identifying both problematic and favorable locations within the city. It conducts a detailed spatial analysis considering factors such as site enclosure relationships, road accessibility, building visual prominence, green space ratios, and Visual Geographic Analysis (VGA). These methods enable the identification of common characteristics of urban spaces that are either favorable or unfavorable to women. In conclusion, this research offers a comprehensive examination of gendered spatial justice and women's safety perceptions in London's urban spaces. It underscores the importance of adopting a holistic approach to urban design that promotes inclusivity and effectively addresses the spatial implications of gendered power dynamics. By recognizing the impact of fear and vulnerability on women's experiences and mobility, the study contributes to a better understanding of urban spaces' complexities and the role of gender in shaping them.

Gendered Spatial Justice, Women's Safety, Fear, Socio-spatial, Exclusions, London, Spatial Analysis, Feminism

A House All My Own: An intersectional reflection on the failures of post-apartheid law and policy to provide tenure security for black women in urban South Africa

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This socio-legal study focuses on the right to tenure security for Black women in urban South Africa. It acknowledges the historical landscape in which Black people could not own land under apartheid and explores how the progressive laws that have been put into place by the post-apartheid government to rectify past injustices have failed to address tenure issues pertaining to women.

The legal analysis will be focused on the Upgrading of Land Tenure Act, the Conversion Act, and the Mary Rahube case. By comparing legislation and the litigation arising therefrom, this article will create an understanding of the shortcomings of the state in addressing the issue of tenure security in a manner that adequately caters to all South Africans.

By interrogating tenure security through a gendered lens, this article will seek to problematize the development of contemporary law and policy in South Africa. It will argue that the existing interventions fail to adequately conceptualize South Africa's urban housing landscape in an intersectional manner and thus cannot address the issues women face. These laws and their sociological underpinnings highlight and have implications for important socio-political and economic issues such as belonging, equality, ownership, and gender-based violence. Lastly, it will consider how policies that try to undo social harm may recreate that same harm if policymakers do not consider the gendered aspect of property rights.

Tenure security, Black women, Urban South Africa, Apartheid legacy, Gendered perspective, Progressive legislation

Design Reparations. Harlem, New York: A Case Study

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The historical legacy of housing segregation and regulatory policies in the United States has yielded far-reaching consequences, culminating in a persistent national dearth of affordable housing, thereby exacerbating a housing crisis. The reverberations of these policies have transcended mere economic implications, as they have perpetuated and entrenched social inequalities, disproportionately affecting marginalized and minority communities. At the heart of this issue lies the intricate web of contemporary zoning regulations, which function as a principal instrument for steering urban development practices. Paradoxically, these regulations, which ostensibly serve to guide urban morphologies and spatial arrangements, have inadvertently culminated in hindrances to equitable spatial distribution and opportunities, especially in the domain of housing. This paper endeavors to explore the notion of spatial reparations, proffering a thought-provoking and transformative examination of a case study centered on Harlem, New York. By delving into historical policies, policy reform, housing market trends, and emergent spatial morphologies, this research underscores the potential of design-based interventions to stimulate meaningful policy debates and reforms. This, in turn, could serve as a strategic countermeasure to the detrimental consequences of advancing gentrification.

Housing Segregation, Regulatory Policies, Affordable
Housing, Social Inequalities, Zoning Regulations

Envisaging future cities within intersectional strategy in the Arab Region [withdrawn]

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Since the 1980s, the concept of “Intersectionality” gained prominence and became widely recognized in discussions of gender-related issues. This concept extended to the realm of gender and space, establishing the connection between gender and urban studies, both sharing a common foundation (Löv, 2006). Despite later critiques of intersectionality (Nash, 2008), the academic acknowledgment of gender intersectionality had a significant impact on education, research, and practices within spatial disciplines. This study centers on the intersections of gender and space, particularly in the context of urban public spaces, to assess the potential for gender-inclusive urban design, especially with regard to women’s safety in cities. The study aims to offer a discursive summary of the diverse experiences of heterogeneity in the Arab region and applies a socio-spatial paradigm from a theoretical and methodological standpoint. The United Nations (UN), along with other international organizations advocating for gender equality in cities, serves as a point of reference in the study’s official documents, secondary sources, and literature review, contributing to the data assembled. To gain a deeper understanding of gender inequalities in the Arab region, the study underscores intersectionality as an analytical strategy and advocates for a multidimensional perspective on gender in Arab states. It explains the concept of intersectionality and justifies its relevance to the region, detailing how this concept can be used to foster development and inclusivity. The study delves into intersectionality as a crucial theoretical framework to advance and enhance urban planning from an intersectional viewpoint, adding to ongoing debates about

the incorporation of gender mainstreaming in urban policies. It highlights the utility of intersectionality as a tool for urban planning, enabling feminist theorists to distinguish between the diverse experiences of women in the city. The paper’s structure consists of four sections: 1) Introduction to key concepts; 2) Exploration of the impact of gender on the city and how women have historically been disadvantaged by urban planning; 3) Examination of policy documents and interviews to assess the intersectionality of gender mainstreaming policies; 4) Synthesis of the results to evaluate gender planning and provide recommendations for future studies. The study employs a mixed-methods approach, analyzing significant policy documents, conducting surveys, and organizing semi-structured interviews. As a result, this study investigates the significance of intersectionality in urban design, highlighting the valuable research conducted by distinguished scholars across various disciplines, including anthropologists, geographers, architects, urbanists, and cultural theorists. It concludes that women are underrepresented in decision-making roles within the urban sector, including legislators, planners, architects, and engineers. This lack of representation and precise data collection directly impacts the urban configuration of cities. Furthermore, intersectionality has practical implications that can be harnessed for policymaking to address issues related to gender diversity.

Intersectionality, Gender and space, Urban design, Women’s safety, Arab region, Gender mainstreaming

Benchmarking inclusion in public space: A Place—and Space—Based Assessment Method

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Current urban studies often explore the concept of inclusion in public spaces through an individualistic and place-based perspective, characterized by post-occupancy evaluation. Seeking a more comprehensive understanding, this paper promotes a shift towards a group-based approach, incorporating space- and place-based methods. Digital platforms, including Google Street View, Mapillary, and similar services, offer an extensive array of urban space imagery, which provides a new prospect in the study of inclusion. Using such resources, detailed evaluations can be conducted on both group and individual bases across diverse locales and streetscapes. These images not only allow a time and context-independent evaluation but also facilitate the assessment by diverse identities and their interactions within these spaces.

In its essence, inclusion represents the alignment and compromise between an individual's intelligence and values and those of the overarching system. As individuals carry unique attributes and values, they also exist within larger collectives with shared attributes. In cities, multiple factors, such as regulations, norms, politics, and education, shape individual values, thus generating a common culture from individual intelligences. Inherently, publicness in a city embodies collective characteristics. Evaluations, therefore, should integrate group dynamics while recognizing individual experiences, particularly given the complexities introduced by overlapping social categorizations.

Examining inclusion through a space-based lens, this paper emphasizes the latent potential of public spaces, presenting a focus on prior occupancy evaluation. Anticipating occupants with various identity markers necessitates a space's adaptation for inclusive prospects, even before

its actual utilization. This anticipatory evaluation accentuates the importance of ensuring spaces are inclusive from the onset. In contrast to the space-based method, benchmarking inclusion should also embrace a place-based assessment rooted in post-occupancy evaluations. It factors in the memories, emotions, and experiences tied to a space, providing insights into the lived experiences of individuals and groups in different urban settings.

In order to conduct such an assessment, a set of images of public space should be curated for research participants. This compilation should include images from familiar locales and from unknown terrains to the participant. It should also represent the diversity of space typologies in cities, from old to new, and from high-density to low-density neighborhoods, as well as a range of affordances that a space provides. This assessment should comprise two main stages in one setting: first, participants assess each image of a public space individually. Then, they evaluate the same set of images collaboratively in a focus group format. These two stages should be distinct to ensure that the outcomes of the first stage do not impact the second. This two-stage evaluation approach offers insights into the dynamics between pre- and post-occupancy image-based evaluations. It also provides understanding of the evaluation of embodied versus non-embodied spaces, both individually and within groups. Crucially, this assessment method highlights the interplay between individual and group identities, the implications of intersectionality, and the resulting compromises that emerge during evaluations. By delving into the nuances of inclusion, it guides the creation of spaces that are inclusive and harmonious, representing the diverse identities they host.

Inclusion, Public Space, Digital Platforms, Group-based approach, Intersectionality

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Socio-spatial equity: An application of Space Syntax in analysing the spatial justice among women pedestrians in Monastir, Tunisia

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Public open space is considered a crucial resource within urban areas and local communities because it offers individuals many advantages in fostering their social, physical, and psychological well-being. A peculiar case study, a neighbourhood in Monastir (Tunisia), is helpful in challenging pedestrian mobility policies concerning the safety of public urban spaces.

This study explores the correlation between the spatial configuration of street networks in public space, as determined by the Space Syntax approach, and gender-based accessibility. Axial lines offer a methodological tool to address the impact of spatial configurations on people's movement and social interactions by applying integration and entropy attributes. We implemented a semi-structured observation methodology to approve the results of the appropriation of women in public spaces in Monastir.

The research findings reveal a correlation between examining the space layout and women's appearance in public areas. More interconnected streets attract more female pedestrians, albeit for shorter durations. The insights derived from this research have implications for spatial design interventions and policy formulation, ultimately contributing to achieving equal access to public spaces.

Public urban space, space syntax, spatial configuration, gender-based accessibility, Monastir

Mobility Justice Pedagogy for Whom? Reading urban roads beyond car usage

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Since the 1950s, there has been a growing awareness among urban planners, policy-makers, and public authorities worldwide regarding the existence of social inequalities in access to modern urban mobility infrastructure. Many cities in the global north have recognized and acted upon the need for more inclusive mobility infrastructure through policy and design initiatives. In contrast, contemporary urban roads in Indian cities tend to prioritize the movement of motorized vehicles, particularly cars, while infrastructure for non-motorized modes of transportation is often either lacking or inaccessible. It is essential to equip urban practitioners with scientific knowledge and training in inclusive mobility design to build a critical mass of professionals who prioritize and advocate for equitable streets. Schools specializing in the built environment play a significant role in introducing curricula that focus on creating infrastructures that promote social equity rather than just facilitating profit-oriented development.

In a rapidly privatized urban market environment, which has also extended to the privatization of the education sector, there is a new focus on pedagogies for social justice. Over the past two decades, the Indian higher education landscape has witnessed a substantial increase in private universities, offering more opportunities alongside the highly competitive and limited seats in public universities. Public universities are funded by the state, while the primary source of funding for private universities is student tuition fees. Studies indicate that students attending private universities typically come from families with higher financial capacities, making them finan-

cially privileged.

This paper examines the experience of teaching a group of undergraduate architecture and built environment students, who predominantly come from affluent backgrounds, to view the world through the lens of mobility justice. It explores how these students respond to their own reality of being primarily privileged car users. The analysis draws upon experience-based assignments, field notes, live project work, and interviews with students. The findings reveal that many students were able to recognize previously overlooked nuances and complexities of street life for non-car road users. Some of them also encountered the contested realities of conceptualizing inclusive streets while engaged in design studio work and stakeholder interactions. The narratives in the paper reflect the exploration of social identities, critical examination of spatial aspects, and the emergence of questions related to governance, community, and self-awareness that students experienced over the course of two semesters.

Mobility Justice, Teaching Inclusive Street Design, Questioning the Self, Teaching Social Justice to the Privileged

Public Space and Deafness: A Change of Perspective

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The everyday experience of minorities that we might call 'vulnerable,' about the majority population called 'able-bodied,' is determined by the sum of constraints, challenges and subjective needs that emerge in the practices of using and living spaces. For it to be 'easy', or even possible, to use space in an equal and equitable manner, it is necessary to bring out these difficulties, impediments, reasons, and individual specificities by combining them with the different types of vulnerability.

Within the macro theme of accessibility, the project investigates the difficult and exclusionary practices of use of public space by deaf people and points out sensorial experience, urban design that facilitates or hinders communication between deaf people and between deaf and hearing people, and the field of technologies that can bridge the gap, the inequity, and perhaps facilitate the active participation of the deaf community at the center of the research.

It is intended to overturn the clinical-pathological view of deafness through a socio-cultural and spatial perspective through the concepts of Deafhood (Ladd, 2003), Dorsal Experience (Sirvage, 2015), Deaf Gain (Bauman and Murray, 2010) and Deaf Space (Bauman, 2005) incorporates the deaf community as an active subject and unique sensory input for the design of equitable and inclusive spaces for all.

The general objective of the research is to develop methods and tools for knowledge of worst practices in urban public spaces in terms of inaccessibility, exclusion, architectural barriers and urban spatial injustice, nurturing encounters between citizens and political and research institutions, and outlining a shared pathway towards the accomplishment of the Sus-

tainable Development Goals of the 2030 Agenda (4,10,11) related to social equality, urban spatial justice, and human quality of life.

The research is conducted through a citizen science and community-based participatory approach, as only with the involvement of deaf people is it possible to understand how to move from the paradigms of modern architecture to those of organic architecture. Sirvage (deaf), like Bauman (hearing) and many others, in their research and theories, study through deep immersion in the deaf community and learning sign language and in some cases through their deafness, the real perceptual experiences they speak of.

Imagining a truly equal world means highlighting that the deaf community forms part of society with its uniqueness, history, culture and identity and that it can contribute with an original point of view to the quality of life of all humanity. It is very urgent to bring the deaf community out of its invisible state, to highlight bad/good practices in terms of accessibility, to create inclusive, identity-based communities and places and to erase erroneous beliefs.

Vulnerable Minorities, Accessibility Challenges, Deaf Community, Urban Design, Inclusive Communities

Exploring Trispaciality and Spatial Injustice in the Achievement of Economic and Social Rights: An Analysis of Spatial Barriers to Access Public Programs in Chile

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This research makes a significant contribution to the field of Spatial Justice theory (Soja, 2008; 2010a; 2010b) by conducting in-depth case studies to shed light on the role of trispaciality in the emergence of territorial injustices. Its primary objectives are to address both theoretical and empirical challenges: firstly, to explore how spatial factors perpetuate injustices and, secondly, to understand the enduring disparities in the realization of social and economic rights in Chile, despite government initiatives falling short of their intended goals. In pursuit of these objectives and drawing upon Soja's influential work (2008, 2010b), this research examines the impact of first, second, and third spaces, as well as their intricate interactions, on the fulfillment of rights. It investigates how these spatial dimensions create barriers that impede individuals from benefiting from state programs and affirmative actions designed to safeguard their rights, thereby contributing to the formation of territorial injustices. To achieve this, the study identifies three government programs aimed at ensuring access to education, healthcare, and employment. Utilizing criteria such as coverage, geographical location, temporality, co-presence, among others, the research constructs a sample encompassing three administrative units (communes) where these programs have been implemented. Qualitative sampling techniques are employed, with a specific focus on critical cases. Through this methodology, the analysis centers on specific experiences, involving interactions with the implementing units of these programs and individuals who have participated in them. The objective is to pinpoint the spatial barriers associated with the first, second, and third spaces and to

scrutinize how these barriers interconnect and collectively impact rights realization. Subsequent steps involve evaluating the trialectic operation of these barriers and assessing the injustices that stem from them. These injustices significantly limit individuals' opportunities to access programs aimed at providing, reinstating, or safeguarding their rights.

The research findings support the hypothesis that the State's failure to acknowledge the potential role of space in generating injustices, combined with the existence of spatial barriers that extend beyond mere resource distribution, results in an inadequate protection of individuals' rights, leading to a territorial shortfall. These discoveries deepen our understanding of the spatial dimensions of rights realization and advocate for a critical examination of space as a source of injustice. Furthermore, they underscore the imperative of comprehensively considering the intrinsic spatial aspects of rights, transcending mere recognition. In this context, this research stands as a valuable contribution to the evolution of potential new generations of policies and programs, enriching their conceptualization, development, implementation, and evaluation within a trispacial framework.

Rights Fulfillment, Government Programs, Spatial Barriers
Trispacial Framework, Gender-Inclusive Mobility

The growth of Oxxo retail in São Paulo, Brazil: a food gentrification analysis

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Healthy eating patterns are related to food environments, which concern the type of retail, proximity, availability, access, and type of food available (Borges; Cabral-Miranda; Jaime, 2018). Evidence suggests that current urban food environments contribute to the access to ultraprocessed foods, favoring the obesity pandemic (Machado et al., 2017; Swinburn et al., 2019). The increase in Oxxo retail in São Paulo city, Brazil, illustrates how urban food environments have been impacted by urban changes that hinder access to fresh food. São Paulo is suffering a fast process of verticalization and construction densification, without necessarily promoting diversification and improving life quality (Nakano, 2018). Such changes collaborate to boost speculation and fill the landscape with higher, more expensive, and emptier buildings (Nakano, 2018). These new neighborhoods are perfect locations for Oxxos, a convenience retail chain that has been growing rapidly and in alignment with urban changes, opening more than 100 shops in a 15-month period, starting in 2020. Its retailers mostly offer ready-to-eat ultraprocessed products, while having few or no fresh food options (Mathias, 2022), which raises concerns about access to healthy diets and urban development, since it's a driver for food gentrification. As studied by Anguelovski (2015), food gentrification is a phenomenon that takes place when transformations in the foodscape, such as the opening of "healthy food" stores, compromises the access to affordable and traditional food, privileging new and wealthier residents and paving the way for increases in real estate prices, which leads to displacement and other unjust outcomes.

Objective/methods: We sought to analyze the recent spread of Oxxo stores in São Paulo, using the Food Gentrification perspective, through literature review and secondary data on stores localization, food offer and growth strategy.

Results: The real estate development follows the infrastructure availability, occupying attractive areas, with great access to services and facilities. As pointed by Silva et al. (2020), proximity to the transportation network and job opportunities accessibility are commonly associated with gentrification trends. That's exactly the spaces where Oxxo stores are located or seek to occupy: "high traffic areas, such as around metro stations and bus terminals" (translated from portuguese) (Raízen, 2020). Therefore, Oxxo is appearing frequently in already gentrifying neighborhoods, feeding the customers with ready-to-eat meals, and focusing their marketing on the practicality and proximity (Raízen, 2020), while replacing/displacing the previous uses of the area, such as local business. Furthermore, to guarantee its success, the brand appropriated local food culture, incorporating, for example, bakeries into Brazilian units (Mathias, 2022). The rapid spread of Oxxo stores throughout São Paulo impacts the neighborhood's identity and physiognomy, placing unfamiliar structures where there once were other forms of occupation, which may interfere in the sense of belonging of local residents, especially the most vulnerable ones (Anguelovski, 2015). Oxxo's retail boom is an example of the ongoing food gentrification in São Paulo, which is changing the local food environment and favoring access to ultra-processed foods and unhealthy eating patterns.

Food Gentrification, Urban Food Environments, Oxxo Stores
Healthy Eating Patterns, Urban Development

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